

IN-HABIT – INclusive Health and Wellbeing In small and medium size ciTies

D8.16 Replicable business models to boost IHW

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Authors (names and affiliations)	Vanessa Kováčová (B4B), Cristiano Viegas (B4B), and Bianca Breveglieri (B4B)		

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HISTORY OF CHANGES

Page	Description
2	Updated the Version Log and History of changes.
5-6	The executive summary has been rewritten.
7-10	The index, list of figures and list of tables have been updated.
11-18	A new 8-page executive summary has been added to Chapter 1. It contains an overview of the IN-HABIT methodology and the 16 replicable business models, the key enabling factors for adoption and a summary of lessons learned. It also provides a replication pathway for decision-makers.
19-35	16 replicable business model factsheets have been added.
	Removed the previous chapter 1, 'Summary of the context and objectives of the in-habit project', as it was redundant with the information contained in the executive summary.
36-39	One paragraph of chapter 2 was removed, Added the contents of the previous chapter 3, "Development of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS)" to chapter 4. The clarification regarding the selection process for the 16 replicable businesses has been added.
43-44	An explanation of the transition from 10 VIS/KERs and eight incubated business models to 16 replicable business models has been added to Chapter 4.
47	The description of the B4B Tailored Inclusive Business Training has been updated (Chapter 5).
48-51	Added a dedicated Chapter (6) on the adaptation of GDEI-sensitive sub-dimensions to the selected 16 Replicable Business models.
53-57, 67-69, 82-83, 96-97, 108-109, 124-125, 137-139, and 149-152	To avoid redundancy, the descriptions of the business models implemented by the project partners and their respective key competitive advantages were transferred from Chapter 7 to Chapters 7.1 and 7.2, from Chapter 8 to Chapter 8.1, and from Chapter 9 to Chapters 9.1, 9.2 and 9.3. Chapters 11 and 11.1 were also merged.
62, 73-74, 88-89, 101-102, 116-117, 131, 143, 160, 174, 178, 181, 185, 188, 192, 195-196, and 199	Added a text on the detailed replication prerequisites for each of the 16 replicable business models, aligning it with the contents of the factsheets (Chapters 7.1, 7.2, 8.1, 9.1, 9.2, 9.3, 10.1, 11, 12.1, 12.2, 12.3, 12.4, 12.5, 12.6, 12.7, and 12.8).
169-171	All the pictures of the technology and societal readiness levels, along with their explanations, were taken from the eight business models chapters and placed in the same section of Chapter 12, providing an overview of the TRL and SRL levels of the eight solutions.
171-199	Information was added to the 8 incubated Business models, regarding the following business dimensions: 'Problem', 'Customer Segments', 'Channels', 'Customer Relations', 'Key Resources', 'Competition', 'Revenue Streams', and 'Critical Success Factors and Barriers to Implementation'.
200	Added a new chapter (13), containing the 5 detailed lessons learned from the implementation of the replicable business models.
201	The conclusions (chapter 14) have been rewritten.
217	The Reference List now includes the IN-HABIT reference documents, which can be found after the Annexes.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CA	Consortium Agreement
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication & Outreach
DC	Dissemination & Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDEI	Gender, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion
H2020	Horizon 2020 projects
IHW	Inclusive Health and Wellbeing
KLC	Key Local Contact
LCA	Local Community Activator
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Project Partner
RTD	Research, technology and development
SMSCs	Small and medium sized cities
WP	Work Package

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PARTNERS' SHORT NAMES

AVUE	Neighbourhood Association of Las Palmeras
BOT	Book on a Tree
BSC	Baltic Studies Centre
B4B	Bridge for Billions
CORD	Ayuntamiento de Córdoba
DFC	Design for Change Spain
HIDE	Hidepark Civic Association Triptych
ISIM	isIMPACT
KQ	Kalnciema Quarter
LABORELEC	Engie Laborelec
LCREA	Lucca Crea
LUCCA	Comune di Lucca
NITRA	Mesto Nitra
PUJ	Pontificia Universidad Javeriana
RIGA	Riga Planning Region
SUA	Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra
TSR	Tesseræ
UCO	University of Córdoba
UNIPI	Università di Pisa
UREAD	University of Reading
WTG	WellnessTechGroup

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable, D8.16 "Replicable Business Models to Boost Inclusive Health and Wellbeing", summarises the most promising Business models that have emerged from the **IN-HABIT Project** and have **replication potential**. This document provide Stakeholders with solutions that are contextually relevant and socially impactful. Ultimately, it provides the necessary framework for the development of their cities, contributing to a more equitable and sustainable future for all European cities.

The IN-HABIT Project was implemented in **four different small and medium sized cities in Europe: Córdoba (Spain), Lucca (Italy), Riga (Latvia), and Nitra (Slovakia)**. The purpose of the IN-HABIT Project was to identify and implement visionary solutions to increase health and well-being through the use of underutilized resources including culture; art; food; human-animal interaction; and urban rewilding, while ensuring that gender, diversity, and equity were embedded as cross-cutting principles.

The **16 replicable business models** outlined in this report were chosen after a thorough assessment. Of those models, **eight came from pilot projects conducted by the IN-HABIT Partners'** team which focused on a number of topics including animal-assisted therapy, vocational training programs for people with disabilities, bike-share programs, reviving food markets and environmental monitoring. The remaining **eight models were selected from the B4B Inclusive Business Incubator Programme** by the **Bridge for Billions (B4B) Team**, one model per pilot city with a focus on six themes (sustainable food systems, mental health, rural development, circular economy, and digital skills); these models show how underutilized resources can be used to enhance inclusive well-being through a variety of methods.

Decision-makers can use the models in order to develop practical solutions that can be used in conjunction with some EU initiatives i.e., European Green Deal, One Health initiative and Urban Agenda for the EU. Communities will have new opportunities to build on their community based social cohesion and reduce their levels of isolation; thus, enabling them to adopt healthier lifestyle choices. The models represent avenues for entrepreneurs to pursue socially inclusive business ventures; therefore, allowing for new venture creation with both an economic and a social value.

The **portfolio was developed using a Dual-Stream innovation selection methodology**. This methodology is designed to ensure that both the level of institutional robustness of the candidate innovations and the level of entrepreneurial agility of the candidate innovations were considered when evaluating the potential for success. Using the Societal Readiness Level (SRL), and Technology Readiness Level (TRL) methodologies, the B4B Team and the Partners' Consortium evaluated the candidate innovations to ensure that they had reached a mature level of readiness. The data that was collected was obtained through the completion of self-assessment questionnaires by the innovators, participation in collaborative workshops with the pilot partners, and the application of the Social Business Model Canvas to map the business model for each of the solutions presented.

Target Audience

- Municipal and regional authorities.
- Public health agencies, urban planners, and social innovation practitioners.
- Local stakeholders engaged in urban social transformations.

- Social organisations.
- SMEs and Entrepreneurs

Disclaimer:

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR): While the conceptual ideas and business models presented in this deliverable are shared openly to inspire and guide potential adopters, it is important to note that “ideas” and “methods” in the abstract are not protectable under intellectual property law. What is protectable, and therefore subject to the project’s permission for replication, are the concrete expressions of those ideas: the software code, written content, visual designs, datasets, brand names, logos, and other tangible outputs developed by IN-HABIT. These are safeguarded through a combination of copyright, Community design rights, sui generis database rights, and the IN-HABIT EU trademark. This legal protection does not prevent third parties from developing their own solutions inspired by these models; however, the direct reuse of IN-HABIT’s protected materials, branding, or data requires compliance with the applicable licences (e.g., Apache 2.0, Creative Commons) or, where relevant, a commercial agreement. This approach strikes a balance between encouraging the broad uptake of IN-HABIT’s innovations and ensuring that any replication remains aligned with the project’s quality standards, social mission, and sustainability goals.

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1. EXECUTIVE SYNTHESIS

The Executive Synthesis describes and compares the 16 selected Replicable business models and describes the requirements to implement these new solutions for an interested follower-city that faces a similar problem at a local level. The document is organized in six parts: the methodology used in IN-HABIT; the portfolio of the 16 replicable business models; the procedure of the selection of the 16 business models; the main factors facilitating the implementation of the 16 selected Replicable business models; a Summary of Lessons Learned from Replicable Business Models; and finally, a "Replication Pathway" to help decision-makers to navigate in the document.

1.1. THE IN-HABIT METHODOLOGY

A participatory approach called CO-CO-CO-CO (co-creation, co-deployment, co-management, and co-monitoring) was used to develop solutions for IN-HABIT. By embedding GDEI principles, this approach supports the development of networks, structural dialogue, and cross sectoral collaboration. A list of the GDEI-sensitive, adapted IN-HABIT IHW sub-dimensions with the Replicable Business Models can be found in the Factsheets and in Chapter 6, which provides an in-depth analysis.

The IN-HUB is a laboratory for social innovation where people from the public and private sector and as citizens collaborate in order to create new opportunities for social development. IN-HUB has a polycentric and participative governance structure with three operating levels: 1) Steering Committee: Determines the social needs to be addressed and the possible solutions; it is made up of residents and community organizations, 2) Operation: Companies, institutions and local authorities responsible for determining if a solution is feasible and for providing the necessary expertise and resources, and 3) Support: Partnerships and networks (that do not have an operational role) that can contribute by promoting the work of the IN-HUB, by endorsing its activities, and by developing occasional collaborative projects¹.

Two forms of output were generated through the IN-HABIT project:

- KERs (Key Exploitable Results): The tangible results of the project which are grouped according to their innovation and potential for positive effects in terms of both economy and society as well as innovation capacity (e.g., workshops, cultural events, healthy behaviours, education, or animal-assisted services).
- VIS (Visionary and Integrated Solutions): These include combinations of "soft" solutions involving social-cultural action with "hard" solutions involving nature-based solutions (NBS) and infrastructure, and digital technologies (e.g., renovated public areas, green infrastructure, multi-purpose markets).

¹ For more information about the IN-Habit methodology, please refer to Annex 1 of Deliverable D1.5 (Upscaling Plan of Las Palmeras): "Methodological Guide".

1.2. PORTFOLIO OVERVIEW: THE 16 REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS

To make it easier for decision-makers to find a suitable model in this portfolio, the 16 replicable business models have been categorized according to their focus, urban challenges solved, stream of innovation, and description.

Due to the need to protect intellectual property as well as sensitive business know-how, the detailed business models from Stream B have been anonymized. Anonymization will allow the replicability and potential impact to be analysed while protecting the interests and originality of the participating entrepreneurs.

Table 1 - Replicable Business Models

Focus	Urban Challenge	Innovation Name	Stream	Description
Transversal 	Lack of Wellbeing Data	IN-HABIT Data Platform	A	An open-source (FIWARE) web-based interface (dashboard) that combines both social and environmental data from sensors to measure the impact of IHW.
	Disadvantaged women capacity building	B4B tailored inclusive Business training	A	An innovative and interdisciplinary incubation curriculum which enables socially excluded people to become social entrepreneurs.
Culture & Heritage (Córdoba) 	Neurodiversity Unemployment	Immersive Experience Training	A	Software training program that provides an immersive experience for individuals with Down syndrome, enhancing their employability by simulating realistic work environment settings.
	Underuse of domestic spaces for healthy food production	Urban Farming Kits (Project SP-01)	B	Modular kits that enable low-income families to cultivate food in densely populated urban environments (patios).
	Rural Depopulation	Rural Co-Living Hubs (Project SP-02)	B	Using vacant rural assets to create a new way for digital nomads to live and contribute to the economic growth of rural communities.
Food & Sustainability (Riga) 	Urban Market Decay	The Āgenskalns Food Market	A	An urban marketplace that can be used by all, designed to promote inclusive health and well-being.
	Food Supply Chain Disconnect	Food Digital platform (Project LV-01)	B	The Digital platform that connects small-scale food producers in rural areas to urban consumers that want to purchase fresh, healthy, and traceable food.
	Unhealthy Consumption	Sustainable Functional Beverages (Project LV-02)	B	Plant-based functional beverages made with locally sourced Nordic ingredients.

Focus	Urban Challenge	Innovation Name	Stream	Description
Human-animal bond (Lucca) 	Lack of Humanimal policy services	Humanimal urban policy design centre (HADUP centre)	A	Consultancy service developing "human-animal" urban policies to help cities develop a system that includes pets as part of their public welfare systems.
	Elderly Isolation	Animal Assisted Interventions (AAI)	A	Therapeutic services certified to provide treatment to the elderly using animals, addressing issues of social isolation and cognitive decline in care home settings.
	Disadvantaged Pet Owners	Pet Care Services	A	Services that assist disadvantaged pet owners to reduce the risk of abandoning their pets and enable them to live independently.
	Fragmented Vet Care	Digital Pet Health Record (Project IT-01)	B	Database of veterinary information to assist pet owners to easily obtain care for their pets.
	Neurodiversity Support	Music & Animal Therapy (Project IT-02)	B	Combining music therapy with animal interaction for neurodiverse children.
Art and Environment (Nitra) 	Sustainable Transportation	Community Bike Sharing	A	Circular mobility scheme using refurbished bicycles managed by community associations to empower local residents through co-design, circular resource use and promoting an active lifestyle.
	Underused Natural Assets	Eco-Cycle Tourism (Project SK-01)	B	Services for bicycle tourists along greenways, utilizing local heritage.
	Textile Waste	Circular Wool Textiles (Project SK-02)	B	Upcycling raw materials (wool) generated from processing local wool to produce high value textiles.

1.3. PORTFOLIO SELECTION RATIONALE

The outcome of the selection process was a portfolio of 16 reproducible business models which were a combination of those created through the IN-HABIT consortium partners and the B4B Inclusive Business incubation program. For additional details on this, please refer to Chapter 3.

Replicable Business Models Assessment Criteria

1. Alignment with the Grant Agreement (GA)

- Integration of solutions with commercial and revenue generation potential The emphasis on financial sustainability provides decision-makers with models that are financially sustainable and potentially reduce the need for long-term reliance on public subsidies²:

² In line with Annex 1 to the GA Amendment, this Report provides the "traditional elements of a business model", detailing cost structures and revenue streams.

- Integration of incubated projects business models from the B4B Inclusive Business Incubation Program. Through the integration of the incubated projects with the city-led systematic innovations the portfolio provides a balanced 'top-down' and 'bottom-up' toolkit³. These business case examples have been evaluated using an evaluation matrix that has been applied across the four pilot cities as a way to assess their ability to be transferred and used by other organizations in the future. Two Replicable Business models were selected per city, based on factors such as social/economic viability, the ability to be replicated, and strategic alignment with IHW, covering the entire range of wellbeing innovations, including both digital and place-based, and service and product.

2. Selection of Business Models developed using a "Dual-Stream"

- Stream A (IN-HABIT Consortium Partners Solutions): Based on the preliminary results from the meeting of the IN-HABIT partners aimed to define the exploitation potential of in-habits solutions⁴, The B4B Team performed an additional analysis of the replication potential and innovation maturity of each solution using. This involved distributing Surveys to the IN-HABIT Partners and having discussions with them.
- Stream B (Business Cases Developed in the B4B Inclusive Business Incubation Programme): Of the 179 Projects and 223 Entrepreneurs supported by the B4B Inclusive Business Incubation Programme, the B4B Team strategically selected and analysed a representative portfolio of business case models (two per city). The Business cases were evaluated using a standardized evaluation matrix across all four pilot cities to identify the business cases that are high in transferability and value to external adopters. The curated portfolio provides the full spectrum of wellbeing innovation including place-based, digital, service, and product driven solutions, ensuring a diverse and mature set of reference cases.

3. Innovation maturity

To determine the most mature Replicable Business models, the team used two differing levels of maturity in order to account for each stream's individual path of development. Thus, the team targeted more developed solutions for Stream A, while targeting solutions in the early stages of development in Stream B. As a result, the final portfolio ranges across Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) and Societal Readiness Levels (SRL), Levels 5 through 9. Therefore, the final portfolio consists of a variety of validated innovations as well as solutions that have been assessed and proven in real-world operating environments.

Technology Readiness Levels (TRL):

³ The distribution of the portfolio reflects the particular mandate for Task 8.4 that requires consolidating the most promising business models developed in the course of the B4B Inclusive Business incubation programme.

⁴ As described in "Deliverable D8.14 Market analysis and preliminary exploitation strategies", a series of participatory workshops have been held for assessing and classifying the outputs of the pilot cities of IN-HABIT based on their exploitation potential. A second objective of these workshops is to identify and evaluate KERs and VIS that could be exploited commercially.

- Solutions based upon digital and technical technologies within Stream A were selected from TRL level 7 (System Prototype Demonstration in an Operational Environment) up to TRL level 9 (Actual System Proven in Operational Environment)⁵.
- Solutions based upon digital and technical technologies within Stream B were selected from TRL level 5 (Technology Validated in Relevant Environment) up to TRL level 9 (Actual System Proven in Operational Environment)⁶.

Societal Readiness Levels (SRL):

- The models within Stream A were selected using an SRL level of 6; thus, validating that the solutions had transitioned from theoretical validation into having been successfully demonstrated in a relevant environment with various stakeholders.
- The models within Stream B were selected with an SRL level of 5 to allow for identification of the highest potential grassroots innovation available. With SRL 5, it is assumed that the solutions have been validated by relevant stakeholders in the solution’s target area, and although the actual large-scale demonstration of the solution may not yet be complete, it acknowledges the fact that the demonstration process may still be in progress.

This process resulted in 18 Replicable business models (10 from Stream A and 8 from Stream B). However, the three business models developed in Riga were consolidated into one single replicable business model called "Āgenkalns food market". Therefore, the number of replicable business models fell to 16, with an equal split between Stream A and Stream B.

1.4. KEY ENABLING FACTORS FOR ADOPTION

Before investing in a specific intervention, you have to consider the local situation for your intervention. The key enabling factors are conditions required to reduce risks arising when implementing an intervention. More detailed information about the key enabling factors per solution can be found in the factsheet "replication prerequisites" (after Chapter 1), or in the business model extensive analysis in Chapters 7 – 12.

Table 2 - Key Enabling Factors for Adoption of Replicable business models.

#	Innovation Name	Key Enabling Factors for Adoption
1	IN-HABIT Data Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Enabler: Citizen science frameworks help to foster public trust. • Technical Enabler: Adoption of FIWARE standards provides a means to achieve seamless and plug-and-play integration with existing city legacy systems. • Administrative Enabler: Staff can use real-time dashboards to develop evidence-based health policy.

⁵ These assets were developed as part of an iterative process of co-design and co-deployment over the duration of the project. Because these assets are likely to be at a later developmental stage than those being tested in the other three portfolios, it can be assumed that they will also have a higher TLR threshold.

⁶ The B4B Inclusive Business Incubator programme portfolio of projects was generated through a short, intense process of development. As such, they are likely to be at a medium level of maturity and require a medium TLR threshold.

#	Innovation Name	Key Enabling Factors for Adoption
2	B4B tailored inclusive Business training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Enabler: Partnership with local NGOs are necessary to build trust between disadvantaged groups who are difficult to reach and the program. • Technical Enabler: Using a combination of digital tools and in person mentoring will enable the program to overcome participant's lack of digital literacy. • Operational Enabler: Tailoring curriculum content to fit the cultural and economic context of locale ensures relevance and decrease dropout rates.
3	Immersive Experience Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Partnering: Working with neurodiversity experts will help ensure that the user experience of the program meets the specific cognitive needs of individuals. • Ecosystem Integration: Employer Securing buy-in from employers will validate the effectiveness of the simulation. • Technical Enabler: The immersive experience training will require the use of high-performance tablets and reliable internet to sustain the immersive environment.
4	Urban Farming Kits (Project SP-01)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational Enabler: Partnering with schools will turn kits into valuable educational tools for promoting long term community health education. • Cultural Enabler: Aligning the program with the local food system and its historical roots will allow citizens to reconnect with sustainable food choices. • Technical Enabler: Use of small spaces such as balconies and minimal amounts of equipment will make urban farming available to everyone.
5	Rural Co-Living Hubs (Project SP-02)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic Digital & Physical Infrastructure: Broadband internet and historic building infrastructure will serve as the backbone for the rural hubs to function. • Alignment with Supportive Legal Frameworks: Nomad visas and tax incentives will serve to reduce barriers associated with renovating homes in rural areas. • Local Ecosystem Integration & Placemaking: Packages created with local citizens will ensure that they are able to integrate into the community in a meaningful way.
6	The Āgenskalns Food Market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic PPPP Governance & Tenure: Long-term leases will allow for the security of private investment while allowing community governance of the asset. • Cross-Subsidized Hybrid Revenue Model: Commercial rents must subsidize social programs to balance profit with impact in the community. • Multifunctional Regulatory Flexibility: Flexible zoning regulations must allow for the mixing of commerce, culture, and education in one heritage space.
7	Food Digital platform (Project LV-01)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Logistics Network: Success will rely on having dependable last mile delivery partners to link rural farms to urban consumers. • Producer Network A strong network of small-scale farmers willing to sell their produce using digital sales platforms is essential. • Cold Chain Infrastructure: Access to temperature-controlled logistics will be crucial in ensuring the safe transportation of perishable foods.
8	Sustainable Functional Beverages (Project LV-02)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer Awareness: Success will depend on a market segment of consumers that are willing to pay a premium for sustainable and functional product attributes. • Supply Chain Resilience: Reliable sourcing of high-quality and plant-based raw materials will be critical to the operational stability of the business. • Regulatory Adherence: Market entry will require strict compliance with food safety and organic certification standards.
9	Humanimal urban policy design centre	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural Shift: Institutions will need to change their view of animals as a public good (i.e., something to benefit society) versus private property. • Cross-Departmental Cooperation: Breaking down departmental silos between urban planning, health and environmental departments will be necessary.

#	Innovation Name	Key Enabling Factors for Adoption
	(HADUP centre)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific Validation: University partnerships will provide the evidence base to legitimize human-animal policies.
10	Animal Assisted Interventions (AAI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional Competence: Certified therapist and trained animal access will be the number one operational requirement. • Sustainable Funding: health budgets will need to commission Animal-Assisted Interventions (AAI) as legitimate forms of care to ensure sustainable funding. • Regulatory Framework: National accreditation standards for animal handlers and animals will be important to ensure safety and quality.
11	Pet Care Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust Networks: Strong relationships with social services will be important to identify disadvantaged users without stigma. • Operational Capacity: A strong network of vetted volunteers or professionals will be required to deliver reliable and affordable care. • Inter-Agency Collaboration: Collaboration between health authorities and animal welfare organizations will ensure an integrated approach to policy development.
12	Digital Pet Health Record (Project IT-01)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SME Digital Adoption: Success will rely on providing digital tools to guide offline Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in adopting centralised service management models. • Standardised Integration: Integration will require clinics to accept standardized digital records that support seamless data portability. • Compliant Infrastructure: Replication of the program will require a rapid development of a modular and multilingual architecture that supports strict GDPR compliance.
13	Music & Animal Therapy (Project IT-02)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdisciplinary Human Capital: Success will depend on hiring a workforce with a combination of skills related to clinical music therapy and animal handling. • Institutional Access Agreements: Adoption will require formal access agreements with care facilities to permit the introduction of animals for therapeutic purposes. • Mixed Funding Architecture: Financial sustainability will rely on a blended funding model that combines public health budget funding with philanthropic support.
14	Community Bike Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Stewardship: A local non-government organization (NGO) responsible for managing the physical aspects of the operation and preventing vandalism. • Circular Supply Chain: Success will depend on a continuous supply of bicycles and bicycle parts for low-cost circular refurbishment. • Safe Physical Infrastructure: The creation of safe cycling routes that connect the bike station to the larger city cycling network will be important.
15	Eco-Cycle Tourism (Project SK-01)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated Infrastructure: Existing regional cycling networks will be necessary to plan safe routes and ensure user safety. • Local Ecosystem Collaboration: Collaboration with local producers and tourism boards will be important to provide a stable source of materials and cross promotion. • Regional Branding: Regional identity will be important to successfully promote the cycling route.
16	Circular Wool Textiles (Project SK-02)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste Stream Access: Success will depend on reliable collaboration with local farmers to obtain underutilized raw wool waste. • Processing Capacity: Local access to skilled artisans and processing facilities will be important to convert raw wool into textile products. • Conscious Consumer Demand: Viability will depend on the existence of a consumer market that is willing to pay a premium for sustainable, locally produced heritage goods.

1.5. SUMMARY OF TRANSVERSAL LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODEL

The following transversal lessons learned were derived from an analysis of 16 business models across (see Chapter 13 for further details).

- **Hybrid value creation and financial resilience:** Sustainability depends on cross subsidisation, whereby socially driven goals are funded through commercially viable activity; with any surplus generated is reinvested, rather than being distributed. In order to remain sustainable, organisations will need to develop a diversified revenue model incorporating grants, service fees, and corporate sponsorship.
- **Governance as a Replication Enabler and Risk-mitigation tool:** Agile governance through polycentric partnerships (people/public/private) can help reduce the risk associated with rigid municipal leadership. Additionally, when stakeholders participate in the physical deployment of a solution (i.e. co deployment), they develop a greater sense of ownership of the product/solution.
- **Implementation capacity matters:** Success in replicating the model depends on the local organization's capacity to facilitate onboarding; coordinate; and provide follow up services; particularly if the solution model requires behaviour change; community engagement; or the establishment of new routine behaviours.
- **Institutional anchoring to support regulatory and administrative conditions:** Projects require strategic alignment with public authorities. Initiatives should endeavour to create Memoranda of Understanding (MoU's) or 'regulatory sand boxes' to enable operation beyond the boundaries of standard regulatory constraints, thereby overcoming bureaucratic inertia.
- **Modular Scalability and Context Sensitive Transfer:** Most replicable models deploy a MVP strategy to grow incrementally (i.e., in modules), as opposed to attempting to deploy city wide infrastructure projects simultaneously, resulting in potential budgetary overruns and public resistance.

1.6. A REPLICATION PATHWAY FOR DECISION-MAKERS

To identify which solutions will help decision makers and follower cities achieve their city's strategic vision, decision makers and follower cities should use an Identify-Assess-Enabling approach:

1. **Identify** (Alignment of Strategic Goals): Review the portfolio overview in section 1.2 to select the IN-HABIT solution that is the best fit for the city's urban challenges.
2. **Assess** (Feasibility Study): Review the key enabling factors for implementation (Section 1.4), the transversal business model lessons learned (Section 1.5), and review the 16 business model fact sheets (after this section) to determine if the solution has strategic alignment with the city. If you have any questions regarding the suitability of the solution for the city, please refer to the extensive analysis of the replicable business model provided in Chapters 7 to 12.
3. **Enabling** (Prepare the Ecosystem): Before implementing the chosen solution, create a detailed and comprehensive business plan tailored to the context, challenges and target groups of the city.

REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS FACTSHEETS

- 1 IN-HABIT DATA PLATFORM
- 2 B4B TAILORED INCLUSIVE BUSINESS TRAINING
- 3 IMMERSIVE EXPERIENCE TRAINING
- 4 URBAN FARMING KITS (PROJECT SP-01)
- 5 RURAL CO-LIVING HUBS (PROJECT SP-02)
- 6 THE ĀGENSKALNS FOOD MARKET
- 7 FOOD DIGITAL PLATFORM (PROJECT LV-01)
- 8 SUSTAINABLE FUNCTIONAL BEVERAGES (PROJECT LV-02)
- 9 HUMANIMAL URBAN POLICY DESIGN CENTRE (HADUP CENTRE)
- 10 ANIMAL ASSISTED INTERVENTIONS (AAI)
- 11 PET CARE SERVICES
- 12 DIGITAL PET HEALTH RECORD (PROJECT IT-01)
- 13 MUSIC & ANIMAL THERAPY (PROJECT IT-02)
- 14 COMMUNITY BIKE SHARING & STATION
- 15 ECO-CYCLE TOURISM (PROJECT SK-01)
- 16 CIRCULAR WOOL TEXTILES (PROJECT SK-02)

Value Proposition

Using citizen science to study how environmental factors impact health and well-being this comprehensive digital platform provides an adaptable and scalable infrastructure. The modular structure of this flexible architecture was designed with long-term use in mind and supports the integration of real time and historic data from multiple data sources into personalized dashboards for decision makers and researchers. Additionally, by supporting open standards (such as FIWARE and NGS-LD) it allows for easier discovery, access, and sharing of data thereby maximizing its potential reuse for both research and public policy.

Key Activities

- **Development and management of the platform:** The continuous development and management of the platform.
- **Data Collection and Integration:** Collecting and integrating a variety of data on a continuous basis using different methods.
- **Data Visualization and Analysis:** Interpreting and monitoring the relevant qualitative and quantitative parameters by processing and displaying the data collected.
- **Deploying sensor networks:** These are physical devices including street sensors and cameras which will collect data.

Cost Structure

- **Infrastructure and equipment:** The cost of developing apps, cloud maintenance, and purchasing hardware (sensors and cameras)
- **Sensor network operations:** The costs for deploying and maintaining the devices that measure air quality, noise, temperature, and traffic flow
- **Personnel:** The salaries of the teams working on the project
- **Communication:** Budget for marketing materials, website management, and social media campaigns.

Revenue Streams

- **This platform generates potential revenue streams from subscription fees for accessing the platform.**

Partnerships

- **Pilot City Leads:** The individuals and/or organizations that support the local implementation.
- **Local Entities:** Municipal entities and public institutions in the pilot cities.
- **Technical Partners:** Organizations specializing in developing software and managing sensor hardware.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Data Stewards:** A technical team that manages the architecture of the system to ensure continuous and accurate data flow.
- **Analysts:** Municipality employees trained to interpret dashboard data and convert the data into actions for urban planning decisions.
- **Data Protection Officer (DPO):** An individual responsible for ensuring that all data collected from citizens is compliant with GDPR.

Processes

- **Data Management Plan:** A formal plan to ensure that data is collected and shared in a manner that ensures it is Findable, Accessible, and Reusable (FAIR principles).
- **Interoperability Protocols:** Standard APIs to allow for seamless communication between the platform and existing city systems to avoid vendor lock-in.
- **Maintenance Routine:** Scheduled process to check the physical sensor network to prevent data gaps

Other requisites

- **Cloud infrastructure:** Scalable hosting (for example: AWS or equivalent on premises solutions) that can handle large amounts of data processing and storage.
- **IoT network:** Deployed network of sensors (for example: environmental and presence sensors) that communicates with standard protocols.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 9 - the technology has been used in an operational environment
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 7 - the solution is currently being refined and tested in a relevant environment with relevant stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Safety, and Spatial Well-being.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 7.1 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

2 - B4B tailored inclusive Business training

Solution developed by the IN-HABIT consortium partners

Value Proposition

An entrepreneurial training model adaptable to local circumstances for people who have historically been excluded from mainstream business support, including women and under-represented groups. The business model incorporates both practical business learning and confidence building, mentoring, and community support and can be delivered in formats that are responsive to local realities (i.e., in-person, online, hybrid). The model addresses barriers to entry, such as limited digital skills, lack of devices, time constraints, and limited access to networks so that participants can move from an idea to an action and connect into their local ecosystems.

Key Activities

- Accessibility & inclusivity of delivery: low-barrier communication (ex. WhatsApp voice notes), flexible scheduling, practical learning-by-doing.
- Curriculum localization: content reflecting local context, literacy levels and levels of preparedness of participants (e.g. language, examples, and pace).
- Mentorship & Coaching: one-on-one and small group support for building confidence, establishing structure, and creating accountability.
- Integration into Local Ecosystem: connections to local partners, services, and opportunities (potential customers, potential mentors, potential business support).
- Continuous Improvement: feedback mechanisms and light monitoring to improve the next cohort.

Cost Structure

- People: Trainers/Facilitators, Mentors, Outreach/Community Engagement, Coordination.
- Delivery: Venues, Materials, Translation/Adaptation, Participant Support Measures (as necessary).
- Tools: Simple communication and basic data tracking to monitor.

Revenue Streams

- Revenue streams include Product/Service Sales; Grants; Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR); Donations.

Partnerships

- Community Organizations/NGO's: Access, Trust-Building, Recruitment, On-The-Ground-Support.
- Municipalities/Public Agencies: Funding, Legitimacy, Inclusion & Employment Pathways.
- Educational Institutions: Co-Management Support, Venues, Training Expertise, Evaluation.
- Private Sector/COR Partners: Mentoring, Sponsorship, Equipment, Micro-Support.
- Mentorship Networks: Business Expertise and Follow-Up Support.

Replication prerequisites

People

- Community Activators (Trusted Local Connectors)
- Facilitators Trained in Inclusive Delivery
- Local Mentors/Coaches.

Processes

- Inclusive Recruitment via Grassroots Networks.
- Flexible Delivery Options (In-Person/Online/Hybrid) Based on Digital Readiness.
- Locally Relevant Materials (Language + Cultural Fit).
- Basic Post-Training Follow-Up.

Other requisites

- Options for Basic Digital Access (Devices/Access to Devices via Community).
- Adapted/Translated Curriculum and Templates.

Additional assessment indicators

- Technology Readiness Level: 0 - Non-Technological Solution (TRL Not Applicable).
- Societal Readiness Level: 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-Dimensions: Employment; Financial Situation; Equality; Social Inclusion.

For additional information regarding mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 11 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW."

Value Proposition

The Immersive Training Experience (ITE) is a serious game designed to help adults with Down's syndrome to train as hosts for conferences and events. This digital tool simulates real-life tasks, such as reception duties, catering and seating, helping users to practise routines, improve their memory and build their confidence. By combining gameplay with guided practice, the programme prepares participants to apply their skills in real work settings, creating genuine employment opportunities under standard.

Key Activities

- **Content creation:** Designing engaging, realistic training scenarios based on actual event locations and city themes.
- **App maintenance:** Regularly updating the tablet application to ensure smooth performance.
- **User Support:** Conducting onboarding sessions to familiarise users with the app and the learning process.
- **Evaluation:** Using data analytics to measure the programme's effectiveness and impact.
- **Marketing:** Promoting the programme to employers to increase job placement opportunities.

Cost Structure

- **Content production:** Costs for scripting, designing hyper-realistic 3D environments and creating interactive elements, including avatars and voice-overs.
- **Development and maintenance:** Expenses for software coding, platform hosting, technical support and regular updates.
- **Personnel:** Salaries for project managers, developers and the university research team.
- **Tests:** Costs associated with testing the app with participants from Down's syndrome associations.
- **Operations:** Marketing campaigns, office overheads and administrative costs.

Revenue Streams

Potential Revenue Streams Include Licensing and Grants.

Partnerships

University Research Team: Provided academic expertise and co-authored the user manual.

Software Developer: A software company responsible for building and hosting the immersive platform.

Down Syndrome association: essential to enable the project, provide professional insight and coordinate pilot testing with members.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Psychologists/Social Workers:** To guide users through emotional aspects of training.
- **Corporate Partners:** HR departments in event companies committed to offering internships/jobs to graduates.
- **Tech Support:** IT personnel to manage updates and assist with hardware issues.

Process

- **'Easy Reading' Methodology:** Ensures Instructions Meet Cognitive Accessibility Standards.
- **Repetitive Learning:** Gamified Learning Process Uses Structured Repetition to Consolidate Skills.
- **Accompanied placement:** Protocol for Transitioning Participants From Virtual Training to Real-World Employment With On-Site Supervision.

Other requisites

- **Hardware:** Tablets with Sufficient RAM (4 GB+), Specific Processors (Snapdragon) to Run the Immersive Environment Smoothly.
- **High-Speed Internet:** ac

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level: 6** - indicating that the solution has been validated through pilot testing in a relevant environment.
- **Societal Readiness Level: 7** - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Employment; Job and Skill Satisfaction; Social Inclusion.

Value Proposition

This initiative empowers city residents, families and community groups to grow their own food using accessible home-growing kits and practical educational activities. By adapting farming tools for small urban spaces, it reduces barriers to entry and strengthens ecological awareness, food literacy and personal well-being. The core offering combines:

- **Practical tools:** DIY kits designed for growing food in limited indoor or outdoor spaces.
- **Educational guidance:** Expert instruction delivered through workshops and learning materials.
- **Collective learning:** Experiences that foster social cohesion and shared responsibility for sustainability.

Key Activities

- **Product development:** Designing and producing DIY gardening kits that are suitable for small urban spaces and are made from sustainable materials.
- **Education:** Creating educational content on food cultivation and ecology and delivering workshops for schools and families.
- **Operations:** Managing the sourcing of materials, logistics and distribution of kits.
- **Outreach:** Promoting the initiative through community events, markets and digital channels.
- **Sales coordination:** Managing direct sales (B2C) and educational service contracts (B2B).

Cost Structure

- **Development:** Costs for designing prototypes, creating educational materials and planning workshops.
- **Production:** Expenses for purchasing sustainable materials and assembling the kits.
- **Operations:** Logistics, distribution and personnel costs for workshop facilitators.
- **Marketing:** Initial outreach and communication campaigns.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through Business-to-Consumer (B2C) sales of gardening kits and Business-to-Business (B2B) educational service contracts with municipalities and schools.

Partnerships

- **Educational institutions:** Schools and colleges that implement the workshops.
- **Public bodies:** Municipalities and cultural centres that commission educational activities.
- **Community groups:** NGOs and local organisations working with families and disadvantaged groups.
- **Sustainability networks:** Community gardens and environmental educators who contribute content and support.

Replication prerequisites

- Availability of small-scale urban spaces suitable for home growing.
- Access to basic sustainable materials and simple production capacities.
- Educational partners willing to integrate food literacy into their programmes.
- Municipal or institutional support for community-based learning activities.
- Demand for hands-on sustainability education among urban populations.
- Capacity to adapt kits and pedagogy to local climate and cultural contexts.
- Moderate initial funding for product development and outreach.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 2 - indicating that the solution is a technology concept.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** The solution did not explicitly target this.

Value Proposition

This initiative revitalises underused rural buildings by converting them into hybrid co-living and co-working spaces. It caters for remote workers, creative professionals, and others seeking a slower pace of life, connection to nature, and meaningful social interaction. By combining flexible accommodation with professional workspaces and wellbeing activities, the project fosters community engagement and contributes to the regeneration of rural areas.

Key Activities

- **Property development:** renovating and adapting rural properties for reuse.
- **Operations:** Managing accommodation, workspaces and on-site guest services.
- **Experience design:** organising cultural, wellbeing and community events, as well as local nature and food experiences.
- **Community building:** Facilitating connections between residents, local stakeholders and neighbours.
- **Marketing:** Promoting the spaces through digital nomad platforms and coordinating with tourism networks.

Cost Structure

- **Capital and setup:** Costs for property acquisition (or leasing), renovation, furnishing and installing high-speed internet infrastructure.
- **Operations:** Ongoing expenses for maintenance, utilities and platform fees.
- **Personnel:** Salaries for staff managing guest services and community facilitation.
- **Marketing:** Budget for branding, market entry and event delivery.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through medium-term accommodation rentals and workspace rentals. Additional revenue streams include the sale of event tickets and local experience packages.

Partnerships

- **Public bodies:** Rural municipalities and regional regeneration agencies.
- **Local economy:** farmers, artisans and service providers offering authentic local products and experiences.
- **Networks:** Regional tourism boards and digital nomad platforms.
- **Facilitators:** Experts in culture and wellbeing who deliver on-site programming.

Replication prerequisites

- **Infrastructure:** Access to suitable rural properties with permission for adaptive reuse.
- **Connectivity:** Reliable high-speed internet is essential for remote working.
- **Local ecosystem:** A community capable of providing authentic local experiences (food, nature, culture).
- **Capital and management:** Funding for renovation and the capacity to manage hospitality and community dynamics.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 2 - indicating that the solution is a technology concept.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 5 - indicating that the solution has been validated by relevant stakeholders in the area.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Housing; Spatial Well-being.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.2 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This multifunctional urban marketplace transforms public spaces into accessible, safe and vibrant community health and wellbeing hubs. It promotes healthy lifestyles by improving access to nutritious food and supporting sustainable mobility through infrastructure such as bicycle facilities. Beyond commerce, the marketplace acts as a social hub, hosting cultural events and 'Co-creation Cuisine' initiatives to foster intergenerational connections and reduce social isolation. It also promotes economic inclusion by supporting local producers and creating training and employment opportunities for disadvantaged groups.

Key Activities

- **Infrastructure development:** Renovating market squares and public spaces, installing accessibility features such as ramps and lifts, and creating facilities like community kitchens and waste management 'eco-islands'.
- **Programme implementation:** Involves organising cultural, social and educational events, including culinary workshops and youth festivals, to promote healthy eating and sustainability.
- **Community building:** mapping local stakeholders, training community activators and facilitating workshops to build trust and local networks.
- **Economic development:** Offering incubation programmes, training and mentoring to social entrepreneurs.

Cost Structure

- **Capital investment:** Costs allocated to the construction and renovation of physical spaces, including kitchens, eco-islands and digital purchasing systems.
- **Operational expenses:** Include salaries for cultural coordinators and staff, event materials, and marketing campaigns.
- **Maintenance:** Ongoing funds are required to maintain the facilities and ensure long-term sustainability.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue can be generated through activities such as renting out spaces, charging for workshops or pop-up restaurants, and catering.

Partnerships

- **Lead partners:** collaborations between public authorities, research institutions and social enterprises.
- **Local stakeholders:** A broad network including residents, NGOs, farmers, local businesses, schools, artists and neighbourhood associations.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Agile management team:** A professional team capable of balancing commercial viability with the project's social mission.
- **Community Connectors:** Staff dedicated to curating cultural content and engaging with neighbourhood associations to ensure the market serves the local community, not just tourists.
- **Pro-sustainability vendors:** Traders willing to adopt waste reduction practices and participate in food donation schemes.

Processes

- **Flexible lease model:** Long-term agreements, which grant operators autonomy in exchange for capital investment and social deliverables.
- **Cross-subsidisation:** A financial model where revenue from commercial stalls subsidises community areas such as kitchens and educational spaces.
- **Waste minimisation:** strict protocols for waste separation and utilisation of the 'Eco-Island' system.

Other requisites

- **Multifunctional zoning:** Spaces designed for mixed use, combining sales areas with zones for co-creation, events and education.
- **Accessibility upgrades:** Essential installations such as lifts and ramps to make the space inclusive for the elderly and people with disabilities.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 5 - indicating that the solution is being validated in a relevant environment (only the 'Co-creation kitchen' uses technology).
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 7 - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Social cohesion; Cultural participation; Financial situation.

Value Proposition

This digital marketplace connects small-scale rural food producers directly with urban consumers who want fresh, healthy and traceable food. By curating seasonal products and facilitating direct delivery, the platform shortens supply chains, improves transparency and strengthens local food systems.

The value proposition combines:

- **Convenience:** easy access to locally produced, seasonal food.
- **Trust:** full transparency regarding food origins and production methods.
- **Sustainability:** Eco-conscious consumption through reduced food waste and optimised logistics.

Key Activities

- **Digital Marketplace:** Operating a platform that links rural producers with urban buyers.
- **Supply chain management:** Curating seasonal offerings and managing direct-to-consumer delivery to support a resilient local food system.

Cost Structure

- **Development:** Costs for platform design, technical development and setting up logistics systems.
- **Operations:** Expenses for IT maintenance, logistics partnerships (including the cold chain), and personnel for customer support and producer relations.
- **Marketing and Sales:** Budget for community engagement, marketing campaigns and transaction fees.
- **Onboarding:** Costs associated with bringing new producers onto the platform and ensuring quality control.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue can be generated through commission-based sales on transactions, premium subscriptions for consumers, and the sale of curated seasonal boxes.

Partnerships

- **Producers:** Small-scale farmers and artisanal food producers.
- **Logistics providers:** Local partners who manage home deliveries and collection points.
- **Community:** Conscious consumer groups, food NGOs and workplace or neighbourhood hubs acting as collection points.
- **Public sector:** Municipal actors working on food policy and urban sustainability.

Replication prerequisites

- **Supply and demand:** a sufficient number of local producers willing to sell directly, coupled with urban consumer demand for transparent, seasonal food.
- **Infrastructure:** A robust digital platform for e-commerce and subscriptions, supported by reliable logistics and cold chain solutions.
- **Management:** The capacity to manage seasonal variability and curate product lines.
- **Policy alignment:** Support from local food strategies or sustainability policies.
- **Investment:** Moderate initial funding for technology and operational setup.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders to gain initial feedback on potential impact.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** Level: 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Social cohesion; Financial situation; Employment; Social inclusion

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.5 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This business offers a clean, herbal, tea-based energy drink designed for health-conscious consumers. It provides sustained energy, focus and hydration, and avoids the sugar, artificial ingredients and 'crashes' associated with conventional energy drinks. Combining functional wellness with environmental responsibility, the product targets two main groups:

- B2C consumers: individuals seeking a daily ritual that supports mental clarity and well-being.
- B2B partners: Yoga studios, wellness centres and retreats that want to offer their clients a product that aligns with their values.

Key Activities

- **Production:** Formulating and manufacturing a herbal, tea-based functional beverage.
- **Distribution:** Managing a subscription-based model for regular customers and handling logistics for B2B orders.
- **Marketing:** Positioning the brand for wellness-oriented consumers through digital content and partnerships.
- **Sales:** Acquiring customers via online channels and maintaining relationships with wellness studios and retreats.
- **Sustainability:** Implementing environmental initiatives such as planting a tree for every pack sold and transitioning to zero-waste packaging.

Cost Structure

- **Production:** Procurement of raw ingredients, manufacturing and packaging.
- **Operations:** Logistics, distribution and subscription fulfilment.
- **Marketing:** Costs for paid advertising, content creation and influencer collaborations.
- **Personnel:** Salaries for the growing team.
- **Sustainability:** Funding for environmental impact initiatives.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through direct product sales, recurring subscription models, and limited-edition campaigns.

Partnerships

- **Wellness networks:** yoga studios, teachers and retreat centres that act as distribution channels and brand ambassadors.
- **Operational partners:** Logistics and production providers who ensure a reliable supply and delivery service.
- **Promotional partners:** influencers and marketers who support brand growth.
- **Investors:** Strategic backers who share the brand's vision for wellness and sustainability.

Replication prerequisites

- **Market demand:** A sufficient segment of health-conscious consumers looking for functional beverages.
- **Infrastructure:** Access to reliable production facilities and logistics for subscription delivery.
- **Brand positioning:** A strong identity linked to wellness and environmental values.
- **Compliance:** Compliance with food and beverage regulations in target markets.
- **Partnerships:** Established connections with local wellness ecosystems (e.g. corporate wellness programmes and gyms).
- **Commitment:** Financial resources for market entry and dedication to impact measures such as reforestation.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level: 9** - indicating that the solution was proven in an operational environment.
- **Societal Readiness Level: 9** - indicating that the solution was proven in a relevant environment.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** The solution did not explicitly target this.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.6 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

The HADUP Centre offers specialised consulting services designed to integrate human-animal bonds into urban planning. It provides bespoke policy frameworks, strategies and specialised training to help cities create inclusive, human-centred spaces. By combining evidence-based planning with thought leadership, the Centre establishes itself as a trusted expert in improving urban health and wellbeing through human-animal policies.

Key Activities

- **Specialised research:** Conducting research on human-animal bonds and inclusive health and wellbeing (IHW) using participatory action research (PAR).
- **Policy co-design:** Facilitating workshops where stakeholders collaborate to design effective policies.
- **Training:** Delivering targeted sessions to help officials implement these policies successfully.
- **Project management:** Managing lean pilot projects using agile coordination methods.
- **Thought leadership:** Building authority in the field through advocacy and publications.

Cost Structure

- **Personnel:** Salaries for expert consultants and staff.
- **Operations:** Costs for office space (physical or virtual), software and travel.
- **Research:** Funding for targeted studies to maintain expert status.
- **Networking:** expenses for attending conferences and producing thought leadership content.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through consulting fees for policy design and implementation, training fees for capacity building, and research fees for impact assessments. Additionally, funding is derived from EU grants for pilot projects.

Partnerships

- **Universities:** Provide academic rigour, research and veterinary/behavioural expertise.
- **Municipalities:** Can act as pilot cities and reference cases for policy implementation.
- **Urban planning associations:** Facilitate outreach and industry connections.
- **NGOs and community groups:** offer on-the-ground insights and support implementation.
- **Funders:** Organisations providing financial backing.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Pet Policy Manager:** A professional with cross-cutting skills in urban planning, ethology and public administration,
- **Cross-Departmental Board:** A working group of councillors from Social Services, Environment and Urban Planning to break down administrative silos.
- **Scientific advisors:** collaboration with veterinary or ethology experts to ensure policies are evidence-based.

Processes

- **Participatory council:** A formal council where stakeholders (vets, pet owners and non-owners) jointly design conflict prevention rules.
- **Regulatory alignment:** updating local bylaws to allow animals in public offices, nursing homes and on public transport.

Other requisites

- **Animal-Nature Based Solutions (A-NBS):** Recognising facilities such as dog parks ('Animal Lines') as essential social infrastructure rather than just waste areas.
- **Data mapping:** Using GIS to map pet density and needs in order to inform infrastructure planning.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 0 - indicating that the solution is not developing a technological innovation.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** Level: 7 - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Spatial Well-being; Equality; Social inclusion.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 9.1 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This initiative uses animal-assisted interventions (AAIs) as a natural, stigma-free way of supporting underserved individuals, particularly the elderly in residential care. By introducing animal-nature-based solutions (A-NBS), it offers beneficiaries significant health and wellbeing improvements:

- **Emotional wellbeing:** Companionship with animals reduces loneliness, alleviates depression and buffers against stress.
- **Cognitive stimulation:** Activities encourage communication, engagement, and memory recall (e.g. remembering pets or names).
- **Physical activity:** Interaction involves gentle movement, such as petting, brushing, or playing.
- **Social connection:** Shared time and spaces foster bonding and a renewed sense of belonging.

Key Activities.

- **Session delivery:** Designing and delivering tailored intervention plans based on the specific needs of residents and nursing homes.
- **Partnership management:** Building relationships with care homes, local authorities and stakeholders to increase reach and integration.
- **Animal welfare:** Providing rigorous, continuous training and health management for therapy animals to ensure safety and ethical treatment.
- **Staff development:** Ensuring continuous professional training and certification for therapists and handlers.

Cost Structure

- **Personnel:** Salaries for licensed therapists, coordinators and administrative staff.
- **Animal care:** expenses for veterinary checks, vaccinations, food, grooming and specialised insurance.
- **Operations:** Costs for transport, session equipment, office supplies and liability insurance.
- **Training:** Budget for the ongoing development of both human staff and therapy animals.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through public funding (primary), derived from municipal, national, and regional health and social care budgets. This is complemented by emerging public service contracts with local authorities and significant EU and philanthropic grants focused on social innovation and ageing. Additional income streams include direct revenue from user fees for enhanced services, donations via corporate CSR and community fundraising, and partnership contributions in the form of in-kind support from universities and NGOs.

Partnerships

- **Care homes** are essential partners that provide access to beneficiaries and integrate sessions into daily routines.
- **Public authorities**, such as municipalities and health bodies, provide funding, legitimacy and regulatory support.
- **Universities are academic centres** that offer research support, evaluation methodologies and student internships.
- **Veterinary services** are crucial for monitoring the health and welfare of therapy animals.
- **Organisations (NGOs)** that assist with outreach, volunteer recruitment, and advocacy.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Certified professionals:** Handlers and therapists who are trained in accordance with national guidelines.
- **Veterinarians:** Experts who monitor animal welfare (e.g. stress levels) to prevent exploitation.

Processes

- **Public procurement:** Administrative procedures for tendering services to NGOs, ensuring quality and compliance.
- **Rigorous protocols:** standardised session plans tailored to patients with dementia or mobility issues.
- **Informed consent:** Ethical procedures for obtaining permission from participants or their guardians.

Other requisites

- **Suitable animals:** specially selected and trained animals that have passed behavioural assessments.
- **Insurance:** Specific liability cover for animal-related incidents within health facilities.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 0 - indicating that the solution is not developing a technological innovation.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** Level: 7 - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Social inclusion; Social cohesion

Value Proposition

This service supports individuals who are temporarily underserved by helping them with their pet care needs. By providing support during challenging periods, it alleviates anxiety, prevents social isolation and safeguards the physical and mental well-being of both owners and their pets. The service offers three core levels of support:

- **Domestic services:** in-home care (feeding, cleaning and grooming) and delivery of essential supplies.
- **Assisted outdoor services:** accompanying the owner to transport the pet to the vet or walking the dog.
- **Independent outdoor services:** walking the dog or transporting the pet to appointments on the owner's behalf.

Key Activities

- **Service provision:** Delivering daily care (feeding, administering medication), managing supply procurement and conducting walks or transport.
- **Client onboarding:** Assessing the vulnerability of new clients to understand the specific health and safety needs of both human and pet.
- **Staffing:** recruiting and training compassionate caregivers in pet first aid, emergency procedures and client sensitivity.
- **Partnership building:** Collaborating with local councils, social services and healthcare providers to secure referrals and funding.
- **Network engagement:** Building relationships with local vets for referrals and pet stores for potential discounts.

Cost Structure

- **Personnel:** Salaries for pet caregivers, drivers, client managers and administrative staff.
- **Logistics:** Costs for purchasing or leasing vehicles, fuel, insurance and maintenance.
- **Training:** Ongoing professional development for staff in pet care and supporting underserved populations.
- **Marketing:** Expenses for community outreach and digital advertising to reach those in need.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through a fixed price table. There is also the potential for a membership/subscription model. This could be supplemented by forming partnerships with private urban developers on large-scale integrated projects.

Partnerships

- **Municipalities:** The primary customers and co-developers who serve as pilot sites for the service.
- **Social and health services:** Government departments that provide referrals and align the service with city-wide wellbeing goals.
- **Healthcare providers:** Hospitals and home care agencies that refer patients during recovery or incapacitation.
- **Charities:** Local groups that help connect the service with communities of people on low incomes, with disabilities, or who are elderly.
- **Lead partners:** Collaborations between research institutions, social enterprises and public authorities.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Vulnerability assessors:** Social workers or administrative staff who are qualified to identify and validate beneficiaries.
- **Logistics Network:** A coordinated team of staff or volunteers capable of providing walking, fostering and transport services.

Processes

- **Emergency protocol:** A system for rapidly deploying support when a beneficiary is facing an immediate crisis.
- **Formal agreements:** Legal frameworks between the municipality and NGOs to authorise service provision.
- **Management interface:** A simple platform or phone line for booking services and coordinating volunteers.

Infrastructure

- **Transport:** Access to pet-friendly vehicles suitable for veterinary visits and safe transportation.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 0 - indicating that the solution is not developing a technological innovation.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** Level: 7 - indicating that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Financial situation; Security.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 9.3 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This digital platform streamlines pet care management and enhances access to animal health services. It addresses the needs of two key groups:

- **Pet owners:** Saves time and reduces stress by providing personalised reminders, document storage and direct access to service providers.
- **Professionals (vets and groomers):** Can use it to showcase their services, manage bookings and communicate with clients, solving the sector's lack of online visibility.

Key Activities

- **Platform development:** Building and maintaining a mobile application for iOS and Android.
- **User management:** Managing features such as personalised notifications, document storage and file sharing.
- **Service aggregation:** Continuously updating the database of service providers.
- **Booking system:** Facilitating direct contact, appointment scheduling and client management tools for professionals.
- **Promotion:** Marketing the platform through online and offline channels.
- **Expansion:** Gradually integrating additional services, such as pet sitting and training.

Cost Structure

- **Development:** Costs for software engineering, legal compliance and registration.
- **Operations:** Ongoing platform maintenance, updates and infrastructure expenses.
- **Growth:** Budget for marketing campaigns and scaling the team.
- **Innovation:** Investment in advanced booking and management tools.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through a freemium approach: basic features are provided to owners free of charge, while professionals pay monthly subscription fees for premium features and visibility.

Partnerships

- **Service providers:** Veterinary clinics, groomers and trainers registered on the platform.
- **Business partners:** Strategic allies supporting platform growth and service expansion.
- **Promotional partners:** agencies and networks assisting with communication.
- **Institutions:** Public or sectoral bodies involved in animal welfare ecosystems.

Replication prerequisites

- **Market scale:** A critical mass of active pet owners and service providers.
- **Technology:** Robust mobile infrastructure that is fully compliant with data protection regulations.
- **Engagement:** Service providers willing to maintain updated online profiles.
- **Financials:** Investment capacity for marketing and a market ready for subscription-based models.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 5 - indicating that the solution has been validated in a relevant environment.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 5 - indicating that the solution has been validated by relevant Stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** The solution did not explicitly target this.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.3 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This initiative provides animal-assisted interventions (AAIs) for children, adults and older people who are physically or psychologically underserved. Moving away from clinical, medicalised settings, the programme uses structured interaction with animals and nature to boost motivation, engagement, autonomy and social skills. The core value lies in three pillars:

- **Environment:** A welcoming, non-institutional space designed specifically for underserved users.
- **Expertise:** Highly trained professionals who receive continuous updates in their field.
- **Ethics:** High standards of animal welfare, ensuring that animals are respected participants **rather** than tools.

Key Activities

- **Service delivery:** Providing animal-assisted activities (AAA), education (AAE) and therapy (AAT).
- **Pathway co-design:** Collaborating with social cooperatives and care managers to create personalised intervention plans.
- **Team coordination:** Managing a diverse team of educators, psychologists, ethologists, musicians, veterinarians and certified handlers.
- **Animal care:** Daily management and welfare checks for all therapy animals.
- **Evaluation:** Monitoring outcomes through interviews, psychological tests and progress tracking.

Cost Structure

- **Infrastructure:** Costs for property acquisition (or leasing), renovation, furnishing and maintenance.
- **Operations:** Expenses for utilities, high-speed internet and platform fees.
- **Personnel:** Salaries for staff, including guest services and community facilitators.
- **Programming:** Budget for event delivery, marketing, branding and partnership coordination.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through a mixed funding strategy. This revenue comes from public service contracts with municipalities and health agencies, as well as private support from foundations and philanthropic organisations.

Partnerships

- **Public authorities:** Rural municipalities that support regeneration and the activation of local spaces.
- **Tourism networks:** Regional boards and local tourism groups.
- **Local Economy:** Producers, artisans and service providers who contribute to the local economy.
- **Digital platforms:** Networks for digital nomads and co-working spaces.
- **Facilitators:** Experts in culture and wellbeing who assist with programming.

Replication prerequisites

- **Environment:** A suitable natural setting adapted for underserved users.
- **Expertise:** Access to certified professionals and veterinary support.
- **Standards:** Strong ethical guidelines and animal welfare protocols.
- **Operations:** Capacity to manage long-term personalised pathways and monitor outcomes.
- **Sustainability:** Financial stability to cover costs and ensure surplus.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 1 - indicating that the Basic principles are observed and reported.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 9 - indicating that the solution was proven in a relevant environment.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Social inclusion; Social cohesion.

Value Proposition

This community bike-sharing service provides an affordable and sustainable transport solution that encourages an active lifestyle. By using bicycles refurbished from spare parts and offering seasonal rentals, the service fosters a circular economy. It uniquely involves the community in co-designing the service and public spaces, thereby enhancing urban living, safety and cleanliness. A dedicated repair workshop encourages users to maintain the bikes, fostering a sense of ownership. The initiative also generates economic value by creating opportunities for social entrepreneurship, training, and employment.

Key Activities

- **Operations:** Managing bike rentals and the repair workshop.
- **Co-design:** collaborating with locals to plan cycle routes and integrate them into public spaces.
- **Volunteering:** Organising activities such as bike repairs, litter collection, planting and road maintenance.
- **Education and feedback:** running thematic workshops (e.g. bike safety) and conducting annual surveys to gather improvement ideas.

Cost Structure

- **Personnel:** Salaries for staff managing operations, maintenance and community coordination.
- **Materials:** Costs for purchasing and maintaining refurbished bikes and spare parts (often reduced by partnering with recycling firms).
- **Operations:** Expenses for warehousing, venue hire, insurance, permits and administration.
- **Events and training:** Budget for organising workshops and public events, and for purchasing supplies.
- **Marketing:** Costs for media documentation, campaigns and user engagement.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through tiered rental fees (for monthly or six-month periods) and usage-based charges. Different pricing tables apply at various times of the year. Additional funding can be secured through municipal budget allocations for urban development, public spaces and social services.

Partnerships

- **Implementation partner:** the organisation responsible for managing the service and community engagement.
- **Supply chain:** suppliers of new and used bicycle parts, payment providers and insurance companies.
- **Public sector:** local government and institutions that provide site access, permits and urban planning expertise.
- **Academia:** Universities that support research and evaluate the project's social impact.

Replication prerequisites

People

- **Community Manager:** A trusted local leader (e.g. from a cultural centre) who oversees the system.
- **Volunteer mechanics:** Local youth or DIY enthusiasts who are trained to repair and maintain the fleet.

Processes

- **Trust-based lending:** a low-barrier rental system that relies on community ownership rather than expensive automated docking stations.
- **Circular sourcing:** protocols for acquiring and refurbishing abandoned or donated bicycles.

Other requisites

- **Secure depot:** A physical space (e.g. a shipping container) within a safe community hub for storage and repairs.
- **Cycling paths:** Basic, safe infrastructure to enable riders to use the service effectively.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 0 - indicating that the solution is not developing a technological innovation.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Spatial Well-being; Financial situation; Safety

Value Proposition

This initiative establishes cyclist-friendly rest and refreshment hubs along semi-rural cycling routes. Designed for families, individuals and informal groups, the hubs offer food and drink, bike rental, basic servicing and social spaces. By filling the infrastructure gap for longer, family-friendly trips, the hubs promote physical wellbeing alongside convenience and comfort. They also promote local identity by featuring regional products in their tourism offerings.

Key Activities

- **Operations:** Managing self-service 'Freshbox' snack units, bike rentals, and basic repair services.
- **Supply chain:** Coordinating with local suppliers for food and beverages.
- **Marketing:** Promoting the hubs via digital channels, social media and cycling maps (points of interest).
- **Collaboration:** Working with municipalities and tourism bodies to increase visibility and host events.

Cost Structure

- **Infrastructure:** Installation of Freshbox units, bike rental equipment and small-scale physical structures.
- **Stock and maintenance:** Purchasing food and beverage inventory and servicing bicycles.
- **Personnel:** Wages for technical and operational staff.
- **Overheads:** Utilities, marketing campaigns and initial platform listing fees.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through food and beverage sales, seasonal events, and partnerships with local producers.

Partnerships

- **Local suppliers:** Providers of regional food and drink, prioritising local products.
- **Public sector:** Municipalities and tourism offices that assist with site placement and promotion.
- **Digital platforms:** Mapping services and cycling apps that integrate the hubs as points of interest.
- **Ecosystem partners:** Strategic allies that support community engagement and visibility.

Replication prerequisites

- **Location:** Existing or emerging cycling routes with recreational traffic.
- **Support:** Municipal backing for permits and site placement.
- **Supply:** Local producers willing to supply food and beverages.
- **Investment:** Moderate upfront capital for modular infrastructure.
- **Demand:** Sufficient seasonal traffic to support onsite sales.
- **Management:** Capacity for basic operations and maintenance.
- **Strategy:** Alignment with regional goals for active mobility, rural tourism and wellbeing.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 2 - indicating that the solution is a technology concept.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 6 - indicating that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Leisure & Free Time

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.7 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

Value Proposition

This initiative transforms unused local sheep's wool into handcrafted clothing, accessories and homeware. It combines traditional textile techniques with contemporary, eco-conscious design. By collaborating with local farmers and processors, the project restores regional wool value chains and prevents waste and overproduction.

The value proposition is based on:

- **Sustainable production:** made-to-order and small-batch items to avoid surplus stock.
- **Transparency:** Full visibility of material origins and production methods.
- **Durability:** Timeless products designed for long-term use.
- **Identity:** Fashion that integrates cultural storytelling and regional heritage.

Key Activities

- **Sourcing:** Procuring raw wool from local farmers and regional suppliers.
- **Production:** Coordinating yarn preparation with local processors and overseeing artisanal knitting.
- **Design:** developing products, including custom pieces and limited editions.
- **Sales:** managing direct sales via social media, pre-orders, pop-up markets and select stores.
- **Education:** Organising workshops for schools and the public.
- **Communication:** Promoting sustainability and storytelling through digital channels.

Cost Structure

- **Production:** Costs for raw materials (e.g. wool and yarn), prototyping, and payments to artisans and processors.
- **Operations:** Logistics, packaging and digital infrastructure (branding and web).
- **Services:** Fees for outsourced professionals (design, photography, marketing).
- **Marketing:** expenses for events, pop-ups and customer acquisition campaigns.

Revenue Streams

- Potential revenue is generated through direct sales of woollen products, limited-edition collections, and creative partnerships. Workshops also contribute to the revenue mix.

Partnerships

- **Supply chain:** Local sheep farmers and regional wool processors.
- **Creatives:** Designers, textile specialists, photographers and storytellers.
- **Retail and education:** Concept stores, artisan shops and schools hosting workshops.
- **Networks:** Creative and environmental organisations that support visibility and funding.

Replication prerequisites

- **Resources:** Availability of underutilised natural fibres (e.g. wool and flax).
- **Skills:** Access to skilled artisans or textile expertise.
- **Collaboration:** Farmers willing to participate in short supply chains.
- **Facilities:** Access to small-scale production or processing partners.
- **Market:** Demand for sustainable, locally made products.
- **Operations:** Capacity for storytelling and direct-to-consumer sales.
- **Strategy:** Alignment with circular economy and cultural heritage goals.
- **Investment:** Low to moderate start-up capital focused on materials and market entry.

Additional assessment indicators

- **Technology Readiness Level:** 1 - indicating that the Basic principles are observed and reported.
- **Societal Readiness Level:** 9 - indicating that the solution was proven in a relevant environment.
- **Targeted IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions:** Employment; Job and skill satisfaction; Cultural participation.

For the mapping of GDEI-sensitive IHW sub-dimensions and detailed business model canvas and market analysis, please refer to Chapters 6 and 12.8 of Deliverable D8.16, "Replicable business models to boost IHW".

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE “D8.16 REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS TO BOOST IHW” AND RELATION WITH OTHER WORK PACKAGES

This deliverable, D8.16, titled “**Replicable business models to boost the IHW**”, showcases the 16 business models with replication potential developed during the IN-HABIT project. highlighting the components, processes and success factors of these models makes them easier for others to adopt, adapt and implement in different regions, sectors, or markets. It provides frameworks, success factors, and barriers for scaling these models to other cities and link innovation with policy, market potential, and societal value. These business models serve as inspiration and guidance for potential adopters. D8.16 is based on previous IN-HABIT Project deliverables, including:

- D1.1: Inclusive Transformation Plan, Las Palmeras
- D1.3: Monitoring and Evaluation of VIS for IHW in Córdoba
- D2.1: Inclusive Transformation Plan of the Āgenskalns Market Area in Riga
- D2.3: Monitoring and Evaluation of VIS for IHW in Riga
- D3.1: Inclusive Transformation Plan of Lucca
- D3.3: Monitoring and Evaluation of VIS for IHW in Lucca
- D4.3 – Monitoring and evaluation VIS for IHW in Nitra
- D7.3: Baseline study on IHW report
- D7.6: IN-HABIT Full Operative Data Platform
- D5:3: Final Report of the Inclusive Business Incubation Programme
- D8.14: Market Analysis and Preliminary Exploitation Strategies

This deliverable identifies Key Exploitable Results (KERs), Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VISs), and entrepreneurial projects incubated through the Bridge for Billions incubation Programme that have the potential to be replicated by other organisations.

3. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

A methodological approach was employed in developing this document using a collaborative data collection process, and iterative validation of information collected.

Data gathering

Replicable Business Models Assessment Criteria

1. Alignment with the Grant Agreement (GA)

The assessment criteria for the replicable business models were designed based on the strategic requirements of the Grant Agreement (GA). The following paragraphs detail this strategic alignment.

The selection process prioritised solutions with commercial and revenue generation potential, establishing financial autonomy as a critical success factor. This approach represents a strategic shift, providing decision-makers with self-sustaining models that minimise long-term reliance on public subsidies. In strict accordance with Annex 1 of the GA amendment, this report validates these solutions by detailing the 'classical elements of a business model', including rigorous analyses of cost structures, revenue streams, and investment requirements, which prove their economic sustainability.

Furthermore, the portfolio was constructed to fulfil the specific mandate of Task 8.4 regarding the incorporation of the business models with the highest potential generated through the Bridge for Billions (B4B) Inclusive business incubation programme. By integrating these agile, market-ready, B4B incubated projects alongside city-led systemic innovations, the portfolio provides a balanced 'top-down and bottom-up' toolkit. This dual-stream approach enables follower cities to leverage a comprehensive range of instruments, from large-scale urban governance solutions to grassroots entrepreneurial initiatives, to promote long-term inclusive health and wellbeing.

2. Selection of business models emerging from a “dual stream”

The selection of business models follows a 'Dual-Stream' Innovation Lifecycle. This structure was deliberately designed to ensure that follower cities are equipped with a balanced toolkit integrating both large-scale, top-down institutional solutions and agile, bottom-up grassroots innovations.

- **Stream A (Solutions developed directly by the IN-HABIT consortium partners):**

This stream focuses on solutions developed directly by the IN-HABIT consortium partners, representing the structural backbone of urban regeneration. As detailed in Deliverable 8.14 ('Market Analysis and Preliminary Exploitation Strategies'), the selection process was based on a rigorous, participatory methodology aimed at identifying Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS) with commercial potential. Through a series of assessment workshops held in the pilot cities, partners evaluated technical assets against strict exploitation potential criteria. This internal selection was further validated through complementary innovation maturity analysis conducted by Bridge for Billions (B4B) team, ensuring that only solutions capable of transitioning from grant-funded pilots to financially autonomous operations were included in the final portfolio.

- **Stream B (Solutions developed within the B4B Inclusive business incubation programme):**

This stream showcases the vibrancy of the local social economy via the Bridge for Billions (B4B) Inclusive business incubation programme. A rigorous curation process was employed to select a representative portfolio of high-potential business models from a substantial pool of 179 projects and 223 entrepreneurs supported across the four pilot cities.

These business were analysed using a standardised evaluation matrix across the four pilot cities to identify highly transferable models that would be valuable to external adopters. Two projects per city were selected, prioritising those with strong socio-economic viability, replication potential, and strategic alignment with Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW). The resulting portfolio encompasses

the full spectrum of wellbeing innovation, including place-based, digital, service-driven, and product-driven solutions, ensuring a diverse and mature set of reference cases.

To ensure transferability and protect intellectual property, these models have been anonymised.

3. Innovation maturity:

To ensure that the portfolio consists of investment-ready solutions rather than theoretical concepts, the maturity of each business model was assessed using Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) and Societal Readiness Levels (SRLs). The partners responsible for each KER and VIS completed an online self-assessment questionnaire to evaluate their initiatives against these metrics. For the eight incubated projects, the B4B Inclusive Business Incubation Programme team conducted this assessment.

The IN-HABIT concept and its objectives focus primarily on the *Societal Readiness Level (SRL)*⁷, which is a method of assessing the extent to which specific social projects, technologies, products, processes, interventions, or innovations (social or technical) can be integrated into society. SRL 1 is the lowest level, while SRL 9 is the highest:

- Stages SRL 1 to 3 reflect the initial work of a research project, including the preliminary suggestion and testing of technical and/or social solutions to technical or societal problems.
- Stages SRL 4 to 6 represent the actual solution(s) and the research hypothesis, assessing them in the relevant context in cooperation with relevant stakeholders while focusing on impact and societal readiness for the product.
- Stages SRL 7 to 9 cover the final stages of the research project, including refining the solution(s) and implementing and disseminating the results and/or solutions.

A differentiated threshold strategy was applied to Stream A and Stream B to account for their distinct developmental trajectories: systemic institutional implementation versus agile entrepreneurial innovation.

Societal Readiness Level (SRL) assessment:

- **Stream A:** Priority was given to models achieving SRL 6 or higher. This ensures that these solutions have moved beyond theoretical validation and have been demonstrated in relevant environments with active stakeholder cooperation, providing concrete feedback on their potential societal impact.
- **Stream B:** To successfully capture grassroots innovation within the incubation timeframe, the entry threshold was set at SRL 5. This confirms that the proposed business models have been validated by relevant stakeholders in the target area. While full-scale demonstration may still be ongoing, this level of validation acknowledges that the solution has achieved a critical level of social acceptance and demand.

As some IN-HABIT solutions involve technology, *Technology Readiness Level (TRL)* assessments were also conducted to evaluate technological maturity. Each technology project is evaluated against the

⁷ Source: IN-Habit Grant agreement

parameters of the relevant technology level, and a TRL rating is then assigned based on its progress. TRL 1 represents the lowest level, while TRL 9 represents the highest:

- TLR 1: Basic principles observed and reported.
- TLR 2: Technology concept and/or application formulated.
- TLR 3: Analytical and experimental proof of concept for critical functions and/or characteristics.
- TLR 4: Component and/or breadboard validation in a laboratory environment.
- TLR 5: Component and/or breadboard validation in a relevant environment.
- TLR 6: System/sub-system model or prototype demonstration in an operational environment.
- TLR 7: System prototype demonstration in an operational environment.
- TLR 8: Actual system completed and “flight qualified” through testing and demonstration.
- TLR 9: Actual system proven through successful operations.

Technology Readiness Level (TRL):

- **Stream A:** The selection process for city-led digital and technical solutions was rigorous, admitting only models between TRL 7 (operational prototype) and TRL 9 (proven system). These assets were developed through extensive, multi-year cycles of co-design and co-deployment, and offer decision-makers 'de-risked' solutions that are fully operational.
- **Stream B:** The B4B team selected models ranging from Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 5 (technology validated in a relevant environment) to TRL 9 (system proven in an operational environment). These projects emerged from the B4B Inclusive Business Incubation Programme, which uses a shorter, more intensive development cycle. In recognition of this accelerated timeline, a medium TRL threshold was adopted. This strategic choice enables the portfolio to encompass high-potential, innovative ventures that are still at a medium stage of technical validation.

This rigorous filtering process ensures a balanced portfolio spanning TRL and SRL levels 5 to 9. This offers decision-makers a diverse mix of fully validated systemic infrastructures and agile, high-impact entrepreneurial solutions.

Figure 1 – First page of the online questionnaire for self-assessment of the degree of innovation of each Key Exploitable Results (KER) and Visionary and Integrative Solutions (VIS).

The results of the self-assessment questionnaire were compiled into Word documents structured according to the Social Business Model Canvas. These documents were pre-populated with existing information to facilitate the collection of additional details about each innovation. The Word files were then shared with partners, enabling them to review the data collected on their current business model, correct errors, add missing information, and provide feedback. All documents were stored in a shared online folder for easy access and collaboration.

Figure 2 - Excerpts from the word file used for information collection.

Figure 3 - Social Business Model Canvas

Table 3 - Building blocks of the Social Business Model Canvas

Building Blocks	Questions
Value Proposition	How are you creating value for your beneficiaries and customers through your social programs, your product, or services?
Competitors & Coopetitors	Coopetition: These are potential future partners you can enter into “coopetition”- cooperate with one program and remain in competition in other aspects of your work.
	Competition: These are your direct competitors
Key Stakeholders	Who are the people that you hope to serve? Who are the people who will pay for your products & services? Who are your most important funders? Beneficiaries: Provide all the details you know about your beneficiaries. Also, what are their goals? What are the barriers they face? What do they need?
	Customers: Provide all the details you know about your customers. Also, what are their goals? What are the barriers they face? What do they need?
Relationships	What mechanisms will you use to build and maintain relationships with your Beneficiaries, Consumers/Customers and Stakeholders?
Channels	How will you deliver your social value propositions/interventions to your Beneficiaries and Customers? Depending on your offering, you may need to think about developing mechanisms that effectively deliver your programs to your beneficiaries and at the same time mechanisms, or channels, which deliver your products and/or services to your customers.
Key Activities	What are the critical activities that you need to do, for your social programs, products, or services, in order to achieve your social mission? How are you ensuring that you are incorporating your social mission into all of your activities?
Key Resources	What key resources will you need to deliver your social programs and products & services successfully? Try to give as much detail as possible indicating estimated quantities, for example, where you can. This information will assist you in estimating your costs.
Key Delivery Partners	Focus on those key delivery partners you will need to help you deliver your social business' products or services. Do you need to rent a space? Do you have suppliers? Are you going to be working closely with other agencies on joint contracts to deliver on your Social Mission? List out your Key Partners, indicate the relationship, and rank them in terms of priority. Remember to think about how you ensure that you are incorporating your social mission into all of your activities?
Social Impact Measurement Strategy	Why do you do what you do? How will you know when you have achieved it? Your Social Impact Measurement (Theory of Change) should be laid out together alongside your Social Value Propositions that you have outlined for your beneficiaries, customers, and key stakeholders. You should seek to measure short-term outputs, medium-term outcomes, and long-term impact. What deliverables, changes, or achievements (called indicators) are you going to monitor and measure, that best indicates that your Social Mission is having an impact?
Quantitative and qualitative KPIs	Please define quantitative and qualitative KPIs for your solution

Building Blocks	Questions
Revenue Streams	Can you provide an overview of the income you will have for your social business? What percentage of your income will be from grants, awards, or donations? What percentage of your income will come from contracts & tradable income?
Costs	Can you estimate the overall and main costs you will incur delivering your programs, products, and services? Remember to include costs like recruiting & training volunteers, fundraising costs, networking, etc.
Surplus	The reinvestment of surplus profits back into the community it serves is one of the cornerstone goals of social business. Often, in the early days, most social businesses will not achieve surplus income and will remain reliant on grants and donations to continue to operate. If you generate surplus profits after covering your costs, how do you distribute your surplus?
Macro-Environment/ PESTEL	<p>You need to be aware of changes that are going on around you in the macro-environment. PESTEL stands for political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal context in which your social business operates. Conducting macro-environmental / PESTEL analysis allows you to conduct a 360-degree view of your environment and see any barriers or opportunities ahead in the short, medium, and long-term.</p> <p>Political</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1, What government policies or regulations could impact the business? (e.g., tax policies, trade regulations, labour laws) 2, Are there any local or national initiatives promoting or restricting health and well-being industries? <p>Economic</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1, How do current economic trends affect customer purchasing power? (e.g., inflation, recession, interest rates) 2, What are potential funding sources or economic incentives available for health and well-being programs? <p>Social</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1, What social trends might influence customer behaviour and preferences? (e.g., increased focus on well-being, mental health, aging populations) 2, How do societal attitudes towards sustainability, inclusion, and health impact our offerings? <p>Technological</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1, What emerging technologies could enhance or disrupt our business model? (e.g., digital health tools, online learning platforms) 2, How can technology be used to improve service delivery or customer engagement in health and well-being? <p>Environmental</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1, What environmental factors must we consider in our operations and product offerings? (e.g., sustainable practices, climate change) 2, Are there regulations or customer expectations around sustainability that influence our business?

Building Blocks	Questions
	Legal 1, What legal requirements impact our business, especially in health-related areas? (e.g., data protection laws, health, and safety regulations) 2, Are there intellectual property laws that affect our innovation strategy?

Results discussion and validation

A comprehensive Social Business Model Canvas was created to present each replicable business model alongside its respective market analysis. Each project partner received a Word document containing the replicable business model(s) resulting from their projects for review and validation.

Online meetings were then held with the partners to discuss the information received and confirm which business models could be considered Replicable Business Models. The concept and components of each Replicable Business Model were also validated during the process.

Finally, the complete deliverable was sent to all the partners for their final review.

4. IN-HABIT REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS ASSESSMENT

Following the selection processes detailed in the previous chapter, the initial portfolio appraisal identified eighteen potential candidates: ten from Stream A (consortium-led innovations) and eight from Stream B (incubated ventures)- However, strategic consolidation was applied to the Riga pilot to ensure that the business models represented viable standalone economic entities rather than fragmented interventions. Recognising that the 'hard' infrastructure (e.g. the co-creation kitchen and eco-island) and 'soft' programming (e.g. cultural events) in Riga operate as an interdependent ecosystem, these elements were integrated into a single systemic, replicable business model: the 'Āgenskalns Food Market'. This refinement optimised the final portfolio to 16 Replicable Business Models, creating a perfectly balanced structure with eight systemic models from Stream A and eight agile ventures from Stream B.

Table 4 - Replicable Business models

	Replicable Business models	Local of implementation
1	IN-Habit Platform	Córdoba, Lucca, Nitra, and Riga
2	Immersive experience training	Córdoba
3	The Āgenskalns food Market	Riga
4	Humanimal urban policy design centre (HADUP Centre)	Lucca
5	Animal Assisted Interventions for the elderly	Lucca

	Replicable Business models	Local of implementation
6	Pet care services	Lucca
7	Community Bike Sharing	Nitra
8	B4B Tailored Inclusive Business Training	Córdoba, Lucca, Nitra, and Riga

To complement the systemic solutions identified by the consortium, the portfolio incorporates eight high-potential business initiatives, which were selected from the Bridge for Billions (B4B) Inclusive Business Incubator Programme. To ensure geographic balance, two ventures were selected from each pilot city, and the initiatives were chosen for their innovative approach and robust alignment with the principles of Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW).

A critical methodological step in this process was the anonymisation and generalisation of these business models. This strategic approach protects the intellectual property and sensitive commercial know-how of the participating entrepreneurs.

Table 5 - Selected replicable business models from the B4B Inclusive Business Incubator Programme

	Replicable Business models / market segment	Local of implementation
1	Urban Farming Kits (Project SP-01)	Spain
2	Rural Co-Living Hubs (Project SP-02)	Spain
3	Digital Pet Health Record (Project IT-01)	Italy
4	Music & Animal Therapy (Project IT-02)	Italy
5	Eco-Cycle Tourism (Project SK-01)	Slovakia
6	Circular Wool Textiles (Project SK-02)	Slovakia
7	Food Digital platform (Project LV-01)	Latvia
8	Sustainable Functional Beverages (Project LV-02)	Latvia

5. OVERVIEW OF THE REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS

This chapter provides an overview of the IN-HABIT project's replicable business models. These models are examined in greater depth in Chapters 7–12, with this chapter providing a summary. It includes eight core innovations, identified by the project partners, which address themes such as monitoring

environmental parameters related to health and wellbeing, mental health, sustainable food, active lifestyles, intergenerational inclusion, digital upskilling, and rural revitalisation. It also includes eight business initiatives, selected from the Bridge for Billions (B4B) Inclusive Business Incubator Programme, two from each of the four pilot cities, which align with the Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW) principles, covering the same key thematic areas. The aim of these models is to facilitate the adoption and adaptation of their successful components, processes and factors in other regions, sectors, or markets.

At the core of the IN-HABIT project is the New European Bauhaus (NEB)⁸, a policy and funding initiative that aims to make the green transition in built environments and beyond enjoyable, attractive, and convenient for everyone. It promotes sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful solutions that respect the diversity of places, traditions, and cultures in Europe and beyond⁹. Neb Prioritises people and social inclusion, as well as the economy, to boost competitiveness and EU strategic autonomy.

The replicable business models developed within the IN-HABIT project are directly aligned with the European Union's strategic priorities for a sustainable, digital, and inclusive future. These models offer tangible solutions that contribute to key policy areas, including the European Green Deal (specifically the New European Bauhaus), One Health, and the Urban Agenda for the EU. They also support broader social and economic inclusion objectives.

5.1. IN-HABIT REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS

1 - IN-HABIT Data Platform

Description: The IN-HABIT Data Platform is a unique interface that is open, robust and scalable. It is designed to integrate seamlessly with other applications and APIs. It connects a network of sensors installed in public and private locations across cities. The platform features an intuitive, user-friendly dashboard offering differentiated access to real-time and historical data. Users can apply filters to access information based on sensor types and other parameters. Its inclusive design, featuring a clear visual palette and accessible navigation, ensures inclusivity for all users.

The complete business model can be found in Chapters 7 and 7.1)

2 - Immersive Experience Training

Description: The immersive experience provides a ludic software designed for adults with Down Syndrome to strengthen their abilities in event organisation, specifically in the role of congress hosts and hostesses. It offers a virtual space where users can practise specific tasks, problem-solving, decision-making, and time management within a safe environment, preparing them to apply these skills in real-world settings. The experience is designed to strengthen social and motor skills, thereby promoting greater autonomy and contributing to users' health and well-being

(The complete business model can be found in Chapters 7 and 7.2)

⁸ Source: Deliverable 9.6 policy report

⁹ https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

3 - The Āgenskalns Food Market

Description: A multifunctional urban marketplace designed to improve health and well-being inclusively. It integrates 'hard' solutions, such as accessibility ramps and lifts, and community kitchens, with 'soft' solutions, such as cultural, social and educational events, programmes and community gardens. This revitalises urban spaces, promotes healthy lifestyles and boosts economic inclusion.

(The complete business model can be found in Chapters 8 and 8.1)

4 - Humanimal urban policy design centre (HADUP Centre)

Description: The HADUP Centre is a pioneering innovation in urban governance which aims to turn economic growth and social inclusion challenges into opportunities by promoting human-animal bonds to achieve inclusive health and well-being (IHW). The Centre offers customised, evidence-based policy frameworks, specialised training and flexible pilot projects that incorporate animal companionship into urban planning.

(The complete business model can be found in Chapters 9 and 9.1)

5 - Animal Assisted Interventions (AAI)

Description: This service provides certified animal-assisted interventions for elderly people in nursing homes. Through personalised on-site sessions and rigorous training for animal therapists, AAI breaks down barriers, fostering sustainable, evidence-based transformations that redefine therapeutic landscapes with natural, empathetic efficacy.

(The complete business model can be found in Chapters 9 and 9.2)

6 - Pet Care Services

Description: This service supports individuals experiencing temporary vulnerabilities who need assistance with pet care, alleviating anxiety and risks associated with delayed access to care. It addresses the daily needs of humans and pets in disadvantaged situations, supporting everyday life and preventing difficulties and social isolation. The service aims to position cities as pioneers in compassionate, resilient urban planning.

(The complete business model can be found in Chapters 9 and 9.3)

7 - Community Bike Sharing

Description: This initiative addresses the need for affordable, sustainable urban transport by revitalizing cycling routes in semi-rural areas through dedicated rest and refreshment zones. It provides a community bike-sharing service using refurbished bikes, empowering locals through co-design, circular resource use, and active lifestyles. It also includes a bike repair workshop to foster community ownership and promote circularity.

(The complete business model can be found in Chapters 10 and 10.1)

8 – B4B Tailored Inclusive Business training

Description: A flexible, locally adaptable entrepreneurship training model designed for people who are often excluded from mainstream business support, particularly women and underrepresented groups. It combines practical business learning with confidence-building, mentoring, and community support, delivered in a format that fits local realities (in-person, online, or hybrid). The training reduces barriers such as limited digital skills, lack of devices, time constraints, and low access to networks, helping participants move from idea to action and connect with the local ecosystem.

(The complete business model can be found in Chapters 11)

5.2. SELECTED BUSINESS MODELS FROM THE INCLUSIVE BUSINESS INCUBATION PROGRAMME

(The complete business models can be found in Chapter 12)

1 - Urban Farming Kits (Project SP-01)

Description: This initiative promotes urban sustainability by offering hands-on education and selling DIY urban gardening kits. It also transforms small urban spaces into food production sites and offers educational workshops for schools, families and community groups, encouraging reconnection through sustainable agricultural practices.

2 - Rural Co-Living Hubs (Project SP-02)

Description: This initiative aims to reactivate underused buildings in small rural towns by transforming them into co-living and co-working spaces, designed to promote well-being and reconnect remote workers and creatives with nature.

3 - Digital Pet Health Record (Project IT-01)

Description: This digital platform transforms pet care management by connecting pet owners with certified professionals via a mobile app offering digital medical records, appointment scheduling and service discovery.

4 - Music & Animal Therapy (Project IT-02)

Description: This initiative offers an innovative interdisciplinary care model by combining certified animal-assisted interventions with music therapy to foster healing, companionship, and emotional development, especially for underserved groups like the elderly

5 - Eco-Cycle Tourism (Project SK-01)

Description: This initiative aims to revitalise cycling routes in semi-rural areas by setting up designated rest and refreshment zones. This approach effectively combines sport, leisure and regional infrastructures.

6 - Circular Wool Textiles (Project SK-02)

Description: This project transforms surplus natural wool from local farms into artisanal clothing and homeware. By combining traditional techniques with environmentally friendly design principles, the project aims to revive regional craftsmanship and promote circular production.

7 - Food Digital platform (Project LV-01)

Description: This digital platform connects small-scale rural food producers with urban consumers. It serves as an online marketplace for fresh, healthy and traceable food, offering direct-to-door

8 - Sustainable Functional Beverages (Project LV-02)

Description: This consumer wellness brand offers innovative, plant-based functional beverage kits that combine nutrition, aesthetics and environmental sustainability. The brand directly contributes to environmental restoration by planting a tree with every purchase.

6. ADAPTATION OF THE GDEI-SENSITIVE IN-HABIT IHW SUB-DIMENSIONS TO THE REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS.

This analysis helps decision-makers map how each replicable business model addresses specific sub-dimensions of inequality, such as gender, age, disability, ethnicity, and sexual orientation. The B4B team created this mapping based on the IN-Habit project's IHW sub-dimensions that are sensitive to GDEI¹⁰. The portfolio demonstrated an excellent commitment to a Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (GDEI) approach. Through objective analysis, the team found that almost all of the candidate models met the model criteria (only three solutions did not meet the model criteria).

¹⁰ Source: D5.1 Toolkit for Stakeholders' Engagement with a Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Perspective

Table 6 - IHW sub-dimensions that are GDEI sensitive

IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to age	IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to sexual orientation	IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to gender	IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to disability	IHW sub-dimensions sensitive to ethnicity and religion
Spatial well-being	Discrimination	Security and violence	Social inclusion	Social inclusion
Safety	Security and violence	Discrimination	Social cohesion	Social cohesion
Social inclusion	Social cohesion	Employment	Spatial well-being	Discrimination
Social cohesion	Employment	Spatial well-being	Employment	Equality
Housing	Cultural participation	Leisure and free time	Financial situation	Cultural participation
Financial situation	Leisure and free time	Job and skill satisfaction		Leisure and free time
	Housing	Financial situation		
	Financial situation	Housing		

To ensure structural alignment, a strategic mapping was conducted connecting the GDEI-sensitive sub-dimensions of the IHW framework directly to the 16 Replicable Business Model.

Table 7 - Strategic Alignment Matrix:

ID	Replicable Business Model	IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions	Observations
1	IN-HABIT Data Platform	Safety; Spatial Well-being.	Age: The platform monitors heat/noise stressors that are experienced by the elderly and therefore disproportionately affect the “Spatial Well-being” of the elderly.
2	B4B Tailored Inclusive Business Training	Employment; Financial Situation; Equality; Social Inclusion	Gender/ethnicity: Customised curricula for women living in disadvantaged neighbourhoods (Las Palmeras) and women from the Roma community (Nitra) who are economically unstable.
3	Immersive Experience Training	Employment; Job & Skill Satisfaction; Social Inclusion	Disability: Bridges the “Employment” gap for individuals with Down syndrome by creating a de-risked work environment through Immersive Experience that builds vocational confidence.
4	Urban Farming Kits (project SP-01)	The solution did not explicitly target this	

ID	Replicable Business Model	IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions	Observations
5	Rural Co-Living Hubs (project SP-02)	Housing; Spatial Well-being	Age (youth): The platform addresses both “Housing” affordability and “Financial” precariousness for young professionals, creating a counter-narrative to rural depopulation.
6	The Āgenskalns Food Market	Social Cohesion; Cultural Participation; Financial Situation	Age (seniors): The Market functions as a “Social Cohesion” engine by making accessible infrastructure (e.g., lifts/ramps) available to enable older people to participate in public life. Financial: The Market provides support for the “Financial Situation” of Local Producers, enabling them to grow and sell products within the local market without the barriers they normally would encounter.
7	Food Digital Platform (project LV-01)	Financial Situation; Employment; Social Inclusion	Ethnicity: Mitigates both “Spatial” and “Economic” exclusion by linking rural producers directly to urban consumers, thereby bypassing traditional barriers to entry.
8	Sustainable Functional Beverages (project LV-02)	The solution did not explicitly target this	
9	Humanimal urban policy design centre (HADUP Centre)	Spatial Well-being; Equality; Social Inclusion	Disability/Age institutionalizes “Spatial Well-being” policies that recognize the human-animal relationship as essential for the mental health of socially isolated elderly and disabled people.
10	Animal Assisted Interventions (AAI)	Social Inclusion; Social Cohesion	Age (Elderly)/Disability: A non-pharmacological intervention for “Social Inclusion” will decrease cognitive decline and social isolation among residents in institutionalized settings.
11	Pet Care Services	Financial Situation; Security	Gender/Financial: Acts as an economic safety net (“Financial Situation”) preventing the trauma of pet abandonment for low-income owners (often women/single-parent households) during crises.
12	Digital Pet Health Record (project IT-01)	The solution did not explicitly target this	
13	Music & Animal Therapy (project IT-02)	Social Inclusion; Social Cohesion	Disability (Cognitive): Provides a multi-sensory pathway to “Social Inclusion” for neurodiverse children, addressing gaps in traditional verbal-centric therapies.

ID	Replicable Business Model	IHW GDEI Sensitive Sub-dimensions	Observations
14	Community Bike Sharing	Spatial Well-being; Financial Situation; Safety	Age (Youth): Delivers "Spatial Justice" by providing affordable mobility for youth, physically connecting segregated neighbourhoods (Dražovce) to city resources.
15	Eco-Cycle Tourism (project SK-01)	Leisure & Free Time	Age (Youth): Provides dedicated rest and refreshment zones for young cyclists.
16	Circular Wool Textiles (project SK-02)	Employment; Job & Skill Satisfaction; Cultural Participation	Gender/Ethnicity: Revives "Cultural Participation" and creates "Employment" for rural women and elderly male shepherds by valorising traditional crafts within a modern circular economy framework.

7. REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS ASSESSMENT WITHIN THE CÓRDOBA PILOT

The context of Córdoba: Córdoba, a city in Andalusia, Southern Spain, had 325,916 inhabitants in 2018 (European Commission, 2024a). It is the third largest and most populous city in Andalusia, after Seville and Málaga, and the 12th-largest in Spain. The city has a rich history and cultural heritage, dating back to Roman times, being the second largest, most cultured, and opulent city in Europe at the end of the first millennium. This enduring heritage has earned Córdoba the distinction of being the first city to hold four inscriptions on the World Heritage List, with tourism being a primary economic driver, recording over one million overnight stays in 2018.

Córdoba's Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS) are categorised as either 'hard' or 'soft' solutions aimed at improving Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW). The soft VIS in Córdoba refers to intangible processes and innovations implemented with local stakeholders, focusing on enhancing well-being and lifestyle behaviours, and is mainly linked to social and cultural innovations. The hard VIS refers to physical interventions or infrastructures implemented in urban spaces (María del Mar DELGADO-SERRANO et al., 2024).

Replicable business models: Of all the innovations created during Córdoba's pilot implementation, the partners identified two innovations as having potential for replication¹¹: the KER "IN-HABIT Data Platform", and the "immersive experience training for adults with Down syndrome", which is a subproduct from a training Programme developed in Córdoba for adults with Down syndrome.

¹¹ **Replicable business models** are developed by systematically analysing successful cases and identifying the good practices, people, types of customers, processes, practices, operational requirements, and critical factors for replication involved.

To evaluate the Societal Readiness Level (SRL) and Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) of the KER, VIS and subproducts with replication potential, the project partners completed a self-assessment questionnaire. The results are presented in the images below.

Figure 4 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire for the IN-HABIT Data Platform SLR and TRL levels.

Figure 5 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire for Immersive experience training for Down syndrome adults SLR and TRL levels.

The **IN-HABIT Data Platform**, has a TRL level of nine, indicating that the technology has been demonstrated in a relevant environment. A fully operational version is already in use, with sensors and networks deployed and connected in the four pilot cities (Córdoba, Riga, Lucca, and Nitra). An SRL of seven indicates that the solution is being refined and retested in a relevant environment with relevant stakeholders. The platform has potential for replication thanks to its scalable, interoperable, and open-source FIWARE-based architecture, based on citizen science and offering individual dashboards for the participants.

The **Immersive Experience training for adults with Down syndrome** has reached TRL level six, indicating that the problem has been validated through pilot testing in a relevant environment and that basic functionality has been demonstrated. The SRL level of seven indicates that the solution is being refined and retested in the relevant context, in cooperation with its target users and stakeholders.

7.1. IN-HABIT DATA PLATFORM

REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODEL DIMENSIONS

Disclaimer: This is a business model based on the IN-HABIT project. If you would like to use it as inspiration for your own project, you should develop a specific business plan tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

The IN-HABIT Data Platform is built entirely under a measurement-driven approach. One of its key objectives is to establish shared conclusions regarding improvements in the state of Health and Wellbeing across the four cities. To determine the measurement variables (air quality, number of people, radiation level, soil conditions, and weather state),

The IN-HABIT Data Platform is a unique, open, robust, and scalable interface designed to integrate seamlessly with other applications and APIs. It connects a network of sensors installed across public and private locations in the cities.

It features an intuitive and user-friendly dashboard, offering differentiated access to real-time and historical data. Users can apply filters to access information based on sensor types and other parameters. Its inclusive design, featuring a clear visual palette and accessible navigation, ensures its inclusiveness.

Powered by FIWARE technology, the Platform enables efficient data collection and analysis through an interconnectivity layer that complies with EU regulations.

The platform has been conceptualized to support three main objectives:

- To provide comprehensive visualisations of all data generated by the sensors, making it easier to interpret;
- to support research by generating real-time visualisations of key quantitative parameters, enabling immediate and precise monitoring; and
- to offer the option to download the collected data for further detailed analysis, enhancing researchers' ability to draw conclusions and develop evidence-based solutions.

The Data Platform unifies real-time and historical data from diverse sources into a robust Big Data infrastructure. It supports analytics, smart planning, and optimal operations through an open, scalable ecosystem with a holistic interface. Special relevance is given to its automatism feature for KPI analysis in a user-friendly dashboard, specifically designed for each of the implementation sites.

Source: IN-HABIT Deliverable 7.6 – Full Operative Data Platform

Some of the key features offered by the Platform are:

Data Collection and Ingestion:

- Integration with diverse IoT devices (e.g., air quality monitors, wearables, health kiosks, and mobility aids).
- Support for multiple protocols (e.g., MQTT, LoRaWAN, HTTP, and Bluetooth) for flexibility in device connectivity.

Real-Time Data Processing:

- Capabilities for processing real-time data streams to detect anomalies or trigger alerts (e.g., air pollution thresholds, irregular health patterns in wearable devices, etc.).

Data Analytics and Insights:

- Tools for analysing trends in public health and environmental conditions.
- Enables predictive analytics to forecast the use of public facilities.

Interoperability:

- Compliance with open standards (e.g., NGSI-LD for context information management) to ensure seamless integration with other city services and platforms.

Scalability and Flexibility:

- Designed to scale with the city's population and infrastructure growth.
- Modular architecture to accommodate new devices, data sources, or use cases.

User-Centric Services:

- Accessible dashboards for city officials, healthcare providers, and citizens.
- APIs for external developers to build applications enhancing community health and inclusivity.

Data Privacy and Security:

- Robust mechanisms for anonymizing sensitive health data.
- No personal health information is stored on the platform.
- Compliance with data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR, HIPAA).

Affordability:

- Leverages open-source solutions and cost-efficient technologies to suit the budget of smaller cities.

Source: IN-HABIT Deliverable 7.6 – Full Operative Data Platform

IN-HABIT Data Platform Photos

Figure 6 - Map of Córdoba in IN-HABIT

Figure 7 - Representation of collected metrics

Source: <https://www.fiware.org/2025/07/17/citizen-based-monitoring-of-inclusive-health-and-well-being/>

IN-HABIT Data Platform Photos

Figure 8 - Graphic representation of historical data

Figure 9 - Graphic representation of historical data

Source: <https://www.fiware.org/2025/07/17/citizen-based-monitoring-of-inclusive-health-and-well-being/>

Problem

A primary challenge for citizens and their communities is the limited availability of urban spaces that are inclusive, functional, and conducive to good health. This issue is exacerbated by a general lack of public awareness of important environmental factors such as air quality, noise levels, and ambient temperature, all of which have a significant impact on well-being. Furthermore, residents have few opportunities to participate in the co-design process, meaning urban solutions are rarely tailored to the specific needs of those they are intended to serve. Consequently, users of public spaces often find themselves in

environments that are inefficient or underutilised. This stems from poor initial design and a lack of adaptability to the community's evolving requirements. A critical aspect of this problem is inequitable access to facilities, which disadvantaged groups, including the elderly, children, and people with disabilities have. This limits their ability to engage fully with their local area.

Municipalities and decision-makers, who are responsible for urban stewardship, face major challenges in their efforts. They often lack access to the real-time and historical data required for effective urban planning and environmental interventions. The available data is often fragmented and non-standardised, making cross-city comparisons and scaling up successful solutions extremely challenging. This issue is further compounded by the absence of efficient tools for gauging the impact of urban innovations on public health and well-being, resulting in delays to crucial decision-making processes.

Value Proposition

IN-HABIT Data Platform is an open-access data platform, that has been developed with a scalable, interoperable, flexible and modular design, that supports long-term digital strategies. The Data platform has a scalable, interoperable and user-friendly design, as well as personalized dashboards for decision makers and researchers. Additionally, the platform provides a solid basis for the integration of real-time and historical data from multiple sources. The platform's architecture allows for the discovery of data through indexing, access through standardized APIs and complies with standards such as FIWARE and NGSI-LD. Moreover, the application of metadata and license terms also increase data reusability across different applications (research, policymaking, organizational). Furthermore, the platform integrates environmental, social and health-related data and therefore enables interdisciplinary research and creates new opportunities to generate innovative insights on public health, climate resilience and social equity.

IN-HABIT Data Platform Key competitive advantages

- **Full Interoperability Using FIWARE Standards:** The in-habit Data Platform is built from the ground up to be compliant with the full suite of FIWARE standards. The use of FIWARE and NGSI-LD standards provides for seamless integration of all types of data as well as existing urban systems and supports the connectivity between different cities and different sectors.
- **Personalized and Interactive Dashboards:** One of the most significant and innovative aspects of the in-habit Data Platform are the personalized and interactive dashboards. These dashboards provide actionable insights that are customized to each user (citizens, decision makers, and researchers). Citizens will have the ability to view real-time data related to environmental factors such as air quality, crowds, and noise, which will enable them to make better-informed decisions regarding their lifestyles.
- **Modelling Cities to Support Collaborative Planning:** Using City Modelling allows planners and stakeholders to create interactive models that represent the complex relationships in an urban system and show the effects of different policy changes (for example, creating parks or changing traffic flow) on public health and wellbeing, and environmental sustainability. This modelling capability enables collaborative planning and will provide evidence-based decision-making capabilities for urban planners and decision makers.

- **Predictive analytics enable simulations of future scenarios:** fostering collaborative planning and helping citizens visualise the outcomes of their contributions.
- **Inclusive and accessible design:** Built for inclusivity, the dashboards cater for diverse demographics with clear visuals and the option of multilingual support, as well as tools for users with varying levels of digital literacy.

Customer Segments (Beneficiaries/Users)

Primary market

- **Municipalities and local governments:** Focused on improving the design of public spaces, urban sustainability, and citizen well-being through data-driven decision-making.
- **Urban planners and city developers:** Seeking tools to optimise urban layouts, measure the impact of interventions and improve the usability of public spaces.
- **Research institutions and universities:** Engaged in urban studies, health and well-being research, or sustainability assessments.

Secondary market (potential):

- **NGOs and advocacy groups:** Those focused on promoting environmental sustainability, spatial health, and social equity in this area.
- **Private sector organisations:** Smart city solution providers and companies involved in urban infrastructure and IoT technologies, in particular.
- **Educational institutions:** They use the platform for teaching and research in subjects such as urban planning, environmental science, and public health.

Customer segments:

- **Decision-makers and municipal authorities.** Those interested in tools for evidence-based policymaking, evaluating urban interventions and community engagement.
- **Urban planners and architects:** Those who require insights for designing inclusive, sustainable public spaces and optimising urban infrastructure.
- **Researchers and academics:** Those conducting studies on urban health, climate change, and community behaviour require access to robust, interoperable data.
- **Citizens and community organisations:** Those interested in using the platform to raise awareness of environmental issues and participate in urban co-design initiatives.

Channels

The platform is accessible via a web interface. Scientific publications serve as a channel for wider

dissemination. Cross-learning events and workshops also facilitate knowledge transfer.

Customer Relations

Users: The Platform provides customisable dashboards that serve as the main interface through which users can access and visualise information.

Customers: Relationships with customers, such as municipal departments, are formalised through agreements and data-driven insights.

Funders: Relationships with funders are maintained through transparent reporting, shared visibility, and policy engagement.

Main Activities

The key activities include:

- **Development and management of the platform:** This process involves ensuring that the platform continuously evolved. This includes designing the architecture, setting up the cloud infrastructure, integrating FIWARE components, and ensuring compliance with standards.
- **Data Collection and Integration:** Continuous collection of real-time and historical data from various sources such as sensors (air quality, soil moisture, PAR radiation, cameras, water flow, people counters) in public and private locations.
- **Data Visualisation and Analysis:** Processing and displaying data through user-friendly dashboards and GIS mapping to facilitate interpretation and monitoring of key quantitative parameters.
- **Deploying sensor networks:** These physical devices, including street sensors and cameras, will monitor various environmental parameters such as air quality, temperature, noise and movement of people and traffic.

Key Resources

The key resources that support these activities include:

- **Online Platform:** The Platform to monitor environmental parameters related to Health and Wellbeing using citizen science is a core component designed to facilitate improved responsiveness and decision-making for operational demands through real-time remote monitoring and control of infrastructure and on-field devices.
- **Sensors:** Sensors are critical data sources for the Data Platform, alongside cameras, open data, and the mobile app.
- **Human Resources:** Data engineers, app developers, and tech experts for sensors.
- **Insurance and permits:** These are two key resources that must be taken into consideration when planning activities such as deploying sensor networks, as they can incur significant costs.

Key partners

The key delivery partners include:

- **Pilot City Leads:** Co-coordinates and supports local implementation.
- **Local Organisations and Public Entities in Pilot Cities.**
- **Technical partners:** Partners with software and technical skills to develop the app and manage the sensors and camera units to monitor environmental parameters.

Competition

- Platforms such as BreezoMeter and Plume Labs specialise in providing real-time air quality and environmental data with high accuracy and detailed metrics.
- Use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and traditional urban planning tools (e.g. ArcGIS Urban, a leading tool for urban planning and spatial analysis).
- The Google Environmental Insights Explorer (EIE), which uses exclusive data sources and modelling capabilities to help cities and regions measure emissions sources, run analyses, and identify strategies to reduce emissions
- Other competitors include standalone monitoring systems, manual data collection, and surveys.

Cost Structure

The breakdown of the costs is as follows:

- **Infrastructure and Equipment:** Costs for the app development, development and maintenance of the cloud infrastructure, acquisition, and installation of physical devices such as sensors and cameras
- **Personnel Costs:** Salaries for the teams across all the cities.
- **Communication and Dissemination:** Production of communication materials, website, social media campaigns, and costs associated with media presence.

Revenue Streams

The data Platform could generate revenue through subscriptions for access to the platform.

Surplus

In the context of a social business model, any surplus generated by the Platform would be reinvested to increase its social impact and help it to achieve its mission. This would align with the purpose of promoting inclusive economic development and encouraging community ownership of urban spaces by attracting public and private investment. The surplus would primarily be used to enhance the platform's functionalities and expand its reach.

Social Impact Measurement

This impact strategy is structured around a Theory of Change, which articulates how the project's activities are expected to lead to the desired social impact. Engage citizens. Collect data, inform action, and improve the environment and health.

Table 8 - Key Impact Indicators (KIIs)

<p>Improving environmental Health and Wellbeing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-Time Monitoring: IoT air quality sensors can measure pollutants (e.g., PM2.5, CO2, and NO2) in real-time across public spaces like community patios, parks, relational areas, or markets. • Localized Insights: Data can reveal pollution hotspots, identify trends, and determine how urban activities (e.g., traffic, and festivals) impact air quality. • Health Alerts: Automated alerts can notify citizens, particularly disadvantaged groups (e.g., children, elderly, and those with respiratory issues) when air quality is poor. • Sustainability Efforts: Insights can guide policies to reduce emissions and promote pedestrian zones or green corridors. 	<p>Optimising the use and inclusiveness of public spaces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foot Traffic Analysis: IoT-enabled people counters can track the flow and density of visitors in parks, markets, or cultural venues. • Behavioural Patterns: Data can identify peak usage times, underutilized space. • Design Optimization: Insights can inform the design and deployment of inclusive amenities (e.g., seating, lighting, and ramps). • Social Distancing: In the context of public health crises (e.g., COVID-19), sensors can monitor crowding and assist in enforcing safety protocols.
<p>Enhancing Wellbeing with Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stress-Free Environments: Data from sensors can identify factors like noise pollution, overcrowding, or poor air quality that negatively impact mental health. • Green Space Enhancement: Environmental sensors can evaluate the impact of urban greening projects on air quality, temperature regulation, and biodiversity. • Targeted Interventions: IoT insights can help design interventions tailored to specific communities, addressing health disparities effectively. 	<p>Cross-City Comparisons</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized Metrics: IoT platforms with interoperable standards allow cities to measure and compare indicators like air quality, foot traffic, or accessibility consistently. • Best Practices: Analytics can highlight successful interventions in one city that could be adapted for another. • Collaborative Learning: IoT-driven insights foster dialogue and collaboration between stakeholders in cities
<p>Enabling a Sustainable and Inclusive Future</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data for Policy: Sensor data supports evidence-based policymaking to sustain Health and Wellbeing initiatives. • Cost-Effectiveness: IoT's real-time monitoring reduces reliance on manual data collection, making solutions affordable for small and medium-sized cities. • Innovation Ecosystem: APIs and open data promote third-party innovation, encouraging startups, NGOs, and academic institutions to build solutions aligned with IHW goals. 	

Macro-Environment (PESTEL Analysis)

- **Political:** The project benefits from incentives under the EU Green Deal and aims to align with municipal data-sharing policies.
- **Economic:** As technology for creating software becomes more affordable and accessible, it will become increasingly feasible to develop new functionalities for the platform.
- **Social:** Relevant for social communities
- **Technological:** The Internet of Things (IoT) is becoming increasingly prevalent, as is mobile technology. This means that this solution can become more intuitive for users, dependable and more efficient.
- **Environmental:** There is a growing demand for IHW's technical solutions, which focus on collecting and analysing environmental data in urban areas.
- **Legal:** A critical aspect is ensuring data protection, GDPR compliance and adhering to environmental data accuracy standards.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Please find below a suggestion for the critical success factors and barriers to implementation. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to function as a starting point for further discussion. Critical success factors (CSFs) are the essential conditions that must be met for a business model to be successfully implemented in a new context.

Critical success factors

- **Prioritise people-centred design and outcome focus.** Start by identifying unmet needs and challenges in cities and considering how these can be met more efficiently using digital technologies. Solutions should be co-created with citizens to ensure equity, accessibility, and direct benefits for all demographic groups.
- **Invest in pilot projects and agile methodologies.** Adopt a phased, iterative approach, starting with smaller-scale pilot projects to evaluate solutions and gather feedback from stakeholders and users. Define clear metrics and benchmarks for success and be prepared to iterate rapidly or 'fail fast' and learn from failures.
- **Cultivate a data-driven culture and enhance digital skills.** Support city administrations in developing their digital capabilities and fostering an environment where evidence-based decision-making is standard practice. This involves training staff, spreading digital expertise across departments, and presenting data insights in a way that is easy for decision-makers to understand.
- **Building Trust:** Gaining the trust of citizens and city administrations regarding data privacy and security is paramount. Mismanaged collaborative processes or the perceived misuse of data can erode trust and impact adoption.

Barriers to Implementation

- **Cost modelling:** Developing a robust, integrated data platform with big data capabilities, sensor network integration and advanced analytics tools requires a significant initial investment. Furthermore, attracting and retaining skilled talent in data science requires competitive compensation, which adds to operational costs.

Regulatory mapping: Navigating the complex and stringent EU regulatory environment poses a significant challenge. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) imposes strict requirements on the processing of personal data, necessitating careful compliance with regard to data collection, storage, sharing and ethical use. New entrants must also map and adhere to national-level data protection laws and privacy principles and potentially obtain data protection and service quality certifications. Design must address the risk of algorithmic bias and ensure equitable access to services.

Replication prerequisites

- **People:** The successful operationalisation of the platform relies on a specialised human capital structure that goes beyond standard IT support. Strategically, this requires data stewards to maintain system architecture and ensure continuous data integrity, as well as municipal analysts capable of translating raw dashboard metrics into actionable urban planning decisions. To ensure regulatory compliance and maintain public trust, it is crucial to have a designated Data Protection Officer (DPO) to oversee strict GDPR adherence, particularly with regard to the anonymisation of sensitive citizen data.
- **Processes:** From a procedural perspective, the replication model demands rigorous governance frameworks to ensure data longevity and utility. This involves implementing a formal data management plan aligned with FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) to standardise collection and sharing. Furthermore, cities must adopt interoperability protocols using standard APIs to facilitate communication with legacy systems and prevent vendor lock-in. This is supported by a scheduled maintenance routine to mitigate physical risks and prevent data gaps in the sensor network.
- **Other requisites:** Technologically, the business model requires a resilient backbone capable of handling big data loads. This requires a scalable cloud infrastructure (such as AWS or on-premises equivalents) for secure processing and storage. This must be coupled with an IoT network of environmental and presence sensors that remains compatible with standard communication protocols to ensure the physical capture layer is robust enough to feed the digital ecosystem.

Strategy monitoring

Please find below a suggestion for a strategy monitoring model. This is a *non-exhaustive* list and is intended to be a starting point for further discussion.

Table 9 - Strategy monitoring indicators (Key Performance Indicators)

<p>1) People dimension (Customer Perspective or Stakeholder Engagement)</p> <p>Strategic objectives: Ensure high satisfaction and a positive perception among stakeholders in target areas.</p> <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of stakeholders involved in implementation efforts • Stakeholder feedback (e.g. from surveys, focus groups or interviews) 	<p>2) Processes dimension (Internal Processes & Service Provision)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the full operationalisation of the Platform to monitor environmental parameters related to Health and Wellbeing using citizen science to enable seamless data integration and visualisation in new locations. • Facilitate smooth and efficient integration between the platform and other relevant urban data systems. • Implement and standardise key processes. • Ensure the quality of the implemented services. • Establish robust monitoring and evaluation systems to ensure consistent data collection. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency of internal processes. • Number of integrated innovations.
<p>3) Growth and Learning dimension</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop the organisational capacity and the team's experience. • Foster innovation and the continuous improvement of the business model based on experience. • Improve inter-city learning and the sharing of solutions. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of knowledge-sharing events 	<p>4) Financial dimension</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generating revenue in a sustainable way. • Maximising cost efficiency. • Ensure positive return on investment (ROI). • Secure adequate funding for expansion and new implementations. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of paying customers. • Total revenue generated from Platform.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revenue generated by area of activity or initiative. • Profitability (net profit margin) or ROI of investments.
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MARKET ANALYSIS

Disclaimer: This is a market analysis developed for an IN-HABIT project. Some of the information may be outdated or inaccurate. If you wish to implement this idea, you should conduct specific market research tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Market Overview

The market for data applications measuring Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW) indicators in Europe is primarily within the smart cities and public health technology industries. The product/service focus is on providing comprehensive data platforms, advanced analytics tools, and interactive visualisation dashboards.

The market is defined by the intersection of urban development, digital transformation, and public well-being initiatives in Europe. Geographically, the market covers small and medium-sized cities (SMSCs) seeking innovative solutions to well-being challenges. In terms of product type, the market includes:

- **Data Collection Systems:** These systems integrate data from various sources, including environmental sensors (e.g. for CO₂, temperature, noise, and waste levels), people-counting sensors, street cameras, and existing databases.
- **Data management and processing platforms:** These are solutions capable of integrating, managing, and normalising large volumes of multi-structured real-time and historical data.
- **Advanced analytics and visualisation tools:** These tools produce interactive scenarios and Geographic Information System (GIS) maps, analyse real-time data, and generate customisable dashboards and performance reports to monitor Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and support decision-making. These tools provide insight into complex correlations and enable predictive analytics and 'what if' analysis to improve planning

Market Size and Growth

Urban centres with a population of at least 50,000 are considered high-density clusters and represent major cities. There are over 800 such centres in Europe, as well as more than 9,000 towns¹². The images below illustrates the distribution of urban and town centres throughout Europe and the distribution of population density in Europe, measured in inhabitants per km², highlights territorial asymmetries.

¹² https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/maps/urban-centres-towns_en

Figure 10 - Urban centres and towns in Europe

Source; Eurostat
https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/maps/urban-centres-towns_en

Figure 11 - Population density, 2011 (number of inhabitants/ km²)

Source; Eurostat - <https://ec.europa.eu/statistical-atlas/viewer/?config=typologies.json&ch=CITYCOMMZ ONE&mid=BKGCNT,POPGRDGST2011,CNTOVL&o=1,1,0.7¢er=49.49861,22.65308,3&lcis=POPGRDG ST2011&>

The European market for IHW data applications is set to grow, driven by strong political will and societal needs (European Commission: Joint Research Centre et al., 2025). The OECD's Report 'How's Life? 2024 report' (OECD, 2024) further highlights the importance of addressing various dimensions of well-being, revealing warning signs in areas such as health, subjective well-being, and social connectedness in OECD countries, including those in Europe. This indicates a demand for data-driven interventions. The continuous growth of urbanisation, with 56% of the world's population currently living in cities and this figure projected to rise to 68% by 2050 (World Economic Forum, 2022e), further emphasises the need for smart city solutions that can measure and improve well-being. The estimated infrastructure investment required for global urbanisation is USD 3.7 trillion per year until 2050 (World Economic Forum, 2016). A part of this investment may involve digital technologies and data platforms, which are needed to address urban demands efficiently and sustainably.

Competitive landscape (Porter's five forces):

Threat of New Entrants: Threat of New Entering the IHW data application market in Europe faces significant barriers, primarily relating to the capital requirements for sophisticated data infrastructure, such as big data processing and IoT networks. New entrants must also navigate a complex and evolving regulatory landscape, particularly the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which imposes strict rules on the collection, storage, and usage of personal data across Europe.

Bargaining power of buyers: Buyers in this market, predominantly city administrations and public bodies, have considerable bargaining power. They demand highly customised solutions that are tailored to their unique local contexts and specific unmet needs.

Bargaining power of suppliers: The supplier landscape is diverse and includes sensor manufacturers, data platform providers, and analytics specialists. Although the abundance of IoT device and data acquisition system suppliers dilutes their individual power, specialised providers of complex big data analytics may have more leverage thanks to their unique capabilities. However, the push for open standards and interoperability in smart city initiatives prevents vendor lock-in and thus mitigates supplier power.

Threat of Substitute Products or Services: Substitutes exist in the form of traditional, less integrated data collection methods, such as manual surveys and isolated departmental databases, as well as generic statistical reports that do not offer real-time insights or a holistic view of IHW.

Rivalry among existing competitors: The market comprises a variety of established technology companies, specialised smart city solution providers, and academic/research initiatives.

Market Opportunities and Risks

Market Opportunities

- **Strong Political and Policy Drive:** The EU's explicit commitment to “beyond GDP” metrics and sustainable well-being, as demonstrated by the SIWB initiative, fosters a favourable policy environment and potential funding streams for IHW data applications (European Commission: Joint Research Centre et al., 2025). This political momentum creates demand for comprehensive, outcome-oriented solutions.
- **Vast untapped data potential:** Currently, less than 1% of IoT data is used, presenting a significant opportunity to generate value from existing and new data streams (World Economic Forum, 2022e). Effectively integrating, analysing, and visualising this data can enable applications to generate novel insights for urban management and well-being improvement.
- **Contribution to standardisation:** Actively engaging with and contributing to the development of new standards (e.g. for data formats, interoperability, and ethical frameworks) can establish providers as influential figures in the development of smart city data ecosystems, encouraging broader acceptance and simpler integration of their solutions.
- **Cross-sectoral integration:** The ability to correlate data across various urban domains, such as transport, housing, healthcare, the environment, and social services, can provide a holistic view of well-being and unlock synergies that would not be possible with siloed data.

Market Risks

Privacy and cybersecurity concerns: The widespread use of IoT sensors and the collection of sensitive personal data pose significant privacy and security risks. Data breaches or algorithmic bias incidents can severely erode public trust and lead to regulatory penalties.

Implementation and scaling challenges: Scaling up successful pilot projects to city-wide or national levels can be complicated by technical, organisational, and financial obstacles. Organisational resistance to change and a lack of digital literacy within city administrations can hinder effective deployment.

7.2. IMMERSIVE EXPERIENCE TRAINING

REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODEL DIMENSIONS

Disclaimer: This is a business model based on the IN-HABIT project. If you would like to use it as inspiration for your own project, you should develop a specific business plan tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Immersive experience training

The immersive experience provides a ludic software designed for adults with Down Syndrome to strengthen their abilities in event organisation, specifically in the role of congress hosts and hostesses. It offers a virtual space where users can practise specific tasks, problem-solving, decision-making, and time management within a safe environment, preparing them to apply these skills in real-world settings. The methodology employed facilitates learning through repetition and the structuring of clear objectives. It also incorporates elements like a mentor-guide avatar (María Jesús), a Help button, sound effects, vibrant colours, and a realistic, immersive environment to encourage user engagement.

The immersive experience is delivered as a multi-platform tool that can be accessed on computers, tablets and mobile phones. However, tablet use is recommended due to its user-friendly features. Accessibility features, such as the Easy Reading technique for verbal information (replicated via subtitles in clear, simple language) and visually warm elements, cater to users with comprehension difficulties or visual impairment. The immersive experience was developed using virtual tour software featuring 3D-designed, hyper-realistic settings (D5Render). Data collection, design and dashboards can be offered to managers or trainers.

Content creation involves developing four main scenarios: Setup, Catering, Reception/Check-in and Person Hall Support, as well as a transversal Dressing Room, in which users can choose and dress their avatars. Within each scenario, users perform specific tasks such as arranging furniture and signage, registering attendees, distributing welcome packs, assisting with microphones during Question-and-Answer sessions, seating guests and serving food and beverages. The experience also involves resolving unforeseen incidents during tasks. Custom scripts track user interactions, including click patterns and time spent, to monitor and enhance the learning journey.

A key element is María Jesús, an avatar designed using artificial intelligence to serve as a supportive mentor-guide. She guides users through activities, assists with queries, reminds them of tasks and encourages them as they achieve objectives. She has a neutral and approachable aesthetic, with round eyes to facilitate connection. Her voice and natural expressions (achieved through face-tracking) convey encouragement and concern, helping to build a bond with the user. Users can request assistance from María Jesús via the integrated Help button. 'Lectura Fácil' (Easy Reading) is used for all verbal information to ensure that instructions and messages are clear and concise and accompanied by accessible subtitles. This is particularly beneficial for users with reading comprehension difficulties.

The visual design uses warm, non-strident colours, relatable avatars and clear iconography to enhance immersion and user-friendliness for all users, including those with visual impairments. Positive feedback mechanisms, such as sound effects, vibrant colours and confirmation messages when tasks are completed correctly, encourage engagement. Users also earn insignias (trophies) upon successfully completing each scenario, which reinforces their achievements (Cristina Garita & Sergio Vegas, n.d.).

The experience is hosted on the service provider's platform. Users can access it via the dedicated website. All services are fully integrated within the online platform. An offline mode is also available, but this does not support data registration. Cloud hosting services hosts the platform and securely stores all data and databases.

Source: Manual de acompañamiento al usuario_IN-HABIT Experience

Problem

Despite their valuable strengths, such as social skills, empathy, commitment, responsibility, adaptability and attention to detail, individuals with Down's syndrome face significant barriers to employment. This underemployment represents a missed opportunity for their autonomy and deprives society of their potential contributions.

Value Proposition

The immersive experience was designed to strengthen both social and motor skills, thereby promoting greater autonomy and contributing to the health and well-being of the users. The pilot of the IN-HABIT Experience involved individuals from a people with Down syndrome association, demonstrating direct engagement with the target user group. that can be accessed on computers, tablets and mobile phones. However, tablet use is recommended due to its user-friendly features. Accessibility features, such as the Easy Reading technique for verbal information (replicated via subtitles in clear, simple language) and visually warm elements, cater to users with comprehension difficulties or visual impairment. The immersive experience was developed using virtual tour software featuring 3D-designed, hyper-realistic settings (D5Render). Data collection, design and dashboards can be offered to managers or trainers.

Immersive experience training key competitive advantages:

- **Tailored and Inclusive Design for Neurodiverse Individuals:** Unlike generic training solutions, this immersive experience is specifically designed to cater to the unique needs and strengths of neurodiverse people, particularly adults with Down Syndrome. It incorporates accessibility features such as the "Easy Reading" technique for verbal information through clear, simple language subtitles and uses visually warm elements. The inclusion of a mentor-guide avatar named María Jesús, designed with a neutral and approachable aesthetic and natural expressions, further enhances user engagement and connection.
- **Safe and Realistic Immersive Learning Environment:** The platform provides a virtual space where users can practice specific vocational tasks, problem-solving, decision-making, and time management in a safe and controlled environment. This is a significant advantage over real-world training, as it allows for repeated practice and error-making without real-world consequences.
- **Effective Pedagogical Approach for Skill Consolidation:** The methodology behind the immersive experience facilitates learning through repetition and the structuring of clear objectives, which is highly effective for consolidating learning among this population. It integrates gamified elements such as sound effects, vibrant colours, and positive feedback mechanisms.
- **Holistic Skill Development and Well-being Focus:** Beyond just vocational skills, the experience is designed to strengthen both social and motor skills, directly promoting greater autonomy and contributing to the overall health and well-being of the users. This holistic approach distinguishes it from programs that might only focus on narrow technical skills, fostering confidence and self-esteem.
- **Multi-Platform Accessibility and Data Management:** The immersive experience is delivered as a multi-platform tool, accessible on computers, tablets, and mobile phones, though tablet use is recommended for its user-friendly features. This broad accessibility ensures wider reach, particularly for populations who may have older devices or limited digital literacy.

Customer Segments (Beneficiaries/Users)

The primary customers and beneficiaries are adults with Down's syndrome. The immersive experience is designed to leverage their inherent strengths, such as social skills, empathy, commitment, responsibility, adaptability in structured contexts and attention to detail. These strengths are valuable in various work environments.

Channels

The immersive experience is delivered as a multi-platform tool that can be accessed on computers, tablets, and mobile phones. However, tablet use is recommended due to its user-friendly features. With regard to physical engagement, workshops can be conducted at neurodiversity associations, local community centres, and job fairs. Furthermore, partnerships will be pivotal, involving collaborations with vocational

schools and the human resources (HR) departments of various companies to facilitate outreach and integration.

Customer Relations

There are several mechanisms that can be employed to foster customer relations, with the aim of ensuring user support and engagement:

- In-App relations can provide personalised learning paths and enable comprehensive progress tracking for each individual.
- Community relations can involve direct employer consultations.
- Feedback mechanisms can include various methods such as surveys.

Main Activities

- Create engaging training content to ensure relevance. This includes conceptualising an event and using it as a central theme, replicating real-world locations, and incorporating typical city motifs. Crucial ongoing activities include data collection to evaluate user performance over time. This includes metrics such as time spent per scenario, task durations, errors made and Help button usage. This allows comparison with real-world skill practice.
- Regularly maintain and update the tablet app platform to ensure it functions optimally.
- Conduct user onboarding and testing sessions to familiarise users with the app and the learning process.
- Use systematic data analytics to evaluate Programme impact and measure effectiveness.
- Market the Programme to employers and organisations to boost adoption and job opportunities.

Key Resources

- **Human resources:** This includes content creators, app developers, disability education specialists, and data analysts. The human resources comprise the research team from the University, experienced video game developers and professionals and management from the Down Syndrome Association.
- **Technical resources:** Crucial technological components include tablets for user interaction, software for creating immersive experiences and reliable cloud servers for storing and making data accessible. Technical resources: Crucial technological components include tablets for user interaction, software for creating immersive experiences and reliable cloud servers for storing and making data accessible. Key resources include the D5Render virtual tour software used for development and the provider platform, which hosts the immersive experience.
 - María Jesús, the mentor-guide avatar, was designed using generative AI for her appearance and voice, and her expressions are natural thanks to face-tracking technology. The content itself is also integral, comprising the four main scenarios, sub-sections, interactive elements, visual assets (such as vibrant colours and realistic environments) and sound effects.
 - The technical infrastructure comprises devices with sufficient RAM (4 GB+), Qualcomm

Snapdragon chips, Android operating systems (from 2022 onwards), and high-speed internet (80–100 Mb/s fibre optic recommended).

- **Intellectual resources:** This category includes the Programme's training modules and user data analytics, which can inform future improvements.
- **Methodological resources:** Include the gamification approach with an emphasis on repetition and structured objectives, as well as the implementation of “Lectura Fácil” to enhance accessibility.

Key partners

- The university provided the research team and is acknowledged as a co-author of the user manual.
- The developer company, which has experience in video game development, played a key role in creating the software and is hosting the immersive experience on its platform.
- The Down Association played a vital role in enabling the project to proceed, and its professionals and members participated in the pilot experience, contributing directly to the testing of the immersive experience.

Competition

Specific competitors are specialized content producers for assistive technologies. The broader assistive technology market encompasses a range of products and services.

Cost Structure

- **Content production:** Including scripting and designing immersive experiences. The cost structure would comprise software development expenses, including virtual tour software and the creation of hyper-realistic 3D settings. Content creation costs would be incurred for designing scenarios and interactive elements, creating the María Jesús avatar (including an AI-generated voice and visuals), and integrating sound effects and visuals.
- **App development and ongoing maintenance:** Additional costs would include ongoing maintenance, updates, and potential technical support for the platform and content. There will also be recurring platform hosting fees.
- **Marketing and outreach:** Campaigns and event participation.
- **Staff salaries:** For project managers, developers, and support personnel. Research and development costs associated with the university research team would also be incurred. Costs related to pilot testing with individuals from the Down's Syndrome Association would also be included.
- **Overhead expenses:** Such as office space and administrative costs.

Revenue Streams

Potential revenue sources:

- **Licensing:** Offering licences for the software to other organisations, enabling them to implement the training program.

- Grants: Funding secured from government bodies and various foundations.

Surplus

In the context of a social business model, any surplus generated by the immersive training experience Programme for adults with Down's syndrome would be reinvested to increase its social impact and help fulfil its purpose. For example, this surplus could be invested in research and development initiatives for new training modules, ensuring the Programme's continuous improvement and expansion.

Social Impact Measurement

The "Immersive experience training for Down syndrome adults" is designed to enhance autonomy, confidence, and employment readiness in adults with Down syndrome through customizable training.

Table 10 - Key Impact Indicators (KIs)

Short-term output	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term Outcomes (impacts)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants enrolled. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive feedback from users. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of users who have improved their autonomy

Macro-Environment (PESTEL Analysis)

Political: The European Union's commitment to social inclusion and disability rights is a key political driver. National governments are encouraged to develop and implement assistive technology (AT) policies and action plans.

Economic: The European labour market faces labour shortages in various sectors and economies, creating an incentive for businesses to explore untapped talent pools (World Economic Forum, 2023a). The high unemployment rate among working-age individuals with Down Syndrome indicates a significant economic challenge that such initiatives aim to alleviate by fostering workforce participation

Social: There is a social need to address the significant barriers, substantial risk of poverty and social exclusion experienced by disabled people. Society is increasingly moving towards a skills-first approach to talent management, emphasising a person's skills and competencies over traditional qualifications. This could democratise access to economic opportunities for more people (World Economic Forum, 2023a).

Technological: Assistive technologies are transforming various sectors, including education and training. The shift towards digitalisation requires improved digital skills and access to digital tools for disabled people.

Legal: Data protection regulations such as the GDPR are highly relevant because the processing of personal data relating to individuals in the EU by non-EU entities also falls under their remit. The enforcement of anti-discrimination laws and the provision of reasonable adjustments are also legal requirements (World Economic Forum, 2023a).

Environmental: The global shift towards a green energy transition is reshaping workforces and creating

demand for new skills (World Economic Forum, 2023a).

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Critical success factors (CSFs) are the essential conditions that must be met for a business model to be successfully implemented in a new context. Please find below a suggestion for the critical success factors and barriers to implementation. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to function as a starting point for further discussion.

Critical success factors

- **Strong and collaborative partnerships** between research institutions, technology developers and target community organisations (Down syndrome associations) are fundamental.
- **User-centric design and accessibility features**, such as the María Jesús avatar, Easy reading and warm visuals, are crucial for effective engagement and learning for individuals with Down Syndrome.
- **Robust technical infrastructure and multiplatform compatibility** ensure wide accessibility and a smooth user experience, with tablet use specifically recommended.
- **Engaging and realistic content, including interactive dynamics, practical exercises, and a realistic immersive environment**, encourages sustained user participation.

Barriers to Implementation

- **Capital requirements:** Developing innovative immersive content and ensuring realistic, immersive experiences requires significant investment in hardware, software, and skilled personnel.
- **GDPR compliance:** Strict adherence to the GDPR is paramount when dealing with the personal data of trainees, especially sensitive data relating to disability or performance during training.
- **National regulations for disability support:** Varying national legal frameworks and support systems for disabled people across EU Member States can affect the transferability of solutions.

Replication prerequisites

- **People:** The successful replication of this model requires a multidisciplinary support ecosystem that bridges the gap between social care and the labour market. From an operational perspective, this necessitates the involvement of psychologists or social workers to guide users through the emotional and behavioural aspects of the training journey and ensure their well-being is prioritised. Crucially, the model relies on corporate partners, specifically HR departments within the events sector, to validate the training and commit to offering internships or employment, thereby ensuring a tangible economic outcome. Dedicated tech support is essential for managing software updates and resolving hardware issues, preventing disruption to the learning process.
- **Processes:** The operational success of this solution depends on the strict application of neurodiverse-friendly methodologies. The process must adhere to “Easy Reading” standards to ensure that all instructions are cognitively accessible, coupled with repetitive learning mechanisms that use gamification to consolidate skills through structured practice. Furthermore, the model requires an accompanied placement protocol, which is a critical transition phase in which participants move from

virtual simulation to real-world employment under on-site supervision. This ensures the safe and effective transfer of learned skills.

- **Other requisites:** Important to maintain the fidelity of the immersive environment, the business model demands high-specification infrastructure. This includes high-performance hardware, specifically tablets with a minimum of 4 GB of RAM and specific processors (e.g. Snapdragon), to run the 3D simulations smoothly without lag, which could otherwise disorientate users. Additionally, high-speed connectivity (80–100 Mb/s) is essential to support continuous cloud-based data tracking and the rapid loading of heavy digital content.

Strategy monitoring

Please find below a suggestion for a strategy monitoring model. This is a *non-exhaustive* list and is intended to be a starting point for further discussion.

Table 11 - Strategy monitoring indicators (Key Performance Indicators)

<p>1) People dimension (Customer Perspective or Stakeholder Engagement)</p> <p>Strategic objectives: Ensuring high levels of user engagement and satisfaction to lead to effective skill acquisition and enhanced autonomy for beneficiaries.</p> <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total time spent on each scenario by users. • Number of completed sessions per user. • Qualitative feedback from users, families, and Down's Syndrome associations (e.g. through surveys, interviews, or pilot testing feedback). 	<p>2) Processes dimension (Internal Processes & Service Provision)</p> <p>Strategic objectives: To ensure that the immersive experience operates efficiently and provides clear guidance, effectively facilitating skill development and problem-solving abilities.</p> <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency of platform access and usage. • Usage rate of the “Help” button, indicating points of confusion or difficulty. • User registration and retention rates. • Intermediate and task-specific durations for completing activities within scenarios. • Total time taken to complete full itinerates for specific roles. • Time analysis for specific sub-sections to identify areas that present extra challenges for users. • Number of errors made by users during tasks. • Registration of specific clicks indicating failures or incorrect actions. • Incidence of technical issues (e.g. unresponsive screens, sound loops, and
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	connection problems) to monitor platform stability.
<p>3) Growth and Learning dimension</p> <p>Strategic objectives: The aim is to continually improve the immersive experience, adapt it to evolving needs and expand its reach and applicability to new skills and demographics.</p> <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of new modules developed and their successful integration. • Growth in the total number of registered users/beneficiaries. • Successful integration of new features or accessibility improvements into the platform. 	<p>4) Financial dimension</p> <p>Strategic objectives: To ensure the financial sustainability of the social business model and to efficiently allocate resources to maximise social impact.</p> <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of paying customers. • Cost per user/beneficiary to assess efficiency and scalability. • Revenue generated by area of activity or initiative. • Profitability (net profit margin) or ROI of investments. • Total program costs and cost-effectiveness over time.

MARKET ANALYSIS

Disclaimer: This is a market analysis developed for an IN-HABIT project. Some of the information may be outdated or inaccurate. If you wish to implement this idea, you should conduct specific market research tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Market Overview

The scope of this market analysis is confined to assistive technology (AT), a broad field encompassing products and services designed to maintain or improve an individual’s functioning and independence, thereby promoting their overall well-being and participation in all domains of life. This includes both physical products and digital solutions such as software and applications that support interpersonal communication, access to information, daily time management, rehabilitation, education, and training. The product and service focus is on interactive tablet applications that aim to provide engaging and immersive training Programmes. These applications fall under the category of digital assistive products, which are increasingly seen as a key enabler for learning, communication, and social integration for individuals with disabilities. The contents can be adapted to suit the type of job and the skills being taught. High-quality applications and software are particularly beneficial because they can incorporate the repetition and practice necessary for consolidating learning among this population. The content must be tailored to the cognitive and motor challenges associated with Down Syndrome, ensuring accessibility and effectiveness.

Market Size and Growth

Although the authors didn't find any specific estimates of the demand for content for immersive experiences for people with Down's syndrome, the global assistive technology market is substantial and projected for significant growth. Currently, over 1 billion people worldwide require at least one assistive product (Intellectual Property Organization WIPO, 2021). The market size was estimated at US\$14 billion in 2015 and projected to reach between US\$26 billion and US\$31 billion by 2024, further expanding to US\$35.6 billion by 2026 (Intellectual Property Organization WIPO, 2021).

Target Audience

The primary target audience is individuals with Down's syndrome who are of working age and seeking employment opportunities. This target audience often faces considerable barriers when it comes to accessing traditional work experience, due to societal and professional biases regarding their capabilities (World Economic Forum, 2023a). They often benefit from a learning approach that includes tailored support structures, such as job coaching, individualised needs assessments and ongoing practical support. According to data from the European Health Information Gateway¹³, the number of people with Down's syndrome has been growing, with a significant increase in 2009. This means that, in some years, the number of people with Down's syndrome who are of legal working age will be much higher. The image below illustrates the growth in the number of births involving Down's syndrome throughout Europe.

Figure 12 – Evolution of the number of births with Down's syndrome

There is also an asymmetrical distribution of births with Down's syndrome in Europe.

¹³ Source: <https://gateway.euro.who.int/>

Figure 13 – Number of births with Down's syndrome

The other primary target audience is non-governmental organisations (NGOs) across Europe that are dedicated to providing direct assistance to individuals with Down's syndrome and their families, as well as promoting inclusion, advocacy, and support. An analysis of the main networks in the disability sector reveals that there are hundreds of organisations worldwide addressing this issue. Examples of networks in the disability sector:

- **Global Down Syndrome Foundation** - This organization is a public non-profit dedicated to significantly improving the lives of people with Down syndrome. It achieves this through research, medical care, education, and advocacy¹⁴.
- **European Association of Service providers for Persons with Disabilities (EASPD)** - EASPD is recognized as a leading voice for disability services across Europe. It focuses on promoting human rights and equal opportunities for people with disabilities through effective and high-quality support systems¹⁵.
- **EU for Trisomy 21 (eufortrisomy21)** - EU for Trisomy 21 is a collaborative platform connecting partners across 23 EU countries, working to improve the lives of people with Down syndrome (Trisomy 21). It aims to share ideas, collaborate, and advocate to the European Union, raising awareness about intellectual disabilities¹⁶.

¹⁴ Source: Global Down Syndrome Foundation About Page - <https://www.globaldownsyndrome.org/about-down-syndrome/resources/international-down-syndrome-organizations-clinics/>

¹⁵ Source: The European Association of Service providers for Persons with Disabilities (EASPD) - <https://edsa.eu/members/>

¹⁶ Source: EU for Trisomy 21 - <https://eufortrisomy21.eu/about/>

The unmet need for disability employment suggests some market potential. The growing focus on bespoke training and skills-based approaches for disabled people also supports this view.

Potential inclusion of organisations that facilitate employment for disabled people is also a possibility for the secondary target audience. Examples include (World Economic Forum, 2023a):

- **Mainstream companies;**
- **Work Integration Social Enterprises (WISEs) and sheltered workshops;**
- **Vocational Education and Training (VET) providers;**
- **Public Employment Services (PES).**

Competitive Landscape

A Porter's Five Forces analysis for the content production for immersive experience training for adults with Down syndrome reveals the following:

Threat of new entrants: In the specific niche of immersive training for individuals with Down's syndrome, new entrants would require expertise in immersive content creation and pedagogical approaches for intellectual disabilities, as well as an understanding of the specific needs and learning styles of individuals with Down's syndrome.

Bargaining power of buyers: The bargaining power of buyers (e.g. NGOs, employers, training providers, and government agencies) should be considered as these buyers seek effective, tailored training solutions to address specific skill gaps and integration challenges. Buyers are sensitive to price, driving demand for cost-effective solutions. Given this niche's nascent stage, buyers may have considerable influence in shaping product offerings and pricing.

Bargaining power of suppliers: Suppliers (e.g. software developers and skilled content creators) may hold significant power due to niche expertise and limited competition.

Threat of substitute products or services: Established, non-digital assistive tools and traditional educational materials remain viable substitutes. Existing alternatives include traditional vocational rehabilitation approaches, “train first, place later” models, direct on-the-job training, and sheltered workshops.

Rivalry among existing Competitors: The authors found no specific information on rivalry among existing competitors for content for immersive experiences for people with Down's syndrome.

Market Opportunities and Risks

Market Opportunities:

- **Needs in Disability Employment:** There is a need for effective strategies to help people with intellectual disabilities find employment, given their high unemployment rates and the difficulties they encounter in gaining real-world experience. Immersive training provides a novel, safe and repeatable environment in which to acquire skills.
- **Skills-First Approach:** The growing global adoption of a “skills-first” approach allows a focus on an individual's actual competencies rather than just their qualifications. This can significantly broaden the talent pool for individuals with non-traditional educational backgrounds, including those with Down's syndrome.
- **Eco-friendly and cost-efficient training:** Immersive training can reduce costs associated with physical resources, travel, and potential workplace incidents, making it an attractive long-term investment for employers and training providers.

Market Risks:

- **Resistance to change:** Organisational culture and a reluctance to adopt modern technologies or inclusive practices can pose significant challenges for employers.
- **Lack of awareness and stigmatisation:** Despite policy efforts, stigmatisation, and a lack of knowledge about integrating disabled employees persist, hindering employment opportunities

7.3. REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS ASSESSMENT WITHIN THE RIGA PILOT

The context of Riga

The city of Riga has 632,614 inhabitants, with a predominance of women (351,056 compared to 281,558 men) (Giacomo Arrighini (ISIM) et al., 2022). This population has a total of 291 000 households. On average, households consist of two people. According to Eurostat (Eurostat, 2022) for the year 2020, 44% of households are composed of only one member. The proportion of households with a lone pensioner is 17%, while the proportion of households with a lone parent is 15%. Children aged 0-17 are present in 25% of households in Riga.

Riga's Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS)

The underlying principle of the Riga pilot project is to mobilize undervalued resources, such as food, in addition to cultural and social activities, to promote inclusive health and well-being (IHR) within the community. The model emphasizes the co-design, co-deployment, and co-management of solutions with local stakeholders, aiming at the participation and adaptability of the solutions, in order to make the market an accessible, creative, and inclusive public space that extends beyond the mere supply of food to serve as a recreational and educational centre.

Replicable business models

Of all the innovations created during Riga's pilot implementation at the Āgenskalns Market, the partners identified three as having potential for replication¹⁷. These are presented below:

Co-creation kitchen

This "hard" solution can be described as an indoor open kitchen that acts as a social laboratory within the market. It offers facilities for holding community cooking events, food donation and sharing experiences. Its differentiation lies in its multipurpose nature, serving for private events, free community events and educational activities. The kitchen seeks to promote food entrepreneurship, nutrition education and intercultural exchange, particularly benefiting disadvantaged groups.

Cultural, social, and educational events Programme

These "soft" solutions are comprised of various interactive events on healthy nutrition, urban gardening courses, behavioural games and inclusive cultural presentations that transform the marketplace into an open platform for community initiatives, social interaction, and cultural expression. They promote healthy diets, sustainable mobility, reduce food waste and improve psychological and relational well-being, contributing to social cohesion and address the limited cultural and social opportunities of the neighbouring community.

Accessibility ramp and Lift

These "hard" solutions involve interventions in the catering area of the outdoor market area to make it more accessible and the installation of a lift to the first floor (where the communal kitchen is located). The ramp and lift provide universal access to diverse users, including the elderly, people with disabilities, families with strollers and delivery workers, thus increasing inclusion and equity in public space.

Eco-islands

Although they are not specifically identified as VIS, these physical concepts, and implementations” with “A place in the outdoor area dedicated to promoting sustainable practices, particularly with regard to waste management and consumption, in urban environments.

¹⁷ **Replicable business models** are developed by systematically analysing successful cases and identifying the good practices, people, types of customers, processes, practices, operational requirements, and critical factors for replication involved.

Āgenskalns Market Photo

Figure 14 – The Āgenskalns Market (outdoor)

Source: <https://www.facebook.com/InHabitRiga>

To evaluate the Societal Readiness Level (SRL) and Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) of the KER and VIS with replication potential, the project partners completed a self-assessment questionnaire. The results are presented in the images below.

Figure 15 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire for the Co-creation Kitchen SLR and TRL levels

Figure 16 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire for Programme of cultural, social, and educational events SLR and TRL level

Of the innovations created at the Āgenskalns Food Market, the “Programme of cultural, social and educational events” and the “Co-creation kitchen” are in the SRL 7 stage and have potential for replication. The “Co-creation kitchen” has a TLR level of 5 and the "Programme of cultural, social and educational events" does not make use of technology. The "Accessibility ramp and lift" and the "Eco-islands” support the market’s viability by increasing accessibility, which benefits suppliers and cultural initiatives within the market ecosystem.

These solutions, implemented together as part of a broader innovation (the Market) reveal a replicable business model that contributes to the well-being of market users, enhancing inclusion, promoting equity in public infrastructures, and making spaces accessible to all segments of the population.

The replicable business model of the innovations implemented in the Āgenskalns market is presented below, according to the dimensions of the Social Business Model Canvas,

7.4. THE ĀGENSKALNS FOOD MARKET

REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODEL DIMENSIONS

Disclaimer: This is a business model based on the IN-HABIT project. If you would like to use it as inspiration for your own project, you should develop a specific business plan tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

The Āgenskalns food market is a multifunctional urban marketplace with an attractive value proposition, improving inclusive health and well-being (IHW) for your community, revitalizing urban spaces, making them more accessible, safer, and attractive to diverse populations. Key offerings include promoting healthy lifestyles through improved access to healthy food, encouraging sustainable mobility through infrastructure such as bicycle facilities and accessibility ramps, hosting **cultural, social, and educational events**, and community initiatives such as **Co-creation Cuisine**.

Problem

Urban neighbourhoods across Europe often face health and well-being challenges, including a lack of opportunities for cultural activities, physical recreation, and social interaction, particularly affecting more underserved demographic groups. In certain neighbourhoods, the perception of insecurity and the lack of offers can reduce the social desirability of the territory. Demographic changes or the influx of new residents can also introduce social integration challenges, potentially disrupting the social balance of the community. Additionally, aspiring entrepreneurs, especially those from marginalized communities, may encounter significant barriers such as high license costs and adequate operating space, lack of accessible resources for training or innovation, and social or cultural stigmas.

Value Proposition

Social value is generated by promoting intercultural and intergenerational interactions, building a sense of belonging, and reducing social isolation through a variety of cultural and social events. In addition, the model aims to boost economic inclusion by creating livelihoods and training opportunities for underserved groups, supporting local producers, and integrating waste reduction practices for environmental sustainability. Integrating physical infrastructure ("hard" solutions) with cultural, digital, and social programs ("soft" solutions) is key to achieving these multifaceted benefits.

Key competitive advantages:

- **Multifunctional and integrated approach:** Unlike traditional markets or single-purpose urban interventions, the Āgenskalns Market combines physical infrastructure ('hard' solutions) with cultural, social and educational Programmes ('soft' solutions). This integrated model creates multifaceted benefits, serving as a food market, cultural hub and educational centre.
- **Holistic health and well-being promotion:** The market actively promotes healthy lifestyles by improving access to nutritious food and by hosting events that encourage physical recreation and social interaction. It addresses broader health challenges by providing nutrition education and reducing food waste, going beyond mere food provision.
- **Enhanced accessibility and inclusivity:** Physical interventions such as the Accessibility Ramp & Lift ensure universal access for all users, including the elderly, people with disabilities, families with pushchairs and delivery workers. This increases inclusion and equity in public spaces. This contrasts with traditional markets that may lack such features.
- **Community Cohesion and Social Value Creation:** The market promotes intercultural and intergenerational interactions, builds a sense of belonging and reduces social isolation by offering a variety of cultural and social events and initiatives, such as the 'Co-creation Kitchen'. This co-design, co-deployment and co-management model with local stakeholders emphasises participation and adaptability.

Customer Segments (Beneficiaries/Users)

Beneficiaries

- **Community groups:** Local residents, neighbourhood associations, students, youth organisations, senior clubs, and community activators/representatives.
- **Underserved populations:** children, the elderly, women, people with disabilities, ethnic and religious minorities, and people living alone.
- **Market vendors and workers:** This group includes small-scale producers who, despite being food producers themselves, often face food insecurity, indicating a need for support and inclusion in decision-making processes. Training in basic food hygiene and safe food handling is crucial for this group.

Customers

- **Local authorities and market management:** They are responsible for implementing measures to ensure food safety and promote health, including setting up legal frameworks, conducting inspections, and leading health promotion initiatives within the markets. These stakeholders are responsible for implementing measures to ensure food safety and promote health.
- **Businesses:** The market seeks the engagement of businesses (both small and large) to drive innovation, address financing gaps and support the transition to more sustainable, nature-positive food systems.

- **Non-profit organisations**

Channels

Communication and dissemination actions can occur through a mixture of physical and digital channels. The market's physical space serves as the main channel for direct interaction, allowing for social gatherings, cultural events, and educational activities. In the digital channel, the marketplace can use the website and social media platforms (e.g. Instagram, YouTube, Twitter) for updates, news and promotion of events. Traditional communication materials such as posters, flyers, press releases and local public events, along with thematic workshops and workshops, can also be used to reach diverse audiences, especially those less accustomed to digital tools.

Customer Relations

In the direct relationship with beneficiaries, participatory and co-creative principles can be followed. Methods include co-design workshops, community surveys and focus groups to gather input on community needs and co-develop solutions. Local organisations should be directly involved. Ongoing monitoring and evaluation, involving community activators such as co-researchers and neighbourhood observers, facilitates continuous feedback and adaptation of initiatives.

Main Activities

The main activities cover the co-design, co-deployment, and co-management of solutions in urban space. These activities include:

- **Development and management of Infrastructures:** Renovation and transformation of the market and public spaces such as squares and external market, installation of accessibility features such as ramps and lifts, creation of waste management facilities (eco-islands) and creation of community kitchens.
- **Program Implementation:** Organisation of various cultural, social, and educational events, such as culinary workshops, therapeutic gardening, artistic performances, entrepreneurship initiatives, and youth festivals. Promotion of healthy eating habits, by encouraging sustainable consumption, implementing waste reduction strategies, and fostering social entrepreneurship.
- **Community building:** Mapping *stakeholders* and their needs, training community activators, and facilitating workshops with the community. Building trust and networks as well.
- **Economic Development:** Launch calls for proposals targeting social enterprises, provide business incubation Programmes and offer comprehensive training and mentoring to entrepreneurs.

Key Resources

The model relies on a diverse set of resources, including tangible assets, human expertise, and digital infrastructure.

- **Physical Infrastructures:** Market pavilions and renovated outdoor spaces, community gardens and greenhouses, accessibility ramps and lifts, eco-islands and community kitchens equipped for various

activities.

- **Human and social Capital:** Staff dedicated to the project (e.g. cultural coordinators and assistants), a network of trained activators and community representatives, volunteers, local artists, chefs, urban gardeners, and experts from academic institutions).
- **Digital Infrastructure:** An integrated project website and multiple social networks.
- **Know-how:** Proven methodologies for stakeholder engagement, co-design, mindset change, social entrepreneurship, and comprehensive IHW impact assessment frameworks.
- **Brand and Reputation:** The established public recognition and community-driven image of the central market, built over time, which attracts visitors and contributors alike.

Key partners

The model can thrive based on a robust framework of Public-Private-Personal Partnerships (PPPPs).

- **Lead project partners:** These usually include a research institution, a social enterprise or partner with expertise on the activity to be implemented and, a public authority.
- **Local stakeholders:** a wide range of community actors, such as local residents, neighbourhood associations, NGOs, small businesses, farmers, food consumers, local artists, sports associations, schools, universities, social services, and private companies.
- **Cross-cutting Project Partners:** Experts in specific areas, including gender and diversity, citizen engagement and social innovations, change management, impact assessment, communication, business incubation, and infrastructure experts.
- **Government and regional authorities:** Municipalities and regional institutions that support urban planning and development initiatives, environmental and public health initiatives, and entrepreneurship initiatives.
- **Businesses:** This includes market vendors, local food businesses, and other SMEs, as well as potential sponsors.
- **NGOs:** Organisations that work with social integration, food sovereignty, animal rights, and cultural initiatives.
- **Teaching and research institutions:** Universities working in this fields of knowledge.

Competition

There is competition between traditional markets and the formal retail sector (supermarkets), as well as between traditional markets and other informal vendors.

Cost Structure

The costs mainly involve investments in physical infrastructure and operating expenses. The most significant investments are allocated to the construction and renovation of spaces such as community kitchens, eco-islands, and online food purchasing system. Other operational costs cover staff (e.g. cultural

coordinators, assistants), materials for events, communication campaigns and fees for artists and facilitators. Maintenance expenses are also something to consider for long-term sustainability.

Revenue Streams

Potential revenue can be generated through a combination of business activities and external support, ensuring the financial sustainability of the social mission. Primary revenue can be generated through activities such as renting out spaces, charging for workshops or pop-up restaurants, and catering.

There is also the potential to generate revenue through corporate social responsibility (CSR) events or advertising. Additional sources of funding include grants, donations, and direct municipal support. Promoting new social enterprises linked to the market's focus areas, which are often supported by incubation and seed capital Programmes, can also generate additional revenue.

Surplus

Any surplus generated by the social business model can be reinvested in the community or used to improve services and infrastructure.

Social Impact Measurement

Impact assessment goes beyond traditional financial metrics to capture changes in inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW) across all dimensions, including economic, psychological, social, and relational.

Table 12 - Key Impact Indicators (KIIs)

Short-term output	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term Outcomes (impacts)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Event name. Event type (economic, social, cultural, environmental, or educational). Date. Content description. Number of Partners involved in the organisation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Changes in beneficiaries' attitudes towards sustainability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observed impact on Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW).

Macro-Environment (PESTEL Analysis)

Political factors: Global and regional policy frameworks exert a strong influence. The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provide an overarching framework for transforming food systems. The Paris Agreement on climate change set critical environmental targets for governments and businesses. Specifically, Target 16 (promoting sustainable consumption choices) have a direct impact on business operations (World Economic Forum, 2023b). National governments are developing “country-led

transformation pathways” for food systems (World Economic Forum, 2022d) and are committing proportions of their GDP to innovation.

Economic Factors: The market is navigating a challenging economic environment, exacerbated by the cost-of-living crisis, identified as the most severe global risk in the short term (World Economic Forum, 2024). Despite these challenges, significant economic opportunities are emerging from the push for sustainability: Innovation in food systems (World Economic Forum, 2018b).

Social factors: Urbanisation is a dominant social megatrend, with the majority of the global population projected to be living in cities by 2050. Trends towards urbanisation continue, with Europe experiencing high levels of population concentration in urban areas. Alongside this, there is a growing "erosion of social cohesion"(World Economic Forum, 2024), alongside increasing consumer concern for nature-positive products and sustainability. This demographic shift is driving changes in agrifood systems and consumer behaviour (FAO, 2023). A key trend is the dietary transition towards processed foods and eating out, leading to concerns about rising obesity among children and the growing burden of non-communicable diseases (NCDs). Although industrialisation has led to a more globalised food system, there has also been a notable rise in social movements such as “Slow Food” and local food initiatives that promote traditional and seasonal produce (WHO, 2021). Food tourism is an upward trend in the European Region, offering traditional markets opportunities to promote local culture and cuisine.

Technological factors: Rapid technological advancements are reshaping food systems. Digital innovations are transforming all segments, offering opportunities for increased efficiency and transparency. Connectivity technologies such as social networks and e-commerce platforms can influence consumption patterns and increase access to nutritious foods. Innovations in cold chains, food packaging and precision agriculture are enhancing quality, safety, shelf life, and resource efficiency.

Legal Factors: Regulatory frameworks are evolving to address food safety, nutrition, and environmental impacts. Food laws and regulations, often based on international standards are crucial for ensuring food safety from "farm to table". Compliance with these regulations is crucial, though small-scale producers may face challenges in meeting them. Furthermore, there is an increasing push for anti-food waste regulations and food safety legislation.

Environmental factors: The environmental impact of food systems is a critical concern. Food systems contribute significantly to global greenhouse gas emissions, drive biodiversity loss and contribute to soil degradation, desertification, and water scarcity (World Economic Forum, 2018b). A circular economy is key to addressing these challenges, as it aims to decouple economic growth from material extraction and minimise waste.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Critical success factors (CSFs) are the essential conditions that must be met for a business model to be successfully implemented in a new context. Addressing these factors during the design process is crucial for creating robust, transferable, sustainable business models that can be implemented across regions and sectors. Please find below a suggestion for the critical success factors and barriers to implementation. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to function as a starting point for further discussion.

Critical success factors

- Accessibility ramp and elevator: Success depends on securing adequate funding for investment and maintenance, adhering to local building codes and heritage protection laws, and achieving strong alignment among stakeholders.
- Cultural, social, and educational events Programme: This requires strong community engagement and local partnerships, culturally relevant content, an effective communication strategy and a skilled event planning team.
- Co-creation kitchen: Key success factors include securing adequate funding for investment and maintenance, inclusive and participatory design, access to adequate physical space, strong community outreach, and collaborative partnerships with local culinary experts, NGOs, or training centres.
- Regulatory compliance: Adherence to local building codes, heritage protection laws and health and safety regulations.
- Contextual adaptation: The methodologies and content should be adapted to the specific cultural and social context of the new location.
- Availability of resources: Access to adequate physical spaces and necessary equipment is essential.

Barriers to Implementation

- Ramp and elevator accessibility: Potential barriers include space constraints, particularly with regard to ramps, and the costs of installation and maintenance. Other issues include the need for structural modifications to older buildings and the reliance on energy for lifts.
- Programme of cultural, social, and educational events: Obstacles could include limited funding, insufficient community involvement, and restricted access to venues and local support.
- Co-creation kitchen: Barriers include compliance with health and safety regulations (particularly for food handling), securing initial and ongoing funding, the need for ongoing facilitation and coordination, and taking cultural and dietary considerations into account.

Replication prerequisites

- Other requisites: The successful replication of this hybrid model relies on a specialised human capital structure capable of managing between profit and purpose. The leadership team must be supported by community connectors, dedicated staff responsible for curating cultural content and maintaining deep engagement with neighbourhood associations. This guarantees that the market remains a local hub rather than becoming a tourist-only destination. Furthermore, the model requires the selection of pro-sustainability vendors, ensuring that traders are active partners willing to adopt strict waste reduction practices and participate in food donation schemes.
- Processes: Operationally, the model is underpinned by a flexible lease model, which grants operators significant autonomy and long-term tenure in exchange for upfront capital investment and the delivery of specific social outcomes. Financial sustainability is achieved through a cross-subsidisation mechanism, whereby revenue generated from high-traffic commercial stalls is redirected to subsidise unprofitable community areas such as co-creation kitchens and educational spaces. This ecosystem is reinforced by rigorous waste minimisation protocols, specifically the utilisation of the “Eco-Island” system, which integrates circular economy principles directly into the market's daily operations.

- Other requisites: From a physical perspective, the venue requires multifunctional zoning, a design strategy that deliberately mixes sales areas with zones reserved for co-creation, events, and education, in order to foster social interaction. To ensure the market serves disadvantaged demographics as intended, accessibility upgrades are essential. This involves installing lifts and ramps to make the venue accessible for the elderly and people with disabilities, transforming historic or industrial buildings into fully inclusive public spaces.

Strategy monitoring

Suggestion of a strategy monitoring model

Please find below a suggestion for a strategy monitoring model. This is a *non-exhaustive* list and is intended to be a starting point for further discussion.

Table 13 - Strategy monitoring indicators (Key Performance Indicators)

<p>1) People dimension (Customer Perspective or Stakeholder Engagement)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure high satisfaction and a positive perception among target users and stakeholders in new areas. • Achieve deep and inclusive engagement with local communities. • Promote local ownership and active participation in executing the replicated solution. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of stakeholders involved in implementation efforts, disaggregated by specific characteristics (e.g. gender, age, disability, and ethnicity). • User satisfaction ratings and feedback (e.g., from surveys, focus groups and testimonials) from new locations. • Adoption rate or participation levels in activities/services. • Perceived improvements in social inclusion, cohesion, and intergroup relations. • Number of local community activators involved. 	<p>2) Processes dimension (Internal Processes & Service Provision)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement and standardise key processes. • Ensure the quality of the implemented services. • Establish robust monitoring and evaluation systems to ensure consistent data collection. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency of internal processes. • Fees for the use of solutions, infrastructure, or services. • Number of integrated innovations (technological, digital, nature-based, cultural, and social). • Quality and integrity of the data from implemented monitoring systems.
<p>3) Growth and Learning dimension</p>	<p>4) Financial dimension</p>

<p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop the organisational capacity and the team's experience. • Foster innovation and the continuous improvement of the business model based on experience. • Develop local skills and promote social entrepreneurship in new areas. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of training sessions/workshops held for skills development (e.g. entrepreneurship, digital literacy, and community activation). • Improvements in participants' skills and mindset (e.g., self-confidence, resilience, and strategic thinking). • Number of new (social) enterprises incubated or supported. 	<p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generating revenue in a sustainable way. • Maximising cost efficiency. • Ensure positive return on investment (ROI). • Secure adequate funding for expansion and new implementations. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revenue generated by area of activity or initiative. • Profitability (net profit margin) or ROI of investments. • Amount of external funding/grants guaranteed.
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MARKET ANALYSIS

Disclaimer: This is a market analysis developed for an IN-HABIT project. Some of the information may be outdated or inaccurate. If you wish to implement this idea, you should conduct specific market research tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Market overview

An urban food market in Europe operates within broader agrifood systems that encompass all the actors and interlinked activities involved in producing, aggregating, processing, distributing, consuming, and disposing of food products derived from agriculture, forestry, or fisheries. The market is embedded within a complex system that is subject to rapid transformation due to factors such as population growth, urbanisation, changing consumption patterns, climate change, and depletion of natural resources.

This market analysis focuses on food markets in Europe, particularly traditional ones. Traditional urban food markets are crucial, particularly within the European Region, as they provide food for millions of people. They play a vital role in providing access to safe, nutritious, and culturally appropriate food, thereby promoting health, and preventing disease.

Products typically available include raw and minimally processed foods such as fresh fruit and vegetables, wholegrains, pulses, nuts, meat, poultry, fish, eggs, and dairy products. Homemade foods are also common, though their nutritional composition can sometimes be a cause for concern. A key characteristic is the emphasis on local and traditional products, respecting seasonality, and territorial variety, which

aligns with calls for sustainable food systems. However, they also offer ready-to-eat foods that are either industrially processed or homemade.

Traditional food markets can be segmented into two key dimensions, which can vary in their organisational dynamics: some are permanent structures, such as bazaars, with fixed, designated locations; others are temporary setups, such as informal markets or farmers' markets, which can be established on an ad hoc basis (WHO, 2021). This report will focus on markets with permanent structures.

Market Size and Growth

Urbanisation rates in Europe are high, with around 74% of people living in cities, a figure which is increasing in Eastern Europe and Central Asia ((WHO, 2021). Cities are significant economic engines globally, generating around 85% of global GDP and consuming substantial resources (World Economic Forum, 2022d). It is projected that nearly 60% of the world's population will reside in urban areas by 2030, which will significantly alter consumer demand and put increased pressure on resources (World Economic Forum, 2022d).

A global infrastructure investment gap of \$15 trillion is expected by 2040, some of which will need to be met at a local level (World Economic Forum, 2022c). This implies a need for robust urban development, including food-related infrastructure.

Target Audience

The target audience for the European food market is multifaceted and encompasses a wide range of stakeholders. Millions of urban residents across the European Region rely on these markets for their food (WHO, 2021). There is growing consumer awareness of, and concern about, purchasing habits and the environmental impact of products. They are demanding greater transparency regarding a product's impact on biodiversity and want to know about the sustainability credentials of what they buy (World Economic Forum, 2023b). Some consumers are actively seeking nutrient-dense and safe foods and are engaging with movements that promote local and traditional products, such as the "Slow Food" movement (WHO, 2021). However, consumers are often unaware of the health benefits of eating fresh produce. At the same time, there is a growing appreciation of traditional food cultures and food tourism is emerging (WHO, 2021).

Competitive Landscape

The following Porter's Five Forces analysis illustrates the industry's competitiveness:

Threat of New Entrants: Entering the food market, particularly within traditional structures, presents several challenges. These include poor infrastructure and high regulatory burdens, which are significant cost-raising factors (World Economic Forum, 2018b). Furthermore, the transition to circular economy models, which are gaining traction, requires upfront investments, making it challenging to implement new solutions (World Economic Forum, 2018a).

Bargaining Power of Buyers (Consumers): Consumers wield considerable power in the European food market. Their purchasing decisions are highly sensitive to food prices, which are an "important determinant of food acquisition" (WHO, 2021). There is a pronounced and increasing "consumer interest in nature

positive" products and a demand for transparency regarding a product's environmental impact (World Economic Forum, 2022d). Consumers are actively demanding that their food meets specific sustainability and health requirements (World Economic Forum, 2018b).

Bargaining Power of Suppliers (Producers/Farmers): Small-scale producers supplying traditional markets often have limited power. The expansion of supermarkets can restrict small producers' access to sales channels (FAO, 2023). Food production, particularly of perishable goods such as fruit and vegetables, tends to be located near urban markets in order to reduce costs.

Threat of Substitute Products or Services: The European food market is influenced by a global trend towards more industrialised food systems and a growing demand for e-commerce services, which can offer alternatives to traditional markets (WHO, 2021). Despite this, there is a countermovement with the rise of "Slow Food" and local food initiatives, indicating a preference for traditional and local sourcing among some consumer segments (WHO, 2021).

Rivalry among existing competitors: There is competition between traditional markets and the formal retail sector (supermarkets), as well as between traditional markets and other informal vendors (FAO, 2023). The push for sustainability and health outcomes drives competition among existing players to offer more appealing and compliant products.

Barriers to Entry

There are several significant barriers to entering or effectively competing in the European food market, particularly in the traditional food market segment.

Cost modelling and capital requirements: Although establishing and maintaining a compliant traditional food market is possibly less capital-intensive than large supermarkets, it requires significant investment in basic infrastructure.

Regulatory mapping and EU compliance: Operating within the European Region, businesses in traditional food markets must navigate a complex landscape of "comprehensive contemporary food laws and regulations" (WHO, 2021). Authorities also require continuous adherence to risk-based inspection and enforcement services (WHO, 2021).

Market Opportunities and Risks

Market opportunities

- Growing demand for nutritious and sustainable foods: The increased demand for nutrient-rich foods presents an opportunity for traditional markets to expand their offerings to include organic produce such as fruit, vegetables, whole grains, meat, and fish. This also aligns with consumers' growing demand for products that meet sustainability and health requirements.
- Leveraging urbanisation and rural–urban linkages: Urbanisation creates opportunities to strengthen links between urban, peri-urban, and rural areas, leading to more efficient value chains and reduced costs for nutritious foods. Adopting a "rural–urban continuum lens" is essential for developing effective policies, technologies, and investments.

Market Risks

- Intense Competition: Traditional markets face significant competition from expanding supermarkets. The proliferation of meal delivery apps further intensifies this rivalry.
- Climate Change Impacts: Climate change directly affects food systems and agricultural production, potentially leading to supply disruptions and increased costs.

Recommendations

- Encourage healthier food environments by implementing nutrition education campaigns.
- Invest in infrastructure (e.g. cold storage and improved transport networks) to reduce costs and enhance the efficiency of midstream activities (logistics, processing, and wholesale).
- Support small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) by enhancing their capacity, improving their access to finance and technology, and introducing policies that enable their expansion.
- Support urban and peri-urban agriculture (UPA) by focusing on fresh, perishable foods and integrating UPA producers into territorial planning.
- Initiate and support local-level circular economy initiatives focusing on the prevention, recovery and redistribution of food surpluses, and the conversion of food waste into valuable resources such as compost or biogas.

8. REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS ASSESSMENT WITHIN THE LUCCA PILOT

The context of Lucca

Lucca is a small city in Tuscany, central Italy, with a population of around 88,000–89,000. Lucca is renowned for its intact Renaissance walls, which encircle the entire old town. These walls are surrounded by extensive green spaces that form an urban park. The city is also close to the Serchio River Park and the Nottolini Aqueduct, both of which are popular recreational areas. Lucca's urban layout, with areas scattered throughout the countryside, provides good access to open spaces and fosters interaction with the environment, which has a positive impact on residents' well-being. The city centre is largely car-free, making it safe for pets and pedestrians, and it has many drinking fountains. Lucca is considered a pet-friendly city (Francesco Di Iacovo (UNIFI) et al., 2022). The city has had Man-Animal Cohabitation Regulations in place since 2000 and has operated a City Council Animal Affairs Observatory since 2013.

Lucca's Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS)

The IN-HABIT project in Lucca, aimed to promote inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW) by transforming the city into Europe's first “human-animal smart city”. This visionary approach makes use of the often-overlooked resource of human-animal bonds and interactions, treating animals as nature-based solutions (NBS) to enhance various aspects of urban life and address emerging challenges (European Commission, 2019)

Replicable business models

The primary goal was to promote inclusive mental, social, and relational wellbeing among Lucca's inhabitants. This involves improving the quality of urban life for all residents and tourists by creating innovative habits and ensuring that public green spaces are safer, more accessible, and more inclusive for humans and animals.

Of all the VIS created during Lucca's pilot implementation, the partners identified three innovations as having potential for replication¹⁸: IN-HABIT- LUCCA Start-up for a Humanimal urban policy design centre (HADUP Centre), Animal Assisted Interventions for elderly in nursing homes and Pet care services.

Pet care services Photos

Figure 17 – Pet care services

Figure 18 – Pet care services

Source: Lucca Project partners

To evaluate the Societal Readiness Level (SRL) and Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) of the KER and VIS with replication potential, the project partners completed a self-assessment questionnaire. The results are presented in the images below.

¹⁸ **Replicable business models** are developed by systematically analysing successful cases and identifying the good practices, people, types of customers, processes, practices, operational requirements, and critical factors for replication involved.

Figure 19 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire for the HADUP Centre SLR and TRL levels

Figure 20 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire Animal Assisted Interventions for elderly in nursing homes SLR and TRL levels

Figure 21 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire for Pet care services SLR and TRL levels

The three innovations mentioned; the HADUP centre; animal-assisted interventions for the elderly in nursing homes; and pet care services are at SRL 7. This means that they have been refined and retested with relevant societal stakeholders. A key characteristic of all the listed initiatives is that they have a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of zero. This indicates that they focus on social, cultural, and nature-based solutions rather than developing new technological innovations, as measured by their Societal Readiness Level (SRL).

These consistently high SRLs underscore the project's success in implementing and integrating human-animal bond solutions into the urban fabric through a participatory “co-co-co” approach.

8.1. HUMANIMAL URBAN POLICY DESIGN CENTRE (HADUP CENTRE)

REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODEL DIMENSIONS

Disclaimer: This is a business model based on the IN-HABIT project. If you would like to use it as inspiration for your own project, you should develop a specific business plan tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Humanimal urban policy design centre (HADUP centre)

The HADUP Centre is pioneering a groundbreaking innovation in urban governance by transforming challenges in economic growth and social inclusion into opportunities through the promotion of human-animal bonds for inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW). Unlike traditional, fragmented policies, it introduces bespoke, evidence-based frameworks that integrate animal companionship into urban planning. This novel approach provides customised strategies, specialised training and agile pilot projects, thereby empowering local authorities and benefiting disadvantaged groups such as the elderly by reducing isolation and enhancing mental health. Through participatory research, workshops and advocacy, the Centre fosters thought leadership and redefines inclusive urban spaces, driving equitable and innovative community transformations.

Problem

Small and medium-sized cities (SMSCs) in Europe face challenges in fostering **economic growth and social inclusion**, particularly for underserved groups. Local authorities often lack **specialized expertise** and **integrated policy frameworks** to leverage human-animal bonds for Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW), resulting in fragmented efforts, siloed operations, and regulatory barriers that hinder inclusive urban environments.

Value Proposition

The HADUP Centre offers **niche consulting services** to design and implement **integrated human-animal urban policies**, delivering:

- **Bespoke policy frameworks** and strategies tailored to local contexts.
- **Specialized training** to enhance local capacity.
- **Thought leadership** in using human-animal bonds to boost IHW, creating innovative, inclusive urban spaces.

This innovative service provides a **human-centred, evidence-based urban planning paradigm**, establishing the Centre as a trusted expert in a specialized market.

Key competitive advantages for the HADUP Centre:

- 1. Specialisation in Human-Animal Urban Policy:** The HADUP Centre is a groundbreaking innovation, focusing uniquely on integrating human-animal bonds into urban planning and policy frameworks. Unlike traditional urban planning consultancies or general environmental consulting firms, the Centre's USP is its integrated approach to human-animal interactions as Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). This addresses a niche in the market that is often overlooked by traditional policy frameworks, which frequently fail to consider non-human animals in urban planning.
- 2. Evidence-Based, Human-Centred, and Bespoke Solutions:** The Centre provides bespoke, evidence-based policy frameworks and strategies that are tailored to local contexts. Its human-centred approach emphasises participatory research, workshops, and advocacy. This methodology ensures that solutions are effective and responsive to the specific needs of diverse populations, including disadvantaged groups such as the elderly, by reducing isolation and enhancing mental health. The expertise provided is grounded in the academic rigour of partner universities.
- 3. Holistic Inclusive Health and Well-being (IHW) Focus:** The HADUP Centre's holistic inclusive health and well-being (IHW) focus goes beyond urban planning. It promotes integrated mental, social and relational wellbeing by creating safer, more accessible and more inclusive public green spaces for humans and animals alike. This contributes to broader societal benefits, such as increased social cohesion, reduced marginalisation and the creation of sustainable, resilient and participatory urban ecosystems.
- 4. Thought Leadership and Capacity Building:** The Centre develops policies and provides specialised training to enhance local capacity, establishing itself as a thought leader in using human-animal bonds to promote IHW. Through its expertise and by influencing urban policies and planning, it redefines inclusive urban spaces and drives equitable and innovative community transformations. The Centre can serve as a vital 'knowledge centre' for this emerging field, offering consultancy, training, and research services.

Customer Segments (Beneficiaries/Users)

- **Primary Clients: Public authorities** (urban planning, public health, environmental departments, and mayoral offices) seeking expert policy solutions.
- **Indirect Beneficiaries: Citizens**, particularly disadvantaged groups (children, elderly, women, people with disabilities, ethnic minorities), who benefit from enhanced urban wellbeing, reduced isolation, and improved mental and social health.

Channels

- **Thought Leadership:** Showcasing pilot success via white papers, webinars, and urban development conferences.
- **Strategic Networks:** Leveraging referrals from universities, municipalities, and urban planning associations.

- **Targeted Tenders:** Pursuing high-fit urban development opportunities to demonstrate expertise.

Customer Relations

- **Public Authorities:** Built through **service contracts and Memorandum of Understanding (MoUs)**, with the consultancy organisation ensuring personalized, collaborative co-design via **workshops and meetings**. High-quality deliverables (reports, guides, training) and advisory retainers foster trust.
- **Citizens:** Engaged via **consultations**, online feedback platforms, and transparent reporting to inform policy and ensure community support.

Main Activities

- Conducting **specialized research** on human-animal bonds and IHW using Participatory Action Research (PAR).
- Facilitating **policy co-design** through stakeholder workshops.
- Delivering **targeted training** for officials to implement policies.
- Managing **lean pilot projects** with agile coordination.
- Establishing **thought leadership** through publications and advocacy.

Key Resources

- **Expert Team:** A small team of specialists (urban planners, policy analysts, animal welfare, and public health experts).
- **Proprietary Knowledge:** Research, frameworks, and tools for human-animal policy.
- **Partnerships:** Credibility from Universities, Municipalities, and urban networks.
- **Lean Infrastructure:** Virtual office, cloud-based CRM, and data tools.
- **Branding:** Website, policy briefs, and thought leadership content.

Key Partners

- **Universities:** Provides academic rigour and expertise. Role: Knowledge partner.
- **Municipalities:** Pilot city and reference case. Role: Pilot client and advocate.
- **Client Cities/Municipalities:** Provide data and implement policies. Role: Core clients and co-developers.
- **Urban Planning Associations:** Facilitate outreach. Role: Network partners.
- **Local NGOs/Community Groups:** Provide insights and support implementation. Role: Co-producers of the solutions and Local collaborators.
- **Other Funders.** Other organisations who provide financial support. Role: funders

Competition

Main competitors could be traditional consulting companies and specialist urban planning services based at universities.

Cost Structure

- **Personnel:** Salaries for expert consultants.
- **Operations:** Office space or virtual infrastructure, software, travel, marketing.
- **Research:** Targeted studies to maintain expertise.
- **Networking:** Conferences and thought leadership content.

Revenue Streams

Potential revenue sources include the following:

- **Consulting fees** for policy design and implementation.
- **Training fees** for capacity building.
- **Research fees** for impact assessments.
- **Grants** from EU bodies for pilots.
- **Future subscriptions** for a “humanimal-friendly cities” knowledge hub.

Surplus

Surpluses can be **reinvested** to:

- Develop methodologies.
- Expand thought leadership.
- Build a **reserve fund** for resilience.

Social Impact Measurement

Theory of Change: By enabling cities to adopt integrated human-animal policies, the HADUP Centre fosters inclusive, health-promoting urban spaces, enhancing mental health, social cohesion, and sustainability for resilient smart cities.

Table 14 - Key Impact Indicators (KIIs)

Short-term output	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term Outcomes (impacts)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy frameworks delivered. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy adoption by cities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced IHW for citizens and fragile groups, societal

Short-term output	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term Outcomes (impacts)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training sessions conducted. • Stakeholder workshops held. • Cities engaged in co-design. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased budgets for human-animal initiatives. • Positive official feedback. • Improved citizen satisfaction. • Better animal welfare. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dialogue neighbourly, active life, and gaming life • Human-animal smart cities established. • Reduced marginalization. • Sustainable, resilient, proactive, and participatory urban ecosystems.

Measurement: Mixed-method assessments (surveys, case studies) with ex-ante, interim, and ex-post evaluations.

Market trends and external factors (PESTLE analysis)

Political: The political landscape strongly favours nature-based and circular solutions, driven by high-level European Union policy frameworks. Initiatives such as the EU Green Deal, the New European Bauhaus (NEB) and smart city policies are providing significant impetus for sustainable development and green growth, with the aim of increasing demand for circular solutions, supporting local economies and fostering innovation. At the national level, many European countries are developing National Urban Policies (NUPs) as strategic frameworks for managing urbanisation. However, challenges in implementing these NUPs, particularly with regard to capacity, create a sustained need for expert support.

Economic: The circular economy model aims to generate cost savings and reduce dependence on raw materials, thereby contributing to economic resilience.

Social: Cities currently face significant social challenges, including growing populations, increasing diversity, and persistent inequalities. In response, policy initiatives are increasingly focused on addressing the needs of disadvantaged groups, such as the elderly, homeless people, and people with disabilities. There is also growing societal recognition of the importance of the human–animal bond for well-being and quality of life in urban environments.

Technological: The concept of “smart cities” is evolving to encompass human and animal aspects. The global smart city market is experiencing significant growth (OECD Urban Studies, 2025).

Legal: Complying with GDPR urban planning laws, animal welfare, and fragile rights. There is a vast and evolving body of EU regulations, directives and strategies relating to environmental protection, biodiversity, and the circular economy. Navigating and complying with this complex landscape requires expertise (OECD Urban Studies, 2025).

Environmental: Climate change is a major driver of the adoption of the circular economy, with nature-based solutions offering key strategies for climate change mitigation and adaptation. Meanwhile, biodiversity protection is a high priority within EU strategies, which set clear targets for maintaining and

restoring ecosystems and their services. The principles of the circular economy and NBS directly contribute to achieving these biodiversity goals.

Critical Success Factors and Barriers to Implementation

Please find below a suggestion for the critical success factors and barriers to implementation. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to function as a starting point for further discussion.

Critical Success Factors:

- **Client intimacy** through tailored services.
- **Niche expertise** in human-animal policy.
- **Lean operations** for efficiency.
- **Strong partnerships** with academic and municipal leaders.
- **Evidence-based impact** for credibility.
- **Scalable frameworks** for diverse cities.

Barriers to Implementation:

- **Limited client budgets** for innovative policies.
- **Regulatory complexity** in urban planning.

Replication prerequisites

- **People:** The successful replication of this policy model relies on specialised human capital capable of navigating the complex intersection of urban planning and ethology. Central to this structure is the Pet Policy Manager, a strategic professional responsible for leading the integrated strategy and bridging the gap between technical animal management and public administration. To ensure systemic integration, this leadership must be supported by a cross-departmental board comprising councillors from social services, environment, and urban planning to dismantle administrative silos. Scientific advisors from veterinary or ethological fields must also be included to ensure that all policies are grounded in rigorous evidence rather than anecdotal assumption.
- **Processes:** Operationally, the model requires robust governance mechanisms to manage the social dynamics of human–animal coexistence. Cities must establish a Participatory Council: a formal assembly in which stakeholders, including veterinarians, pet owners, and non-owners, jointly design rules to prevent conflict and foster shared responsibility. Furthermore, successful adoption demands regulatory alignment, which involves systematically updating local bylaws to transition from restrictive measures to inclusive policies. This specifically enables animal access to public offices, nursing homes, and public transport networks, fully integrating pets into the urban fabric.
- **Other requisites:** From an infrastructural and technical perspective, the model necessitates a paradigm shift in how urban space is valued. Facilities such as the “Animal Lines” must be recognised as Animal-Nature Based Solutions (A-NBS), essential social infrastructure that fosters community health and social cohesion rather than merely functional waste areas. Underpinning this physical

deployment is the requirement for data mapping via GIS technology. Mapping pet density and specific community needs is critical to ensuring that infrastructure planning is demand-driven and spatially equitable, thereby avoiding the misallocation of public resources.

Strategy Monitoring

Please find below a suggestion for a strategy monitoring model. This is a *non-exhaustive* list and is intended to be a starting point for further discussion.

Table 15 - Strategy monitoring indicators (Key Performance Indicators)

<p>1) People Dimension (Customer Perspective or Stakeholder Engagement)</p> <p>Strategic Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance mental Health and Wellbeing of citizens, particularly disadvantaged groups, through human-animal urban policies. • Foster social cohesion and inclusion in client cities by leveraging human-animal bonds. • Promote community engagement and ownership of inclusive urban spaces. <p>Strategy Tracking Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen satisfaction ratings with human-animal integrated urban spaces (e.g., via surveys). • Reported improvements in mood, reduced anxiety, or enhanced social connections among residents (based on community feedback or observational data). • Increased participation in public spaces designed for human-animal interaction and societal dialogue, as well as active play. • Qualitative feedback from citizens and local stakeholders on perceived inclusivity and wellbeing benefits. As well as results from focus groups, storytelling, and surveys. 	<p>2) Processes Dimension (Internal Processes & Service Provision)</p> <p>Strategic Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliver consistent, high-quality policy design and implementation services to client cities. • Ensure effective collaboration with partners to develop evidence-based frameworks. • Maintain thought leadership, engagement, and participatory governance systems by synthesizing the best practices for human-animal urban coexistence. • Uphold ethical standards in policy recommendations, prioritizing human, and animal welfare. <p>Strategy Tracking Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of human-animal integrated policy frameworks delivered to client cities. • Number of city officials trained in implementing human-animal policies. • Number of stakeholder workshops or co-design sessions conducted. • Compliance with EU urban planning and animal welfare guidelines in policy recommendations. • Feedback from client cities on the quality and applicability of policy deliverables. • Number of thought leadership publications (e.g., white papers, reports) on human-animal urban policy.
<p>3) People Dimension (Customer Perspective or Stakeholder Engagement)</p>	<p>4) Financial Dimension</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p>

<p>Strategic Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieve high satisfaction among public authorities and stakeholders in client cities. • Promote citizen engagement and participation. • Ensure deep, inclusive engagement with diverse community groups to co-design policies, with the aim of encouraging citizens to play a more active role. • Encourage local ownership and active participation in policy implementation. <p>Strategy Tracking Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of stakeholders engaged in policy co-design. • Satisfaction ratings from public authorities (e.g., via surveys or interviews). • Participation rates in community consultations or workshops. • Perceived improvements in social inclusion and intergroup relations, based on citizen feedback. • Case studies or narrative reports highlighting community ownership of policy outcomes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring financial sustainability through a diversified revenue model combining public funding, service fees, and strategic partnerships, with the ultimate aim of reducing reliance on fluctuating grants. • Achieve greater self-sustainability by securing income from certification and membership fees for pet-friendly businesses, training fees (e.g. for urban gardeners and ludic educators), public funding, sponsorships and ancillary revenues generated through project activities. • Build robust financial reserves to ensure long-term operational stability and resilience, including providing pro bono or subsidised services to smaller cities with significant social needs and fewer resources. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage of total income derived from diversified revenue streams versus initial grant funding or other public sources. • Total annual revenue generated from HADUP services serves as an indicator of market acceptance and operational scaling. • The number of new funding agreements or strategic partnerships secured with public bodies, private sector entities, or non-profit organisations, including those supporting social enterprise initiatives. • Cost efficiency analysis per service delivered.
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MARKET ANALYSIS

Disclaimer: This is a market analysis developed for an IN-HABIT project. Some of the information may be outdated or inaccurate. If you wish to implement this idea, you should conduct specific market research tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Market overview

The market scope is urban planning and design. The focus is on providing strategic consultation and pioneering advice to governments and cities to help them achieve sustainable urban development and improve quality of life. The aim is to co-create resilient, sustainable, multidimensional urban solutions that consider the needs of humans and animals. This involves integrating natural, social, infrastructural, and

economic vitality into city life. Geographically, the market is primarily focused on Europe, particularly in countries and cities that are actively engaging with NBS and circular economy initiatives. The broader European Union (EU) context, with its commitment to sustainable development and the circular economy, also defines this market. The boundaries of the market are shaped by the growing presence of non-human animals in cities, and by the acknowledged yet underexplored advantages of human–animal interactions as a potential nature-based solution (NBS). The centre would address the lack of specific consideration of integrated policies for non-human animals in urban planning.

High-density clusters, also known as urban centres, represent major cities, each with a population of at least 50,000. There are over 800 such centres in Europe¹⁹ as well as more than 9,000 towns. The Degree of Urbanisation (DEGURBA) is a classification that indicates the character of an area. It categorises a country's territory on an urban-rural scale. DEGURBA uses population size and density thresholds to define three mutually exclusive categories: cities, towns and suburbs, and rural areas. This distribution is shown in the following pictures:

Figure 22 - Urban centres and towns in Europe

Source; Eurostat - https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/maps/urban-centres-towns_en

Figure 24 - Degree of urbanisation, 2018

Source: Eurostat - <https://ec.europa.eu/statistical-atlas/viewer/?config=typologies.json&ch=TYPLOC,TYPLOCURT&mid=BKGCNT,TYPLOCDEG2018,CNTOVL&o=1,1,0.7¢er=54.89525,14.10497,3&lcis=TYPLOCDEG2018&>

In terms of product type, the HADUP centre can offer services such as:

- **Policy design and formulation** (Michael Kinyanjui, 2024): Developing evidence-based new generation urban policies (NUPs) to guide effective public spending. It also involves codifying integrated policies on human–animal relationships.

¹⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/maps/urban-centres-towns_en

- **Strategic planning and spatial management:** Develop spatial strategies and plans that integrate human rights, gender, age, and other identity categories. Prioritise public spaces, mixed land use, and equitable access to land (Rogier van den Berg, n.d.).
- **Capacity building:** Providing support at local, national, and global levels in the form of tools development, organisational development, and institutional strengthening. This includes training on sustainable planning principles (Rogier van den Berg, n.d.).
- **Evaluation and monitoring:** Providing a methodological framework for monitoring and evaluating urban policy processes and their impacts, moving beyond just outputs and outcomes to assess policy phases (Rogier van den Berg, n.d.).

Market size and growth

Cities and regions are recognised as playing a pivotal role in driving the transition to a circular economy. Rapid urbanisation is a global trend, with cities expected to accommodate an ever-growing population, which brings with it mounting environmental, social, and economic challenges. Many countries struggle to implement National Urban Policies (NUPs) due to insufficient financial, human, and institutional capacity, creating a clear demand for external support.

There is an opportunity to develop integrated urban policies for animals, with the aim of improving the quality of life for citizens and animals alike. The European Union's strong emphasis on green growth, sustainable development, and the circular economy, with which this niche is aligned, provides significant impetus for market expansion. Furthermore, urban planning's potential is often underestimated, suggesting substantial latent demand for the comprehensive, innovative approaches offered by such a centre.

Competitive Landscape

An assessment of the competitive landscape using Porter's Five Forces reveals the following:

Threat of new entrants: Entering this specialised market requires in-depth, interdisciplinary expertise in urban planning, policy, nature-based solutions (NBS), human–animal interactions and European regulatory frameworks²⁰. The ability to integrate legal, financial, and spatial planning aspects, as well as robust data analysis and human-centred design methodologies, is crucial. Building a reputation and establishing trust with government bodies and international organisations is a significant barrier to entry, often requiring long-term engagement and demonstrating successful outcomes. Investment in highly skilled teams, extensive research and infrastructure for participatory processes is necessary to meet capital requirements.

Bargaining power of buyers (governments and institutions): Primary buyers, including national and local governments, international organisations, and private entities, possess significant power. They control the implementation of policies, the allocation of funding, and ultimately decide on the adoption of solutions.

²⁰ Source: <https://unhabitat.org/2-urban-planning-and-design>

They often seek bespoke solutions to complex urban challenges and can demand specific expertise and demonstrable impact.

Bargaining power of suppliers (experts, data providers): These services require highly specialised knowledge and expertise in niche areas such as animal welfare, NBS implementation, sustainable urban design, and human-centred policy methodologies.

Threat of Substitute Products or Services: Traditional urban planning consultancies, internal government planning departments and general environmental consulting firms can offer partial substitutes. However, the centre's unique selling point is its integrated focus on human–animal interactions as NBS within urban policy and its human-centred design approach. While the market for general urban planning is broad, this niche seems to be less crowded due to the lack of specific policy reflection on this particular integration.

Intensity of rivalry: Although the urban planning and sustainability consulting market as a whole is competitive, with traditional consulting companies and specialist urban planning services based at universities, no specific data was found. However, it is expected that there will be fewer direct competitors in the niche area of human and animal urban policy design in Europe.

Barriers to entry

Cost modelling and capital requirements: The development of new tools and methodologies requires investment in terms of time and resources.

Regulatory mapping and EU compliance needs: The European regulatory landscape is often complex and fragmented. Some countries lack specific, integrated regulation for green infrastructure and human–animal interactions. Navigating various EU directives and national laws requires specialised legal and policy expertise.

Lack of Specific Policy Reflection: A key barrier, as well as an opportunity, is the lack of specific consideration of the advantages of human–animal interactions as potential nature-based solutions in current policy frameworks. This means that there are limited established guidelines and precedents for this niche, requiring pioneering work in policy codification and advocacy.

Capacity Gaps within Governments: Many countries struggle with the inadequate human, financial and institutional capacity required to implement National Urban Policies (NUPs). There are also skills mismatches in the workforce for emerging circular economy roles, indicating a need for extensive capacity building, which the centre would provide.

Complexity of Urban Planning Processes: Urban planning is inherently complex, involving numerous stakeholders, intricate legal and financial frameworks, and dynamic political situations. This complexity means that successful interventions require a significant investment of time and energy from all parties involved.

Market Opportunities and Risks

Market opportunities

- **Addressing an underserved niche:** The rapid growth of cities and the environmental and social issues that accompany it create a continuous and expanding demand for sustainable urban solutions. The centre can establish itself as a leading provider of innovative solutions to these issues. Existing policy frameworks may not consider the advantages of human–animal interactions as potential nature-based solutions (NBSs). This presents a significant opportunity to pioneer an integrated approach to urban human–animal policy that would offer cities multifaceted benefits.
- **Driving social innovation:** The growing acknowledgement of human–animal relationships presents an opportunity for social innovation processes to redefine urban planning and action, resulting in new public goods and reimagined public spaces. A human-centred design approach can effectively identify unmet needs and encourage the development of innovative solutions.
- **Demand for Integrated Approaches:** There is a recognised need to move beyond sector-based policy approaches in urban planning and design towards more integrated, participatory, and multifunctional solutions.

Market risks

- **Niche Market Size:** While presenting a unique opportunity, focusing on a specific niche (human–animal urban policy) may initially limit the overall addressable market compared to a broader focus on urban planning consultancy.
- **Resistance to systemic change:** Shifting established urban planning paradigms, particularly from “total control” to more adaptive and strategic approaches, can be a slow and challenging process. Overcoming entrenched sector-based policymaking also poses a risk.

Recommendations

Specialise and innovate: The centre can capitalise on its unique proposition by explicitly focusing on integrating human–animal interactions into urban policy design and presenting this as an innovative and effective NBS approach. This distinct focus will differentiate it from traditional urban planning consultancies.

Emphasise participatory co-creation: Actively involve a wide range of stakeholders, including government bodies, private sector entities, NGOs, citizens, and academic institutions, in the co-design, deployment and management of solutions. This approach fosters consensus, ownership, and more effective policy outcomes.

Provide targeted capacity building and knowledge transfer: Offer specialised training Programmes, tools and methodologies to governments and other urban stakeholders to address identified shortcomings in their capacity to formulate, implement and evaluate policies. The centre can serve as a vital “knowledge centre” for this emerging field.

Articulate a clear value proposition: Explain how the centre’s integrated approach delivers multiple benefits, such as enhancing environmental quality, promoting social well-being, fostering economic opportunities, and improving the overall quality of life for human and non-human urban inhabitants. This value proposition should be clearly communicated to potential clients and beneficiaries.

8.2. ANIMAL ASSISTED INTERVENTIONS (AAI)

REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODEL DIMENSIONS

Disclaimer: This is a business model based on the IN-HABIT project. If you would like to use it as inspiration for your own project, you should develop a specific business plan tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Animal Assisted Interventions

Animal-Assisted Interventions (AAI) are transforming elderly care in nursing homes by harnessing Animal-Nature-Based Solutions (A-NBS) to combat loneliness, cognitive decline and physical inactivity. This innovative approach transcends traditional therapies by providing holistic emotional support without the stigma associated with them. This pioneering approach uses human-animal bonds to improve mood, stimulate the mind through memory recall and engagement, encourage gentle physical activity through pet interaction and foster profound social connections, thereby empowering disadvantaged residents, such as those with autism or experiencing homelessness. Through personalised on-site sessions and rigorous training for animal therapists, AAI breaks down barriers, fostering sustainable, evidence-based transformations that redefine therapeutic landscapes with natural, empathetic efficacy.

Problem

The core problem addressed by Animal Assisted Interventions (AAI) is to valorise the power of animals to support therapeutic activities for disadvantaged people from diverse backgrounds. For example, human-animal interaction can prevent social isolation among elderly nursing home residents and lonely people, which can lead to a decline in cognitive and emotional well-being. Many elderly people experience loneliness, reduced physical activity and a lack of stimulating engagement, which can result in a progressive reduction in capabilities and long-lasting disengagement. Traditional therapies may not always be effective in providing the holistic emotional support that some residents require, nor can they use the potential of animals to stimulate people's senses.

Value Proposition

key competitive advantages of Animal Assisted Interventions:

- **Holistic, Natural, and Stigma-Free Approach:** AAI offers a distinctive therapy that harnesses the natural connection between humans and animals. Unlike traditional therapies, it provides holistic emotional support without the stigma often associated with conventional psychological or physical interventions. This natural stimulation can be highly effective in engaging individuals who might be resistant to other forms of therapy.

- **Multidimensional Benefits for Well-being:** AAI is designed to strengthen social and motor skills, promoting greater autonomy and contributing to users' overall health and well-being. Specific benefits for beneficiaries, such as elderly residents in nursing homes, include improved mood and emotional well-being by alleviating loneliness and providing comfort, cognitive stimulation through activities such as recalling animal names, and encouragement of gentle physical activity through interaction such as stroking or playing with animals.
- **Evidence-Based Practice and Professional Standards:** The field of AAI adheres to rigorous professional standards and competencies, including formal training, ongoing education, and regular assessment and evaluation of both human professionals (therapists and handlers) and the animals involved. This commitment to professionalism, animal welfare and participant safety ensures the ethical delivery of services and builds credibility.
- **Addresses Critical Societal Needs:** AAI directly tackles prevalent issues such as social isolation among the elderly, cognitive decline and a lack of stimulating engagement, which traditional therapies may not always address effectively. By fostering social connections and increasing participation, AAI helps to reduce marginalisation and create more empathetic care environments.

Customer Segments (Beneficiaries/Users)

Beneficiaries

- **Primary:** elderly residents in nursing homes, people with autism and the homeless, including those with cognitive impairments, physical limitations, and general age-related fragilities.

Customers

- **Local public administrations:** Municipalities and Local Health Authorities.
- **Nursing homes (RSA):** Seeking innovative ways to improve resident well-being.
- **NGOs, Foundations, and private enterprises** with corporate social responsibility (CSR) policies.

Channels

Services are delivered to beneficiaries on site within nursing homes. This includes scheduled group sessions in designated safe spaces, as well as the integration of services into daily care routines (e.g. specific times and procedures for activities with animals).

- Direct, personalised interaction with trained therapists and animals during therapy sessions (e.g. one-to-one or in small groups).
- The regular presence of trained therapists and animals helps to build trust and familiarity.
- Feedback mechanisms should be in place, such as simple surveys for lucid residents and observations by staff and therapists.
- Formal service agreements/contracts.

- A dedicated account manager/liaison to address needs and concerns.
- Collaborative planning meetings for scheduling and customisation
- Direct communication with funding stakeholders and partners.

Customer Relations

Beneficiaries:

- **Direct, personalised interaction** during therapy sessions (one-to-one or in small groups).
- The regular **presence of trained therapists** and animals to build trust and familiarity.
- **Feedback mechanisms** (e.g. simple surveys for lucid residents or observations by staff/therapists).

Customers (nursing homes, public administrations)

- **Formal service agreements/contracts.**
- **Regular progress reports and impact assessments** to facilitate adaptation and reflexive exercises on the practices
- **Collaborative planning meetings** for scheduling and customisation, providing spaces for co-planning and continued interaction.
- **A dedicated account management/liaison to address needs and concerns.**

Funding stakeholders/partners:

- **Grant applications and reporting**
- **Joint steering committees and working groups**, transparent communication on project progress and financial utilisation
- **Networking at relevant conferences and events.**

Key Activities

The critical activities required to achieve the social mission include:

- **Session planning and customisation:** Developing tailored intervention plans based on resident needs and nursing home requirements, including setting objectives and designing activities. This ensures a personalised, adaptable, inclusive approach.
- **Session delivery:** Conducting animal-assisted intervention sessions in nursing homes consistently, personalized, and safely.
- **Partnership Management & Outreach:** Building and maintaining relationships with nursing homes, local authorities, and other stakeholders to expand reach and ensure systemic integration.
- **Funding & Grant Management:** Identifying, applying for, and managing funding sources to ensure the long-term sustainability and viability of social impact.
- **Animal Training & Welfare:** Providing continuous and rigorous training, as well as ongoing health

and welfare management of therapy animals to ensure their safety, wellness, efficacy, and ethical treatment.

- **Therapist/Handler Training & Certification:** Continuous professional development for licensed professionals to provide high-quality, empathetic care.
- **Monitoring and evaluation:** Collecting data (key performance indicators – KPIs) and assessing impact to demonstrate effectiveness and inform improvements. This ensures accountability and the continuous improvement of social impact.

Key Resources

Key resources needed for successful delivery include:

- **Trained therapy animals:** These could be dogs or other small animals. An estimated five to ten animals may be needed initially.
- **Licensed professionals:** Animal-assisted therapists, Programme coordinators and administrative staff also taking into consideration existing local/national guidelines.
- **Animal handlers/volunteers:** Training, supervision and stipends will be provided if applicable.
- **Veterinary expertise:** Providing health/wellness checks and emergency care for therapy animals.
- **Operational capital:** Funding for salaries, office space, travel, and project expenses.
- **Training content and tools:** Ongoing training and certification.
- **Specialised animal insurance.**
- **Equipment and materials for sessions and specific activities.**
- **Monitoring and evaluation tools and software.**

Key partners

- **Elderly homes:** Crucial for delivery. Provide access to beneficiaries; integrate sessions into their schedules; provide staff support during sessions.
- **Municipality and local health authorities:** Crucial for funding and legitimacy. They should provide political support, potential funding, referrals, and integration into local healthcare strategies. Relationship: Funder, strategic partner, and regulatory liaison.
- **University centre:** Strategic for research and validation provides academic rigour, research support, evaluation methodologies, and potential for student internships.
- **NGOs and Elder Associations:** Supportive and outreach focused. Can assist with outreach, volunteer recruitment, advocacy and potentially co-funding or in-kind support. Relationship: Community partner and advocate.
- **Veterinary services:** Essential for animal welfare. They provide health checks and emergency care for therapy animals.

Competitors & Coopetitors

Coopetition:

- **Care institutions and therapy providers:** Although they offer competing services, they are also key partners in integration and delivery.
- **Elderly associations:** They can provide volunteers or advocate for residents and potentially collaborate on joint initiatives.
- **Local Health Authorities:** They can become a funding or referral partner in the co-deployment of the activities.
- **Municipalities:** Can become a funding or referral partner.

Competition:

- **Traditional therapy models:** These include occupational therapy, physiotherapy, music therapy, art therapy, and psychotherapy, which are often offered by internal staff or specialised clinics. They are better known and easier to manage.
- **Volunteer Programmes:** Unstructured or less specialised visitation Programmes.
- **Other recreational activities:** Bingo, craft sessions and group exercises are often offered in-house. Bingo, craft sessions, and group exercises are often offered in-house just for spending time, although they miss the co-therapeutic potential of AAI.

Cost Structure

Main costs are primarily personnel, animal care, and operational expenses.

- **Personnel Costs:** Salaries for licensed professionals (animal-assisted therapists, program coordinators, administrative staff) and training/supervision for animal handlers/volunteers.
- **Animal Care & Welfare:** Veterinary expenses (regular check-ups, vaccinations, emergency care), food, grooming, and housing supplies, and specialised animal insurance.
- **Training & Professional Development:** Ongoing training for animals and human staff, and certification renewals.
- **Operational & Administrative Costs:** Transport for animals and staff, equipment and materials for sessions, office space, office supplies, communication, IT, and general liability insurance, as well as monitoring and evaluation tools/software.

Revenue Streams

Some potential revenues sources are:

- **Direct revenue:** Potentially user fees for specific individuals or enhanced services.

- **Public funding (primary):** Municipal budgets (e.g. Municipality and Local Health Authorities) and national and regional health and social care budgets (e.g. the Ministry of Health and the local Region) for elderly care and innovative social services.
- **Grants:** EU grants (e.g. the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and Horizon Europe for social innovation pilots), which focus on social inclusion, health, and ageing. Grants will also come from private philanthropic foundations focused on elder care, animal welfare, or social innovation.
- **Public service contracts (emerging):** Direct agreements with municipalities and local health authorities for the delivery of AAI as a public service, which is a form of “product/service sales” to public entities.
- **Donations:** From individuals, corporations (via Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives) and community fundraising.
- **Partnership contributions:** In-kind contributions from entities such as Universities (research and academic support) and NGOs (expertise and volunteers).

Surplus

Any surplus generated by a social business model is usually reinvested in the community or used to improve services and infrastructure.

- **Expansion of Services:** Investing in additional trained animals, hiring more therapists, or extending services to more nursing homes or other disadvantaged populations.
- **Program Development:** Investing in new types of animal-assisted interventions, research, and development of best practices.
- **Staff Development:** Further training and professional development for the team.
- **Sustainability Fund:** Building a reserve to ensure long-term operational stability and resilience against grant fluctuations.
- **Impact Measurement Enhancement:** Investing in more robust systems for data collection and reporting to better demonstrate social value.

Social Impact Measurement

Theory of Change: When trained therapy animals and licensed professionals deliver personalised, structured Animal-Assisted Interventions beneficiaries could experience an improved mood, reduced social isolation, increased cognitive stimulation and gentle physical activity. This could lead to an overall enhancement of their Health and Wellbeing, as well as creating a more humane care environment.

Table 16 - Key Impact Indicators (KIs)

Short-term output	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term Outcomes (impacts)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of AAI sessions held. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved resident mood scores (qualitative and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustained improvement in the overall quality of life for

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of nursing homes involved. • Number of elderly patients reached. • Hours of animal-human interaction delivered. 	<p>quantitative).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced incidence of depression and anxiety symptoms (based on clinical observations and staff reports). • Social interaction among residents has increased. • Enhanced cognitive engagement during sessions (e.g. responding to prompts and memory recall). • Increased participation in other nursing home activities. 	<p>elderly residents.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in reliance on certain medications for mood and behavioural issues. • The creation of more compassionate and engaging care environments within nursing homes. • Observed impact on Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW).
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Macro-Environment (PESTEL Analysis)

Political

- **Government policies that promote active ageing and non-pharmacological interventions can encourage** the adoption of AAI and secure potential funding.
- **Local and national initiatives that promote health and well-being**, such as regional health plans, can generate funding opportunities or facilitate integration.

Economic

- **AAI offers a relatively cost-effective solution** with significant quality-of-life benefits as healthcare costs rise.
- Public budget constraints can hinder direct public funding, but they can also **encourage innovative, efficient solutions**.
- **The potential willingness of nursing homes to allocate a budget to enrichment Programmes** is also important.

Social

- **Growing acceptance and awareness of the benefits of pet therapy:** Increasing public and professional recognition.
- **Aging populations:** A significant demographic shift driving demand for elderly care solutions, and the use of animal-NBS to promote active aging.

- **Increased focus on mental health and social well-being.** There is a greater emphasis on holistic care that goes beyond physical health.
- **Societal attitudes towards animal welfare:** Public expectation of the ethical treatment of therapy animals.
- **Urbanisation Trends:** Currently, more than half of the world's population lives in urban areas, and this figure is projected to reach 75% by 2050 (World Economic Forum, 2022b). This rapid urbanisation presents opportunities and challenges for health and well-being.

Technological

- **New technologies:** A simple app or website enables seniors to easily arrange services such as dog walking, grooming or home visits without having to make a phone call. The service can send photo and video updates directly through the app.

Legal

- **Data privacy:** General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) emphasise the importance of confidentiality for all documentation and participant information. The need to address data privacy and surveillance issues when adopting technology is also noted.
- **Compliance and regulation:** AAI Programmes must meet AAI standards, as well as any additional standards or regulations required by local governing bodies. This includes adherence to local canine legislation (e.g. leash laws, transportation, and vaccinations requirements).
- **Ethical Practice:** The professional ethics of the relevant professions and organisations must be adhered to, and policies and procedures must be in place to ensure the welfare of animals assisting in AAI.

Environmental

- **low-carbon intervention:** AAI generally has a smaller environmental footprint than resource-intensive medical interventions.
- **Nature-Based Solutions (NBS):** There is a push to integrate nature as the backbone of urban development through NBS for infrastructure and land-sparing interventions. These can provide benefits such as climate regulation, disease control, improved air quality, and biodiversity protection.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Critical success factors (CSFs) are the essential conditions that must be met for a business model to be successfully implemented in a new context. Addressing these factors during the design process is crucial for creating robust, transferable, sustainable business models that can be implemented across regions and sectors. Please find below a suggestion for the critical success factors and barriers to implementation. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to function as a starting point for further discussion.

Critical success factors

- Adoption of animal-nature-based solutions (A-NBS) and an integrated human-animal urban policy (IHAUP) by public institutions.
- Availability of scientific expertise in animal behaviour and human-animal interactions to inform strategies.

- Requirement for trained personnel, including community activators, therapists, and animal handlers, to deliver services effectively.
- Ongoing monitoring and evaluation to measure impacts and improve interventions.
- Shift in local stakeholders' perspectives to recognise animals as valuable contributors to urban Health and Wellbeing.
- Active community participation in practical, straightforward, and proactive initiatives.
- Flexible methodologies tailored to address context-specific needs and challenges.
- Compliance with regulations, including local building codes, heritage protection laws, and health and safety standards.
- Effective knowledge transfer through documented methodologies, toolkits, and shared insights on successes and challenges.
- Establishment of robust public-private-people partnerships (PPPs) to support initiatives.

Barriers to Implementation

- Initial difficulties in creating knowledge and raising awareness about the innovative concept of human-animal bonds as a public good.
- Delays in administrative and executive steps in the public competition for personnel selection (e.g. Local Community Activators).
- Resistance to a change of mindset from certain professional sectors (e.g. pet care and, initially, animal rights associations).
- Financial constraints and the need for sustainable funding models beyond initial grants.
- The need for continuous social mediation and reflexivity to maintain the innovation process.

Replication prerequisites

- **People:** The successful replication of this therapeutic model relies on a highly specialised, multidisciplinary workforce that ensures both clinical efficacy and animal welfare. Strategically, this requires certified professionals, handlers and therapists who are trained in strict accordance with national guidelines, to deliver interventions that go beyond simple companionship. This team must be supported by veterinary experts who function as independent monitors of animal welfare, tracking stress levels to ensure ethical standards are met. Furthermore, the model's viability depends on receptive institutional staff; success hinges on care home directors and medical teams willing to integrate these non-pharmaceutical interventions into their established daily care routines.
- **Processes:** From a procedural perspective, the model demands robust governance frameworks to ensure safety and regulatory compliance within sensitive health environments. This involves establishing transparent public procurement mechanisms for tendering services to specialised NGOs, ensuring that providers meet quality standards. Operationally, the intervention must adhere to rigorous protocols, using standardised session plans specifically tailored to patients with complex needs, such as dementia or reduced mobility. Underpinning these operations is a strict ethical framework based on informed consent, requiring clear administrative procedures for obtaining permission from disadvantaged participants or their legal guardians.

- **Other requisites:** The technical feasibility of the model hinges on the selection and protection of its core “living assets”. Replication requires suitable animals that have been specially selected and rigorously trained to pass behavioural assessments. This ensures that they can safely navigate the unpredictable environment of a care facility. To mitigate operational risk for the municipality and the facility, specific liability insurance must be in place to cover animal-related incidents within health facilities. This will secure a safe environment for both disadvantaged residents and therapy animals.

Strategy monitoring

Please find below a suggestion for a strategy monitoring model. This is a *non-exhaustive* list and is intended to be a starting point for further discussion.

Table 17 - Strategy monitoring indicators (Key Performance Indicators)

<p>1) People dimension (Customer Perspective or Stakeholder Engagement)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enhance the quality of life, mental health, and social well-being of elderly residents in nursing homes through animal-assisted interventions. ● Strengthen social inclusion and reduce isolation among disadvantaged groups, particularly the elderly, through human-animal bonds. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reduced incidence of depression/anxiety symptoms (based on clinical observations/staff reports). ● Increased social interaction among residents during and outside AAI sessions. ● Enhanced cognitive engagement during sessions (e.g., response to prompts, memory recall). ● Positive feedback and testimonials from elderly residents, nursing home staff, and families. ● Increased participation in other nursing home activities. ● Physiological and endocrine parameters (e.g., changes in saliva oxytocin and cortisol concentrations in elders) to measure stress reduction and well-being. ● Quality of life and sleep evaluated through 	<p>2) Processes dimension (Internal Processes & Service Provision)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To co-design, co-deploy and co-manage high-quality, ethical, and effective AAI Programmes in nursing homes. ● To ensure the continuous training and welfare of therapy animals and licensed professionals involved in AAI. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of nursing homes contracted/served. ● Resident participation rate (e.g. percentage of eligible residents engaging). ● Completion of scheduled training and professional development for therapists and animal handlers. ● Regular health checks and welfare assessments for therapy animals. ● Progress in establishing formal service agreements/contracts with nursing homes and public health systems. ● Number of sessions held per month/quarter. ● Number of unique beneficiaries participating per month/quarter. ● Average session attendance. ● Staff-reported behavioural improvements (e.g. reduction in agitated episodes). ●
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<p>validated scales and measurements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mood indicators: Observed changes in resident demeanour (e.g. smiling, laughing, calmness versus agitation) during and after sessions. • Health assessments (observational): Staff notes on engagement levels, verbal and non-verbal communication and social interaction. • Focus group feedback: Gather insights from nursing home staff and associations. 	
<p>3) Growth and Learning</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To explore and achieve the replicability and sustainability of AAI programs within Lucca and other cities/institutions. • To contribute to the scientific understanding and public discourse on human-animal bonds as a resource for Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW) and Animal Nature-Based Solutions (A-NBS). • To foster professional development and new job opportunities for AAI experts and related professionals. • To influence urban policies and planning to better integrate human-animal coexistence and A-NBS. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of additional nursing homes or institutions expressing interest in or adopting AAI programs. The Municipality is actively seeking technical and financial solutions to make AAI replicable and stable in city nursing homes. • Securing of specific contracts or municipal budget allocations for the continuation of AAI activities beyond the project lifespan. • Number of scientific articles published, or presentations given. • Feedback from AAI professionals indicating improved professionalism, skills, and satisfaction due to participation in the project. • Participation in cross-learning programs or city networks to share AAI best practices. • Adaptation of methodologies for different 	<p>4) Financial</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To ensure the financial sustainability of AAI programs for the elderly. • To diversify funding sources, moving beyond initial grants. • To demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of AAI as a low-cost, high-impact intervention compared to traditional therapies. • To explore potential for job creation and economic inclusion. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost analysis per AAI session or per participant. AAI generally has a low environmental footprint compared to resource-intensive medical interventions. • Identification of new business models or social entrepreneurship opportunities related to AAI. • Evidence of re-investment of any surplus profits (if generated) back into expanding services, program development, or building a sustainability fund. • Number of professionals who report new job opportunities or strengthened professional skills related to AAI. • Amount of public funding (municipal, regional, national) or grants secured for AAI programs.

target groups or settings (e.g., beyond elderly in nursing homes).	
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MARKET ANALYSIS

Disclaimer: This is a market analysis developed for an IN-HABIT project. Some of the information may be outdated or inaccurate. If you wish to implement this idea, you should conduct specific market research tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Market overview

The European market for animal-assisted interventions encompasses various specific categories, each with a distinct scope and application (Winkle, 2022):

- **Animal-Assisted Activity (AAA):** This involves planned, goal-oriented, informal interactions and visits conducted by a human-animal team for motivational, educational, and recreational purposes.
- **Animal Assisted Education (AAE):** AAE incorporates specially selected and trained animals into educationally relevant, goal-directed teaching plans.
- **Animal-Assisted Therapy (AAT):** AAT involves the integration of specially selected and trained animals into therapeutic, or intervention plans that aim to improve physical, cognitive, psychosocial, behavioural, and/or emotional functioning in humans.
- **Animal Assisted Special Programmes (AASPs):** These are goal-oriented Programmes that incorporate animals into professional fields outside of education and therapy, or in conjunction with licensed professionals.

The market under consideration is animal-assisted interventions (AAIs), an emerging field within the wider human and animal services industries. AAIs are structured, goal-oriented interventions that intentionally incorporate animals into health, education, and human services to promote therapeutic benefits for humans. AAI is centred on collaborative models comprising three or four equally valued parties: the participant (human beneficiary), the dog handler, the AAI provider, who may also be the dog handler, and the dog (Winkle, 2022). This concept is rooted in the concepts of “One Health” and “One Welfare”²¹, which recognise the interconnectedness of human health, animal health, and the environment (Winkle, 2022).

Market size and growth

In 2021, 43% of people aged 65 and over living in cities in the EU reported that their health status was good or very good; this was 2 percentage points higher than the national average for this age group (41%)²². The highest proportions were recorded in Ireland (66%), Sweden (64%), and Belgium (60%). Conversely, the lowest proportions were recorded in Lithuania (11%), Latvia (15%), and Portugal (21%). This means that some countries still have opportunities to improve the health of their elderly population.

Figure 23 - Self-perceived health by sex, age, and degree of urbanisation

²¹ Source: <https://www.fao.org/webcast/home/fr/item/6273/icode/>

²² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/w/ddn-20230413-1>

Source: Eurostat

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/HLTH_SILC_18_custom_5160584/bookmark/map?lang=en&bookmarkId=774a8c4c-3dfc-43df-b224-59178159d29e

Target audience

Older adults, particularly those experiencing social isolation or low digital literacy, as pet ownership has been linked to slower rates of verbal memory and fluency decline among those living alone.

Competitive Landscape

Analysing the competitive landscape for animal-assisted interventions (AAIs) using Porter's Five Forces framework requires interpreting the provided sources, which do not directly discuss market competition in a traditional business sense, but rather focus on standards, ethical practice, and collaboration within the AAI field.

- **Threat of New Entrants:** The AAI Standards of Practice and Competencies outline extensive requirements for individuals and organisations seeking to provide AAI services. These include (Winkle, 2022): Professionals (AAT, AAE and AAC providers) must be licensed or possess an equivalent qualification and specialised expertise. Dog handlers require specific training and experience. All AAI team members must participate in formal continuing education each year. Dogs and handlers must undergo initial and annual re-evaluations to assess their suitability, temperament, and skills. Comprehensive written policies covering complaints, risk assessments, emergency procedures, health and welfare, and ethical treatment are mandatory. Providers must have liability/business insurance that covers AAI and must understand the relevant federal, state, and local laws. These rigorous requirements, together with the emphasis placed on professional qualifications, animal welfare and participant safety, create substantial hurdles to casual entry, thereby ensuring a certain level of professionalism and ethical commitment within the market.

- **Bargaining power of buyers (participants/organisations):** Participants and organisations commissioning AAI Programmes have the explicit right to terminate an intervention at any time. Organisations seeking AAI services are likely to have significant influence as they are encouraged to work above minimum standards and must comply with regional regulations. They can demand adherence to ethical guidelines, professional qualifications and documented outcomes as set out in AAI standards. The emphasis on bespoke plans and measurable progress in AAT and AAE Programmes provides buyers with a means of evaluating providers.
- **Bargaining power of suppliers (dog handlers, professionals, dogs):** Suppliers, particularly dog handlers and the animals themselves, have notable bargaining power due to the highly specialised nature of AAI and the ethical commitment to animal welfare.
- **Threat of substitute products or services:** Although the threat of direct substitutes (e.g. traditional therapies or educational methods without animal involvement) exists, there are unique benefits of the human–animal bond. This fosters positive emotional, psychological, and physical interactions, and there is evidence that it has a beneficial impact on mental health, physical activity, social interaction, cardiovascular health, healthy ageing, and early child development (Pet Alliance Europe., n.d.). This suggests that, although substitutes exist, the distinct advantages offered by animal integration reduce their appeal for certain outcomes.
- **Rivalry among existing competitors:** There could be some geographical competition: For example, AASI has dozens of organizations members in Europe ²³, some operating in the same country

Market trends and external factors

The AAI market in Europe is influenced by a variety of external factors.

- **Policy prioritisation:** Authorities and stakeholders are increasingly recognising the importance of pet population data. Findings on the human-animal bond can inform national and regional priorities relating to healthcare, healthy ageing, and education.
- **Governance and collaboration:** The World Economic Forum (WEF) emphasises the need for multistakeholder action and public–private partnerships to address urban health, climate resilience, and inclusion. Cities are regarded as pivotal in driving policy innovation and implementing global agendas such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Paris Agreement.

Barriers to entry

Entering or competing in the AAI market, particularly in Europe, involves several significant barriers, primarily relating to rigorous competence, ethical practice, and animal welfare requirements (Winkle, 2022).

- **Training and education:** Significant investment is required for formal education, licensure, and specialised AAI training for professionals (AAT, AAE and AAC providers). Dog handlers also require training in specific, humane methods. This includes formal continuing education.

²³ Source: <https://aas-int.org/continents/europe/>

- **Animal Acquisition and Care:** This includes costs associated with the ethical procurement of dogs, comprehensive health checks by a licensed veterinarian at least once a year, vaccinations, parasite prevention and ensuring that the dog's basic needs (food, housing, and enrichment) are met throughout its life.
- **Infrastructure and equipment:** To provide a safe working environment, first aid kits for humans and dogs are required. Clean, accessible facilities that are conducive to AAI activity must also be provided. Equipment such as toys and blankets must also be kept clean.
- **Insurance:** AAI providers must have liability/business insurance that specifically covers AAI activities, including potential emergency transportation, bodily injury, and aftercare.
- **Professional qualifications:** AAT and AAE must be directed/delivered by licensed, qualified or equivalent professionals within their scope of practice.
- **Legal counsel:** Providers are recommended to seek legal counsel to review policies, procedures and documents concerning participation and safety, and to familiarise themselves with local laws.

Market opportunities and risks

Market opportunities

- **Growing recognition of benefits:** There is growing recognition of the benefits of the human-animal bond. These benefits include positive impacts on physical well-being, mental health, healthy ageing, social inclusion, and cardiovascular health. T
- **Economic Impact and Savings:** The potential for AAI to positively impact the economy through reduced doctor visits and improved healthcare outcomes provides a strong economic case for investment and integration into public services.
- **Collaborative models:** The focus on collaboration between multiple stakeholders (including governments, businesses, non-profits, and academia) in urban development creates opportunities for AAI providers to work alongside a variety of organisations, such as healthcare providers, educational institutions, and community Programmes.
- **Standardisation and professionalisation:** Comprehensive standards and competencies (e.g. the AAI framework) provide a pathway for professionalisation and increased credibility, which could attract more investment and public acceptance as the field matures.

Market risks

- **Animal Welfare Concerns:** A significant risk is the potential for animal exploitation, either intentionally or accidentally. Any compromise to animal well-being, whether physical or emotional, or the use of inhumane training methods, could severely damage the reputation of the organisation. It is crucial to ensure that dogs genuinely enjoy participating.
- **Zoonotic disease transmission and public health crises:** Despite the existence of guidelines, there is still a risk of transmission of zoonotic diseases (e.g. parasites, viruses, and bacteria) and of challenges during public health crises.

- Participant safety and suitability: Risks associated with improper screening of participants (e.g. allergies, a history of animal cruelty or immunocompromised status) or handlers failing to control the situation can lead to injury or negative outcomes for humans and animals.
- Retirement and loss of animals: The emotional impact of the retirement or death of an animal involved in animal-assisted interventions (AAIs) on participants and staff must be managed, and clear transition plans are necessary.

Recommendations

- Emphasise evidence-based practice and outcomes. Continuously measure and document the efficacy of AAI Programmes, particularly in AAT and AAE, to build a robust evidence base. This will strengthen the economic case for AAI by demonstrating its value in improving health outcomes and potentially reducing healthcare costs.
- Champion animal welfare and advocacy: Maintain and clearly communicate an unwavering commitment to the physical and emotional well-being of animals involved in AAI. Ensure that they are truly considered "equal valued parties". Educate participants and the public on how to interact with animals appropriately and respectfully. This ethical foundation is paramount for the long-term sustainability and acceptance of the field.
- Invest in continuous professional development. Due to the high barriers to entry and the evolving nature of the field, it is crucial to consistently invest in the training, ongoing education, and supervision of all AAI personnel (handlers and professionals). This ensures competence, addresses emerging risks (e.g. zoonoses), and maintains high standards of practice.
- Target niche markets with high social value. Focus on delivering AAI services tailored to disadvantaged groups (e.g. older adults), where the human-animal bond can provide significant and measurable benefits and address unmet social needs.

8.3. PET CARE SERVICES

REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODEL DIMENSIONS

Disclaimer: This is a business model based on the IN-HABIT project. If you would like to use it as inspiration for your own project, you should develop a specific business plan tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Pet care services

This service supports individuals who are temporarily underserved and need assistance with pet care. This alleviates their anxiety and reduces the risks associated with delayed access to care. The service can also address the daily needs of humans and pets in underserved situations, supporting everyday life and preventing difficulties and social isolation. It fosters mental and physical health. By empowering municipalities, and NGOs with specialised expertise, regulatory innovation and cost-effective strategies, the service positions cities as pioneers in compassionate, resilient urban planning through collaboration with animal welfare groups.

Problem

Individuals experiencing temporary vulnerabilities need assistance with pet care. Without this support, they may experience anxiety and face the risks associated with delayed access to care.

Value Proposition

For beneficiaries (citizens and animals in client cities): This service supports individuals who are temporarily in need and need assistance with pet care. This alleviates their anxiety and reduces the risks associated with delayed access to care. The service can also address the daily needs of humans and pets in underserved situations, supporting everyday life and preventing difficulties and social isolation. It fosters mental and physical health. Three 'macro-categories' of services were offered:

- **Domestic services: taking care of the pet and purchasing basic pet supplies.**
- **Outdoor services with the owner: services such as transporting the pet to the vet or walking the dog together.**
- **Outdoor services without the owner: transporting the pet to the vet or walking the pet without the owner.**
- **For customers (cities/municipalities, urban planners, public administrations):** The service provides evidence-based solutions and innovations in human-animal services for underserved citizens, enhancing citizen satisfaction by responding to their needs regarding human-animal coexistence and well-being.

key competitive advantages for the Pet Care Services:

- 1. Integrated Support for Underserved Populations and Their Pets:** The service uniquely addresses a critical and often overlooked dual need by providing assistance to individuals experiencing temporary vulnerabilities or fragilities (such as the elderly, those with disabilities, or those facing financial insecurity) and supporting their pet care needs. This integrated approach alleviates anxiety for pet owners, reduces the risks associated with delayed access to care and helps to maintain the daily routines of both humans and pets in disadvantaged situations. This helps to prevent difficulties and social isolation. It goes beyond conventional pet services by promoting the mental and physical wellbeing of an underserved demographic.
- 2. Holistic Health and Well-being Enhancement and Inclusive Communities:** This service uses the natural advantages of human-animal interaction to encourage overall mental and physical health. For beneficiaries, this means improved well-being through reduced loneliness, increased physical activity and stimulated cognitive function thanks to their bond with pets. Furthermore, the service aims to create inclusive communities by developing policies that consider the diverse needs of pet and non-pet owners alike, thereby reducing human-animal conflicts and enhancing safety, cleanliness and overall well-being within urban environments.
- 3. Strong alignment with societal trends and policy directives:** Pet Care Services are strategically aligned with major societal trends, including the ageing population in Europe and the growing recognition of the importance of human-animal relationships for well-being and quality of life in urban areas.

Customer Segments (Beneficiaries/Users)

Beneficiaries: Citizens: Fragile (also temporarily) Pet owners in urban environments.

Customers:

- **Cities/Municipalities:** Urban planning, public health, environmental departments, and mayoral offices.
- **Regional Governments:** Aiming to create overarching guidelines or support local initiatives.
- **Urban Development Agencies:** Seeking innovative policy solutions for integration into new projects.
- **NGOs:** social organisations adopting innovative solutions

Channels

For Beneficiaries. A dedicated website and online resources highlight the service's methodology, success stories, and thought leadership.

For customers (i.e. cities and municipalities), delivery channels include direct business-to-government (B2G) sales and consultancy models. These involve outreach to urban planning departments, public health departments, and mayoral offices.

Customer Relations

For clients (cities/municipalities), relationships are maintained through formal service contracts and memoranda of understanding (MoUs). Dedicated project managers provide a personalised and responsive service. Regular progress meetings and workshops facilitate collaborative policy co-design and iterative development.

Post-project support and monitoring and evaluation ensure ongoing engagement in order to assess impact and provide refinement.

Key Activities

Service delivery:

- **Domestic Pet Care:** This includes feeding, administering medication, light grooming, cleaning pet areas and ensuring pet comfort and safety.
- **Managing pet supply procurement and delivery:** Purchasing and delivering necessary pet food, medication, and other basic supplies.
- **Providing outdoor services with or without the owner.** Arranging and conducting pet transportation (e.g. to vet appointments) and dog walking services.

Client management and support:

- **Business Development & Client Acquisition:** Identify potential client cities, develop proposals, and secure contracts.
- **Vulnerability assessment and onboarding:** Identifying and assessing disadvantaged clients and their pets, understanding their specific needs and health conditions (human and pet), and familiarising them with emergency protocols.
- **Scheduling and coordination:** Efficiently scheduling services, managing logistics and coordinating with clients, their families and other care providers.
- **Building and maintaining client relationships:** Providing ongoing support and adapting services as client needs change through empathetic, personalised communication.

Partnership Development & Management:

- **Cultivating strategic partnerships:** Actively engaging with local governments, healthcare providers, social service agencies and non-profits to secure referrals, align with city-wide well-being goals and explore funding opportunities.
- **Veterinary and Retailer Engagement:** Forge relationships with local vets to secure referrals and with pet supply stores to negotiate potential discounts or expedited services.

Staff Management & Training:

- **Recruitment, vetting and training:** Hire compassionate, reliable, and skilled pet caregivers and administrative staff. Provide comprehensive training in pet care, first aid, client sensitivity, and emergency procedures.
- **Ongoing professional development:** Ensuring staff are continuously educated on best practices in pet care and supporting disadvantaged populations.

Technology Development & Maintenance:

- **Platform management:** Developing and maintaining a user-friendly and secure digital platform for scheduling.

Key Resources

The model relies on a diverse set of resources, such as:

Human capital:

- **Skilled Caregivers:** A team of trained and reliable pet care professionals is essential for delivering a high-quality service.
- **Dedicated administrative and support staff:** Responsible for client onboarding, scheduling, customer relations, and partnership management.
- **Specialised expertise:** Individuals with knowledge of animal behaviour, elder care, disability support, and social work can improve the quality of the service.

Technological infrastructure:

- **User-friendly digital platform:** A robust and accessible mobile app and/or website for managing clients and staff, scheduling and communicating.

Physical assets:

- **Vehicles:** A fleet of pet-friendly vehicles for the safe transportation of pets to vets or other locations and to facilitate staff mobility.
- **Office space (if applicable):** For administration, training, and coordination.
- **Communication & Dissemination Tools:** Professional assets, including a website, branding materials, presentation resources, and policy brief templates.

Key partners

- **Lead project partners:** These usually include a research institution, a social enterprise or partner with expertise on the activity to be implemented and, a public authority.
- **Research institutions:** Provides academic rigour and research insights, as well as faculty expertise, to legitimise the “humanimal” approach. It serves as an academic partner and knowledge base.
- **Client cities/municipalities:** They are the primary customers and co-developers. Acts as the key pilot

city, providing a real-world testing ground and a compelling case study for other cities. It acts as a pilot customer and reference partner.

Social Services & Health Departments: For client referrals, policy alignment with city-wide well-being initiatives and potential public funding.

- **Aging & Disability Services:** For targeted outreach and specialised programme integration.
- **Hospitals, clinics, and home healthcare agencies:** For patient referrals, especially during temporary incapacitation or recovery periods.
- **Local charities and support groups:** To reach specific disadvantaged communities (e.g. low-income, disabled and elderly) and deliver integrated support together.
- **Local veterinarians:** For referrals, advice on pet health and emergency contacts.
- **Pet supply stores:** Discounts on basic pet supplies or delivery partnerships.

Competitors & Coopetitors

Competition: Emerging pet-care service providers and informal care networks: These include neighbours, friends, family members, and individual freelance caregivers.

Coopetition: Animal welfare NGOs/associations, animal shelters and rescue organisations, home healthcare agencies, and local councils/social services.

Cost Structure

- **Salaries and wages:** For pet caregivers, drivers, client coordinators/case managers, administrative staff, and management.
- **Training and development:** Ongoing professional development, certifications, and specialised training in pet care, first aid and supporting disadvantaged populations.
- **Transportation:** Purchase/lease of vehicles, fuel, maintenance and insurance for pet transport and staff mobility.
- **Technology:** Development, maintenance and licensing of the digital platform (app/website), software, and data management systems.
- **Marketing & Outreach:** Costs associated with reaching disadvantaged populations and potential partners, including materials for community centres and digital advertising.
- **Office and administrative costs:** Rent, utilities, communication systems, and office supplies.
- **Pet supplies:** The cost of purchasing basic pet food, medication, and other essentials, especially if subsidised or provided as part of the service.
- **Licensing and permits:** Costs associated with operating a pet care service and working with disadvantaged populations.

Revenue Streams

The service would primarily generate income through a fixed-price table. There is also potential in the future for a membership/subscription model.

This could be supplemented by forming partnerships with private urban developers on large-scale, integrated projects.

Surplus

Any surplus generated by the social business model is usually reinvested in the community or used to improve services and infrastructure.

Social Impact Measurement

Impact assessment goes beyond traditional financial metrics to capture changes in inclusive health and well-being (IHW) across all dimensions, including economic, psychological, social, and relational. The Theory of change is based on the principle that client cities will develop more inclusive, animal-friendly, and healthier urban environments, which will lead to improved well-being for citizens and enhanced animal welfare, as well as promoting sustainable human-animal relations.

Table 18 - Key Impact Indicators (KIIs)

Short-term output	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term Outcomes (impacts)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of disadvantaged individuals and their pets who receive care, support, and resources directly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subjective wellbeing: mental distress, Psychological wellbeing Social wellbeing. Social cohesion. social inclusion. Equity Healthy lifestyles. Perceived physical health. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Life satisfaction.

Macro-Environment (PESTEL Analysis)

Political: The decentralisation of powers to municipalities grants more autonomy for the implementation of local policies. The UN Decade of Healthy Ageing (2021–2030), led by the World Health Organization²⁴, represents a coordinated global and European initiative aimed at enhancing the lives of older individuals.

²⁴ <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ageing-and-health>

Economic: As healthcare costs increase, the demand for low-cost, high-impact care is rising, making Pet care services a relatively cost-effective solution and opportunities. While public budget constraints can hinder direct public funding, they also drive the need for innovative, efficient solutions.

Social: The benefits of human-animal interactions are becoming increasingly accepted and recognised by the public and professionals alike. There is an increased focus on mental health and social well-being, emphasising holistic care.

Technological: Technological advancements offer opportunities for innovative pet services. The increasing popularity of buying pet supplies online suggests potential for online service booking and delivery. The project could use online platforms for the administrative or training aspects of Pet services.

Legal: Any service collecting and processing personal data, including customer demographics and service preferences, must comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe. Any services involving animal health would also need to adhere to veterinary and animal welfare laws.

Environmental: Pet services generally has a smaller environmental impact than resource-intensive medical interventions. Ethical breeding and rescue practices (e.g. sourcing animals from shelters) can align with environmental and social values.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Critical success factors (CSFs) are the essential conditions that must be met for a business model to be successfully implemented in a new context. Addressing these factors during the design process is crucial for creating robust, transferable, sustainable business models that can be implemented across regions and sectors.

Please find below a suggestion for the critical success factors and barriers to implementation. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to function as a starting point for further discussion.

Critical success factors

- **Demonstrated positive impact.** The ability of the services to visibly improve quality of life for citizens, particularly disadvantaged and fragile groups, strengthens support.
- **Strong partnerships and collaborations.** Collaboration between municipal authorities, research institutions, NGOs, and other partners is essential for co-design, co-deployment and fostering new business models.
- **Adaptability and innovation in methodologies:** Innovative participatory methods and adaptable toolkits are used to tailor solutions to specific contexts and ensure inclusive engagement.

Barriers to Implementation

- **Administrative and institutional complexities:** Significant delays can arise from administrative processes such as the recruitment of local activators. Coordinating interactions between multiple municipal departments can also be time-consuming.
- **Engagement challenges:** There could be some difficulties in involving certain disadvantaged groups.

Replication prerequisites

- **People:** The successful replication of this social support service relies on a tiered human capital structure that can bridge the gap between social care and animal welfare. Strategically, this necessitates vulnerability assessors, typically social workers, or administrative staff, who possess the qualifications to identify and validate beneficiaries, ensuring that resources are targeted effectively at those most in need. This oversight function must be supported by a robust logistics network consisting of a coordinated team of vetted staff or volunteers who can deliver core services such as dog walking, temporary fostering, and transport. This ensures that disadvantaged owners receive reliable support.
- **Processes:** From a procedural perspective, the model demands agile governance mechanisms to manage the unpredictability of disadvantaged users' needs. Cities must establish an emergency protocol, a codified system for the rapid deployment of support when a beneficiary faces an immediate crisis, such as sudden hospitalisation. This operational agility is underpinned by formal agreements that establish clear legal frameworks between the municipality and the implementing NGOs, authorising service provision and defining liability. Furthermore, coordination efficiency is maintained through a streamlined management interface using a simple digital platform or dedicated phone line to centralise bookings and coordinate volunteer deployment.
- **Other requisites:** The model's independence relies on specific mobility infrastructure to ensure access to care. A critical requirement is pet-friendly transport, specifically access to vehicles suitable for veterinary visits and the safe transportation of animals. This ensures that the service can operate independently of the beneficiary's resources and overcome mobility barriers that often prevent disadvantaged owners from accessing essential veterinary care.

Strategy monitoring

Please find below a suggestion for a strategy monitoring model. This is a *non-exhaustive* list and is intended to be a starting point for further discussion.

Table 19 - Strategy monitoring indicators (Key Performance Indicators)

<p>1) People dimension (Customer Perspective or Stakeholder Engagement)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improving the mental health and psychological well-being of disadvantaged pet owners. ● To enhance social cohesion and inclusion for fragile people in need of pet management support. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● User satisfaction ratings with the service. ● Observed improvements in mood and reduced anxiety and depression 	<p>2) Processes dimension (Internal Processes & Service Provision)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To co-design and co-deploy innovative pet care services through a participatory approach involving local authorities and social organisations. ● Offer a range of services tailored to the diverse needs of disadvantaged pet owners. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Defined service macro-categories: This confirms the implementation of varied service types, such as domestic care and
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<p>symptoms among beneficiaries (e.g. based on clinical observations or staff reports where applicable).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative feedback from users and service providers on perceived support and reduction of anxiety related to pet management. 	<p>outdoor services, either with or without the owner (e.g. vet transport or dog walking).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequency and scope of service delivery: Documenting the daily availability and reach of pet care services.
<p>3) People dimension (Customer Perspective or Stakeholder Engagement)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure high satisfaction and a positive perception among target users and stakeholders in new areas. • Achieve deep and inclusive engagement with local communities. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of stakeholders involved in implementation efforts, disaggregated by protected characteristics (e.g. gender, age, disability, and ethnicity). • Adoption rate or participation levels in replicated activities/services. • Perceived improvements in social inclusion, cohesion, and intergroup relations in new contexts. 	<p>Financial dimension</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To ensure the financial sustainability of Pet services. • To demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of Pet services as a low-cost, high-impact intervention compared to traditional therapies. • To explore potential for job creation. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost analysis per Pet service. • Evidence of re-investment of any surplus profits (if generated) back into expanding services, program development, or building a sustainability fund. • Number of professionals who report new job opportunities or strengthened professional skills related to Pet services. • Amount of public funding (municipal, regional, national) or grants secured for Pet services programs.

MARKET ANALYSIS

Disclaimer: This is a market analysis developed for an IN-HABIT project. Some of the information may be outdated or inaccurate. If you wish to implement this idea, you should conduct specific market research tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Market overview

Approximately 139 million European households own a pet, with 26% owning at least one dog and 25% owning at least one cat (FEDIAF, 2025). The market is supported by a large pet population, with cats and dogs being the most popular pets in Europe, with 108 million and 90 million, respectively. The pet services market in Europe falls within the broader pet care industry and is expected to benefit from the overall growth in services and products, which increased by 9% in 2023 (FEDIAF, 2025).

Market Size and Growth

The European pet care industry is a significant market. The total European value of pet related services and products (including accessories and services) is estimated at €24.6 billion (FEDIAF, 2025). The growth of the services sector within the wider pet industry suggests a positive outlook for this niche.

Target Audience

The primary target audience for pet services is the Fragile (also temporarily) Pet owners in urban environments. In 2023, a total of 71.9 million people were at risk of poverty. Of these, 5.5 million were also experiencing severe material and social deprivation and living in a household with very low work intensity. (European Commission, 2024b).

Europe is experiencing significant demographic ageing, a long-term trend driven by low fertility rates and rising life expectancy. The EU-27's population of people aged 65 years or more is expected to increase significantly, rising from 90.5 million in early 2019 to an estimated 129.8 million by 2050²⁵. Even more strikingly, the number of people aged 85 or over is expected to more than double (an increase of 113.9%) between 2019 and 2050, rising from 12.5 million to 26.8 million. The number of centenarians is also expected to increase from 96,600 in 2019 to almost half a million (484,000) by 2050²⁶.

This demographic shift highlights the growing potential client base. Older residents often face significant vulnerabilities, including financial insecurity, poverty, and social and physical isolation (World Economic Forum, 2022a). They are also more likely to spend most of their time at home, which can exacerbate loneliness and experience mobility issues and have limited access to healthcare services. This highlights the need for services that cater to the needs of both pets and their elderly owners, contributing to their well-being and social connection.

Services that support pet ownership, such as grooming, dog walking or home-based veterinary visits, would address the needs of elderly people with reduced mobility or limited social networks who still wish to keep their pets.

Competitive Landscape

A Porter's Five Forces analysis of the pet services industry for the elderly in Europe indicates a dynamic and evolving competitive environment.

Threat of new entrants: The emergence of standalone Pet care companies within the wider pet industry suggests that barriers to entry for new, innovative pet service providers may not be overly high. However,

²⁵ Source: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ageing-and-health>

²⁶ Ibid

building trust with disadvantaged elderly people, establishing a reputation, and navigating potential regulatory complexities (e.g. for home visits or specialised care) could be challenging.

Bargaining power of buyers (elderly pet owners): Older residents may face financial insecurity (World Economic Forum, 2022a), which could increase their demand for affordable services. On the other hand, the deep emotional bond between owners and their pets, and the tendency to view pets as family members, can lead to a willingness to pay for quality care. This can potentially reduce price sensitivity and thus limit buyer power for premium or highly trusted services.

Bargaining power of suppliers: In the broader pet care industry, suppliers could include providers of pet care products or training services. Their bargaining power would depend on how unique they are, how concentrated they are, and how high the switching costs are for service providers.

Threat of Substitute Products or Services: While informal care provided by family, friends or volunteers could substitute some services (e.g. dog walking), this may not suffice for all needs, particularly those of increasingly frail owners or pets requiring complex veterinary care. Owners who view their pets as family are likely to resist the undesirable alternative of neglecting a pet's needs.

Rivalry among existing competitors: The emergence of new players indicates an active, though not necessarily saturated, market. The degree of rivalry within the "pet services" niche would depend on the number of specialised providers, how differentiated their services are, and the growth rate of this specific market segment.

Barriers to Entry

There are several challenges that could hinder new entrants or competition in the pet services market for the elderly.

Cost modelling: Setting up a comprehensive pet services business (e.g. veterinary services, mobile grooming, or dog walking) requires an initial investment in equipment, transport, licensing, and marketing.

Regulatory mapping: It is crucial to understand and adhere to existing national and local pet care laws, as well as any potential future regulations related to services for the elderly.

Building trust: A significant challenge is building trust and rapport with the elderly population, who may prefer well-established providers or rely on personal recommendations.

Market Opportunities and Risks

Market opportunities

- **Market opportunities for pet care services for temporarily disadvantaged people:** The broader pet care market is experiencing growth, driven by the growing significance of pets in their owners' lives. For individuals who are temporarily disadvantaged, pets often provide more than companionship; they are a vital source of emotional support and well-being. This makes their care a priority, even during difficult times.
- **Addressing the needs of older adults and disabled individuals:** Services such as mobile grooming, in-home pet care, or assistance with transporting pets to the vet can directly address mobility limitations and social isolation. This ensures that pets receive the necessary care they need while

supporting their owners' well-being. This approach is in line with the broader push for holistic health and supportive environments.

- **Support during financial hardship and employment instability:** There are opportunities to develop affordable, flexible, or subsidised pet care models. Inspiration can be drawn from “pay-it-forward” schemes or micro-lending initiatives to help owners maintain their pets' care during temporary financial distress.
- **Assistance during displacement and housing insecurity:** Services offering temporary pet housing, emergency foster care or assistance with pet-friendly relocation could address a critical need for these populations and contribute to “durable solutions” for displaced communities. Such support can alleviate the emotional strain on owners who are already under immense stress.

Market risks

Affordability constraints:

- **Limited financial resources:** Disadvantaged populations often have limited disposable income. The general market trend towards premiumisation may not align with the financial realities of these clients. This requires pet care services to develop highly flexible and cost-effective pricing models, which can present a challenge to financial sustainability.
- **Reliance on subsidies/grants:** To ensure accessibility, organisations may need to rely on grants, donations, or public funding, which can be inconsistent and subject to policy changes.

Fluctuating demand and resource instability:

- **Unpredictable needs:** The “momentarily disadvantaged” nature of clients means that their need for pet care services can be unpredictable and vary with changes in health, financial stability, or housing situation. This can make resource planning and staffing challenging.
- **Crisis-driven demand spikes:** During acute crises, such as health emergencies or natural disasters, there may be a sudden and overwhelming demand for services, requiring robust and adaptable response mechanisms.

9. REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODELS ASSESSMENT WITHIN THE NITRA PILOT

The context of Nitra

Nitra is widely recognised as the largest agricultural centre in the Slovak Republic. Situated in the Danube Lowland, an area with a long-standing agricultural heritage, the city boasts a considerable number of food processing industries.

With a population of 78,353 (as of 2020) and an area of 100.48 square kilometres, Nitra is the sixth largest city in Slovakia (Katarína Melichová (SUA) et al., 2022). In terms of the Slovak Republic's settlement structure, the city of Nitra is defined as a centre of superregional to nationwide importance and, in terms of some specific functions, of international importance.

Nitra's Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS)

The IN-HABIT project in Nitra, Slovakia, uses the themes of “art” and “environment” to connect places and people. The co-deployment process relies heavily on the “do it yourself” (DIY) culture and collaborative attitude of the community around Hidepark, promoting economic sustainability through innovative business models.

Replicable business models

Of all the VIS created during Córdoba’s pilot implementation, the partners identified one innovations as having potential for replication²⁷: the Community bike-sharing station and service.

Community bike-sharing station and service Photos

Figure 24 – Refurbished old bicycles

Figure 25 – Community Bike Sharing station

Source: <https://www.facebook.com/bikesharingnitra>

To evaluate the Societal Readiness Level (SRL) and Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) of the KER and VIS with replication potential, the project partners completed a self-assessment questionnaire. The results are presented in the images below.

²⁷ **Replicable business models** are developed by systematically analysing successful cases and identifying the good practices, people, types of customers, processes, practices, operational requirements, and critical factors for replication involved.

Figure 26 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire for the community bike-sharing station and service SLR and TRL levels

The **community bike-sharing station and service** has an SRL of 6, meaning the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment to gain initial feedback on its potential impact. This approach focuses on repurposing existing materials, which aligns with a TRL of 0. This indicates that the core innovation is not centred on developing a new technological solution. Deploying the service, engaging the community in repairs and usage, and operating continuously in a real-world setting demonstrate that the solution is being evaluated and refined using direct stakeholder feedback. This fits the description of an SRL of six.

9.1. COMMUNITY BIKE SHARING

REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODEL DIMENSIONS

Disclaimer: This is a business model based on the IN-HABIT project. If you would like to use it as inspiration for your own project, you should develop a specific business plan tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

The community bike-sharing service provides an affordable, sustainable urban transport solution that empowers local communities by promoting an active lifestyle. It also brings the community into the design process. The bicycles are made from spare parts and are available for seasonal rental. A bicycle repair workshop is also provided to encourage users to get involved in maintaining the service. The service promotes cycling culture and offers flexible rental options. It also supports the local economy by increasing 'slow' traffic. It improves the quality of urban living by co-designing better public spaces, enhancing safety and cleanliness, and fostering inclusive communities. By involving users in bicycle maintenance, the model fosters a sense of community ownership and promotes more circular use of resources. The service also generates economic opportunities by encouraging social entrepreneurship, such as bike repair shops, as well as offering labour, training, and socialisation opportunities.

Problem

There is a general need for affordable, sustainable urban transport solutions that actively encourage communities to adopt healthier, more active lifestyles.

Value Proposition

The community bike-sharing service provides an affordable, sustainable urban transport solution that empowers local communities by promoting an active lifestyle. It also brings the community into the design process. The bicycles are made from spare parts and are available for seasonal rental. A bicycle repair workshop is also provided to encourage users to get involved in maintaining the service. The service promotes cycling culture and offers flexible rental options. It also supports the local economy by increasing 'slow' traffic. It improves the quality of urban living by co-designing better public spaces, enhancing safety and cleanliness, and fostering inclusive communities. By involving users in bicycle maintenance, the model fosters a sense of community ownership and promotes more circular use of resources. The service also generates economic opportunities by encouraging social entrepreneurship, such as bike repair shops, as well as offering labour, training, and socialisation opportunities.

Key competitive advantages for the community bike-sharing station and service

- **Affordability and accessibility:** The service provides an affordable, sustainable urban transport solution. Using bicycles made from refurbished old bikes and spare parts allows for lower fares compared to traditional bike-sharing models that use new fleets. This makes the service highly appealing to low-income households, students and environmentally conscious individuals. This meets the demand for accessible, low-cost mobility solutions, particularly among groups who might otherwise rely on more expensive private transport or have limited options. It offers a cheaper alternative to regular bike-sharing schemes. The model aligns with cities' goals of making mobility accessible to those who are unbanked, digitally illiterate or on a low income.
- **Community Empowerment and Ownership:** The service actively encourages communities to adopt healthier, more active lifestyles by empowering locals through co-design and the sustainable use of resources. It fosters a sense of community ownership and promotes the more sustainable use of resources by involving users in bicycle maintenance through public repair workshops, where volunteers provide instruction. This promotes resourcefulness and community involvement. Designing cycle routes in collaboration with the community and integrating them with public spaces, as well as organising volunteer activities for repairs and space maintenance, strengthens community engagement through shared cycling networks.
- **Focus on sustainability and the circular economy:** The service repurposes existing materials and refurbishes old bikes, aligning with a circular economy approach and reducing overall resource consumption and waste. This model strongly supports environmental benefits and EU environmental objectives, providing a unique selling point. It demonstrates a commitment to sustainable urban mobility and climate goals.

- **Local Economic Development and Social Entrepreneurship:** The service reinforces the local economy by supporting social entrepreneurship, such as bike repair shops, and by offering employment, training and socialisation opportunities. It encourages 'slow' traffic, which benefits the local economy. Focusing on community resources rather than large initial investments makes this business model ideal for local deployment.

Customer Segments

- General public, cyclists, students, low-income families
- Municipalities and local governments
- NGOs promoting sustainable transport
- Universities and educational institutions

Channels

The service can be provided by a single bike rental shop or by a network of shops located along newly developed or revitalised cycle corridors and public spaces.

Community engagement can be achieved through monthly cycling events and social media campaigns. Social channels (such as WhatsApp) can also be used, as well as the telephone.

Other offline communication tools can also be employed, such as posters, local events, and workshops led by community activators that are tailored to specific groups. Workshops and conferences can be held to encourage the sharing of knowledge and the adoption of these ideas in other cities and networks.

Partnerships with local media and communication channels can be established to reach the right people in the local area.

Customer Relations

Users: Directly Contact during the bike rental and maintenance process via social channels such as WhatsApp or by telephone.

Volunteers: In-person services and repairs require the involvement of volunteers for preparation, implementation, management, and maintenance. This helps local communities to develop a connection to the spaces and solutions.

Customers: Relationships with funders are maintained through transparent reporting, shared visibility, and policy engagement.

Main Activities

The key activities include:

- Managing bike rentals and bicycle repairs.
- Co-designing cycle routes and integrating them with public spaces.
- Organising volunteer activities such as repairing bicycles, preparing, implementing, managing, and maintaining spaces (e.g. planting, litter collection, and road repair).

- Implement thematic workshops (e.g. educational Programmes on bike safety) and annual satisfaction surveys to gather improvement ideas.

Key Resources

The key resources that support these activities include:

- **Skilled maintenance teams with fully equipped repair facilities. One or more bicycle maintenance staff or volunteers. One person coordinating the leasing and communication with participants**
- **A fleet of refurbished bicycles and a supply of spare parts, which promote resourcefulness and community involvement.**
- **A bicycle repair workshop for maintenance and community engagement.**
- **Warehousing facilities for the storage and distribution of bikes and resources.**
- **Payment gateway.**
- **Insurance and permits.**

Key partners

The key delivery partners include:

- Implementation partner: The partner is responsible for managing the bike-sharing service and engaging with the community.
- Other partners: Bicycle parts suppliers (used and new), payment providers, urban planners' experts, and insurance companies.
- Local government and institutions. These stakeholders are essential in providing access to sites and permits for project activities.
- Universities: Academic institutions that support the project's research and social impact evaluation.

Competitors & Coopetition

Competitors include traditional bike-sharing systems, car-sharing services, public transport operators, e-scooter/micro-mobility providers, private bike owners (targeted long-term rentals), and ride-hailing services.

Cost Structure

The breakdown of the costs is as follows:

- Human resources: Salaries for staff involved in the management, maintenance, and community coordination of bike-sharing services.
- Material and infrastructure costs: Purchase and maintenance of refurbished bicycles and spare parts, as well as general infrastructure build costs. Partnering with waste collection or recycling companies can lower the costs associated with purchasing or refurbishing bicycle parts.
- Operational and administrative costs: Venue hire for workshops or events, warehousing, marketing, administrative and overheads, insurance, and permits.
- Training and event costs: Expenses for organising workshops and public events, and workshop supplies.
- Communication and media costs: Media documentation, marketing campaigns, and dissemination efforts. Promotion and user engagement campaigns.

Revenue Streams

Potential revenue can be generated through the implementation of tiered rental fees (monthly or six-month options) alongside usage-based charges. Different pricing tables apply at various times of the year. Initial and ongoing support can be secured through municipal budget allocations for urban development, public spaces, and social services.

Surplus

In the context of a social business model, any surplus generated by the bike-sharing service would be reinvested to increase its social impact and help it achieve its mission.

Social Impact Measurement

This impact strategy is structured around a Theory of Change, which articulates how the project's activities are expected to lead to the desired social impact. The Theory of Change suggests that encouraging active lifestyles through bike-sharing services will have a positive impact on people's Health and Wellbeing. On the other hand, promoting community involvement will foster a sense of belonging.

Table 20 - Key Impact Indicators (KIIs)

Short-term output	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term Outcomes (impacts)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in the modal share of cycling. • increase in the attendance at events. • increase in the influx of people and tourists in public spaces. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased inclusivity, accessibility, and safety. • Changes in space utilisation and mobility patterns among the general population. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • impact on mental health, socio-economic wellbeing, and healthy lifestyles.

Macro-Environment (PESTEL Analysis)

Political

- **EU Policy Framework:** The European Union provides dedicated support through initiatives such as the Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy, the New EU Urban Mobility Framework, and the European Declaration on Cycling. These initiatives explicitly recognise the importance of bike sharing for sustainable urban transport and “first and last mile” access to public transport (Cycling Industries Europe, 2024a).
- **Climate targets:** The EU's commitment to reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 and achieving climate neutrality by 2050 is driving investment in cycling and bike-sharing schemes.

- **Urban planning:** Cities are increasingly adopting Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP) and focusing on developing “15-minute cities” that prioritise active and shared mobility (World Economic Forum, 2021).

Economic

- **Cost of living/affordability:** high transport costs, particularly those associated with car ownership, have a disproportionate impact on low-income households. This creates a demand for affordable alternatives, which bike sharing, especially with refurbished bikes, can meet.

Social

- **Social Inclusion and Equity:** A key factor is the need to promote social inclusion by ensuring that all population groups, including those in low-income communities, people with disabilities, women, and the elderly, have equitable access to transport.
- **Community engagement:** There is a growing recognition of the need for community involvement in mobility planning, to ensure that solutions address local issues and cultural biases (World Economic Forum, 2021).

Technological:

- **Digital platforms:** Digital technologies are transforming transport by enabling real-time matching of supply and demand, dynamic pricing, and user-friendly interfaces.
- **Mobility as a Service (MaaS):** A key trend is the development of MaaS apps that integrate various transport modes, including bike sharing, to make multimodal journeys seamless for users.
- **Data Collection and Analysis:** Advanced data collection (e.g. GPS and real-time traffic data) and analysis are crucial for optimising fleet distribution, identifying issues and measuring performance.

Legal:

- **Regulatory Frameworks:** Cities are developing and adapting regulatory frameworks for bike-sharing schemes, including licensing agreements, data-sharing requirements and rules on fleet size and operations.
- **Competition law:** It is challenging to balance the need to encourage innovation and competition with preventing monopolies and ensuring fair practices for all market players.
- **Data protection:** Protecting user data collected by platforms is a significant legal concern, requiring the sharing of anonymised data where necessary (World Economic Forum, 2017).

Environmental

- **Decarbonisation:** Bike-sharing schemes provide a low-emission alternative to private vehicles, directly supporting the decarbonisation of urban transport.
- **Resource efficiency:** The sharing economy, including bike sharing, promotes a shift from individual ownership to shared access, thereby reducing overall resource consumption and waste.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Critical success factors (CSFs) are the essential conditions that must be met for a business model to be successfully implemented in a new context. Please find below a suggestion for the critical success factors and barriers to implementation. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to function as a starting point for further discussion.

Critical success factors

- Local ownership of solutions is essential for sustainability.
- Designing and customising solutions to be context-specific is paramount.
- Dedicated project management and coordination are necessary to oversee complex activities.
- An effective communication and dissemination strategy is essential for raising awareness and garnering public support.
- Strong collaboration and active involvement from stakeholders are crucial for success.

Barriers to Implementation

- Difficulties in engaging certain target groups, particularly marginalised communities.
- Resistance to mindset shifts within Urban communities.

Replication prerequisites

- **People:** The operational success of this low-cost mobility model hinges on trusted local leadership rather than automated surveillance. Strategically, this requires a community manager — typically a respected figure from a local cultural centre or NGO — who can oversee the system. Complementing this leadership are volunteer mechanics, ideally recruited from local youth or DIY enthusiasts.
- **Processes:** From a procedural perspective, the model is distinguished by its removal of financial barriers through a trust-based lending protocol. Unlike commercial schemes that rely on expensive automated docking stations and credit card guarantees, this low-barrier system uses community ownership to secure assets, making mobility accessible. This is operationally sustained by circular sourcing protocols, a supply chain strategy that establishes formal channels for acquiring and refurbishing abandoned or donated bicycles. This approach minimises capital expenditure (CAPEX), aligning urban mobility with the goals of the circular economy.
- **Other requisites:** Physically, the model requires a secure depot, such as a repurposed shipping container located within a safe community hub, is essential for storing and maintaining the fleet, protecting it from theft and the weather. However, the service's utility is intrinsically linked to the broader urban environment. Therefore, basic cycling infrastructure, specifically safe and connected cycle paths, is a non-negotiable prerequisite.

Strategy monitoring

Please find below a suggested strategy monitoring model. This is not an exhaustive list and is intended as a starting point for further discussion.

Table 21 - Strategy monitoring indicators (Key Performance Indicators)

<p>1) People dimension (Customer Perspective or Stakeholder Engagement)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To increase citizens' participation in the transformation of public spaces, with a particular focus on engaging disadvantaged groups. • To engage and influence key stakeholders, fostering a growing network of partners and supporters. • To encourage citizens in the pilot areas to take ownership of the solutions. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of stakeholders involved in implementation efforts. • Feedback from stakeholders (e.g. from surveys, focus groups or interviews). • Job creation and skills development within the local community are measured annually. 	<p>2) Processes dimension (Internal Processes & Service Provision)</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement and standardise key processes. • Ensure the quality of implemented services. • Set up robust monitoring and evaluation systems to ensure consistent data collection. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency of internal processes: • Number of integrated innovations. • Increases in the modal share of cycling. • The economic impact on local businesses near popular routes.
<p>3) Growth and Learning dimension</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop organisational capacity and team experience. • Foster innovation and continuous improvement of the business model based on experience. • Encourage the sharing of solutions and promote inter-city learning. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of knowledge-sharing events. 	<p>4) Financial dimension</p> <p>Strategic objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revenue generated • Maximising cost efficiency. • Ensure a positive return on investment (ROI). • Securing adequate funding for expansion and new implementations. <p>Strategy tracking metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of paying customers. • Total revenue generated by the bike-sharing service. • Revenue generated by area of activity or initiative.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Profitability (net profit margin) or ROI of investments. • The amount of external funding/grants guaranteed.
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MARKET ANALYSIS

Disclaimer: This is a market analysis developed for an IN-HABIT project. Some of the information may be outdated or inaccurate. If you wish to implement this idea, you should conduct specific market research tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Market overview

The bike-sharing industry is a world-leading example of a mobility transition in Europe. Bike sharing is recognised as a vital part of the transition to urban mobility in Europe, strongly supporting EU objectives relating to climate change, mobility, and active transport. The industry is characterised by public and private operators providing bicycles for short-term shared use. This analysis focuses on a community bike-sharing service that uses refurbished bikes. This specific offering aligns with the broader push for sustainable, affordable, and inclusive urban transport. This makes the service a cost-effective, environmentally friendly alternative to traditional bike-sharing models, which usually involve new fleets.

Key product segments include pedal bikes and electric bikes (e-bikes), with e-bikes becoming increasingly popular, particularly in hilly areas and large cities. Services are offered through both docked and dockless models, with private operators often favouring the latter.

The community bike-sharing service primarily targets pedal bikes and uses refurbished bikes to provide an affordable way to access shared mobility.

Market Size and Growth

Extending product lifespans and increasing usage intensity can reduce environmental impact. The growing popularity of bike-sharing in Europe, which saw a 4% increase in bikes per 1,000 citizens between 2016 and 2023, illustrates this efficiency boost²⁸.

According to the report “Quality of Life in European Cities 2023” (European Commission: Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy, 2023), cycling is only a relevant mode of transport in a few cities. On average, 14% of respondents use it as a mode of transport, and its use tends to decline with city size. -While around 16% of residents in cities with fewer than 250,000 inhabitants say they cycle on a typical day, this figure decreases to 14% in cities with between 1 and 5 million inhabitants. Only three cities report more than 35% of their residents using a bike on a typical day.

²⁸ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/circularity/sectoral-modules/product-lifespans/availability-of-bike-sharing-systems-in-european-cities-intensity-of-use>

A recent market analysis (Cycling Industries Europe, 2024b), informed by comprehensive benchmarking data from 148 EU cities reveals growth potential for bike sharing, particularly in cities not well served by existing schemes. While bike-sharing fleets are currently active in 122 of the 148 benchmarked cities, approximately 7.3 million citizens in these cities still lack access to any bike-sharing scheme.

For a bike-sharing scheme to have a significant impact, cities usually require a minimum of fifty bikes for every 10,000 inhabitants (Cycling Industries Europe, 2024a). There is currently a significant disparity in market performance: the best-performing city in the study (Paris) achieves almost thirty-seven trips per 1,000 inhabitants per day (Cycling Industries Europe, 2024a), while others fall far short. This indicates considerable untapped potential.

A community bike-sharing service using refurbished bikes would particularly appeal to low-income households, students and environmentally conscious individuals due to its affordability and sustainability. It would address an unmet demand for accessible, low-cost mobility solutions for groups who might otherwise rely on more expensive private transport or have limited options.

Competitive Landscape (Porter's Five Forces)

Rivalry among existing competitors: The bike-sharing market in Europe is characterised by intense competition. Many cities have multiple private operators as well as public schemes, which leads to competition for users and market share. In some cities, exclusive long-term contracts limit direct competition (Cycling Industries Europe, 2024b), but these contracts can also hinder innovation and adaptation. The presence of both docked and dockless systems adds another dimension to the competition, with dockless private services becoming increasingly popular.

The market includes established European bike share operators and service providers. Competitors utilize various operational models and bike types (Cycling Industries Europe, 2024):

- **Docked vs. dockless models:** While many cities operate a 100% docked fleet, the growing popularity of private, dockless services is evident, especially in larger cities such as Paris, where only 45% of the fleet is docked. Some schemes are “hybrid”, offering specific parking locations without physical docks.
- **Electric vs. mechanical bikes:** Although 78.64% of fleets comprise mechanical bikes and 21.36% comprise electric bikes, the latter make up 30.65% of all trips, indicating that they generate more rides. Top-performing cities have a mix ranging from 100% to 12% electrification.

Threat of New Entrants: Depending on the city's regulatory environment and market maturity, the threat of new entrants is moderate to high. While establishing a substantial fleet requires significant capital investment, cities are actively seeking innovative solutions and operators. However, exclusive contracts and the need for seamless integration with existing public transport systems can pose significant barriers. Furthermore, the requirement for data transparency and compliance with city regulations (e.g. licensing agreements) poses a challenge for smaller or less compliant new entrants.

Threat of substitute products or services:

- **Private bike ownership:** Elevated levels of private bike ownership can hinder the implementation of bike-sharing services.

- **Private cars:** Despite efforts to reduce car dependency, private vehicles remain the dominant mode of transport.
- **Other shared mobility:** Car and scooter sharing, e-scooters and mopeds compete for users, and their introduction has sometimes impacted bike-sharing ridership (e.g. Milan).
- **Public transport:** Buses, trams and metro systems are direct substitutes, though bike-sharing is increasingly being promoted as a “first and last mile” solution to complement them.
- **Walking:** Active mobility is encouraged, particularly in compact cities.

Bargaining power of buyers (customers): Customers have high bargaining power due to the numerous transport options available and the strong demand for affordability and convenience. Users expect attractive pricing models, such as free or discounted rides and subsidies. They also expect well-maintained bikes and user-friendly apps that simplify the booking and payment process. Customer feedback and usage patterns directly influence operators' strategies and city policies.

Bargaining power of suppliers (operators, manufacturers, data providers): There is some bargaining power of key suppliers, such as bike manufacturers. Leading European bike-share operators are well organised, which ensures they have a voice in EU policies and funding. Exclusive contracts with cities can give operators significant leverage. However, cities are increasingly demanding data transparency and performance indicators, which could shift some of this power back to the public sector. The bargaining power will be reduced if refurbished bicycles are used.

Barriers to Entry

Several challenges exist for new entrants or those competing in the bike-sharing market:

Capital Requirements: Launching a bike-sharing service requires a significant initial investment for purchasing fleets, setting up docking stations (if applicable), and developing technology platforms. Annual operating costs averaging €1,200 per bike also present a recurring financial commitment (Cycling Industries Europe, 2024a). These costs could be much smaller if refurbished bicycles were used.

Regulatory mapping: Navigating the complex regulatory landscape across different European cities poses a significant challenge. This includes adhering to city-specific licensing agreements and permits for fleet deployment (docked or dockless), as well as data sharing obligations and potentially local contractual incentives or disincentives. Some cities operate under exclusive long-term contracts (Cycling Industries Europe, 2024b), which effectively bars new entrants until the contract expires. The requirement to provide benchmarkable data for urban mobility frameworks also adds to the compliance burden.

Market Opportunities and Risks

Opportunities

- **Market Potential:** A small proportion of the urban population in Europe currently lacks access to bike-sharing services, indicating room for market expansion if sufficient fleets are deployed. In 2024, at least twenty-three cities had no bike-sharing services at all. A further three cities have a scheme that has not been given a fleet size due to uncertainty over whether the service is still running (Cycling

Industries Europe, 2024a). In the ten largest cities, 5.5 million people do not have access to bike sharing. A community-driven model could be a viable entry point for these areas, particularly focusing on affordability and accessibility for low-income and disabled populations. The refurbished bike model could address the unmet demand for lower-cost bike-sharing options, allowing for affordability and social inclusion in underserved communities. This approach is in line with cities' goals of making mobility accessible to unbanked, digitally illiterate, or low-income individuals (World Economic Forum, 2021).

- **Affordability Gap:** There is a clear demand for more affordable solutions to serve low-income communities and address transport poverty, a gap that refurbished pedal bikes can uniquely fill.

Risks

- **Operational Scale is Crucial:** To achieve meaningful impact, a sufficient fleet size is essential, and larger fleets may require public financial support to remain viable due to potentially lower per-bike utilisation.

Recommendations

- **Prioritise Affordability and Accessibility:** Design the service with a flexible and inclusive pricing model, potentially offering subsidised or free rides for target groups (e.g., public transport subscribers, low-income households, students). This will directly address the unmet demand for accessible mobility and enhance social inclusion.
- **Focus on Strategic Expansion:** Instead of attempting city-wide saturation initially, identify specific "mobility deserts" or underserved peripheral areas within target cities that currently lack adequate public transport and bike-sharing options. This phased approach can demonstrate impact and secure support.
- **Ensure Quality and User Experience:** Despite using refurbished bikes, prioritise well-maintained and modernised fleets to ensure reliability and user satisfaction.
- **Forge Strong Public-Private Partnerships:** Collaborate closely with city administrations, public transport authorities, and potentially other mobility providers to ensure regulatory compliance, integrate services, and secure essential public funding or cross-financing mechanisms.
- **Highlight Sustainability Differentiator:** Emphasise the environmental benefits of using refurbished bikes, promoting a circular economy model that resonates with growing ecological awareness and EU environmental objectives. This unique selling proposition can attract environmentally conscious users and differentiate the service from competitors.

10. B4B TAILORED INCLUSIVE BUSINESS TRAINING

Disclaimer: This is a business model based on the IN-HABIT project. If you would like to use it as inspiration for your own project, you should develop a specific business plan tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

B4B Tailored Inclusive Business Training

The "B4B Tailored Inclusive Business Training" is a hybrid entrepreneurship training program. The program has a main focus area on women in underprivileged areas including women from Las Palmeras (Córdoba, Spain), and the Roma community of women in Nitra, Slovakia. The programs are designed to target new start-up businesses and develop the entrepreneurial mindset and critical strategic components associated with new start-ups with little financial resources. B4B is primarily responsible for developing and implementing this program. Local universities, and local/national authorities were often used as partners to develop and implement the program. The program concludes at a Pitch Day event where participants will have an opportunity to showcase their product/service and learn how to effectively pitch to potential customers and local stakeholders. This program addresses both individual empowerment and the creation of a supporting community environment to promote long-term sustainable economic growth and self-sufficiency. Through a combination of individualized support, interactive learning, and practical assignments, the program provides participants with the necessary skills and confidence to successfully navigate the entrepreneurial landscape while overcoming common barriers including limited digital literacy and access to technology.

Key competitive advantages for the Bridge for Billions (B4B) Tailored Inclusive Business Training

- **Tailored and context-specific design:** The Programme is designed to reflect the local context and the varying levels of preparation among participants. It is particularly targeted at women in underserved communities, such as Las Palmeras in Córdoba, Spain, and Roma women (Slovakia).
- **Focus on Entrepreneurial Mindset and Holistic Development:** A key differentiator is its emphasis on developing an entrepreneurial mindset, including confidence, resilience and strategic thinking, rather than solely focusing on traditional business skills. The Programme combines personalised support, interactive learning and practical assignments to equip participants with the essential skills and confidence needed to navigate the entrepreneurial landscape.
- **Hybrid Learning Model for Accessibility:** This design is crucial for accommodating varying digital literacy levels and ensuring inclusivity, particularly for populations with limited access to technology or unfamiliarity with online learning environments.
- **Addressing Specific Barriers of Underserved Communities:** This Programme tackles key barriers such as limited digital literacy, lack of access to technology and economic constraints, which hinder participation in traditional entrepreneurship Programmes. This makes it particularly suitable for organisations that collaborate with underserved communities, including women in rural or disadvantaged urban areas, ethnic minorities, and individuals with limited access to traditional entrepreneurial education.

B4B Tailored Inclusive Business Training photos

Figure 27 – Tailored inclusive Business training sessions

Source: B4B photo database

To evaluate the Societal Readiness Level (SRL) and Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) of the KER and VIS with replication potential, the B4B Tailored inclusive Business training project team completed a self-assessment questionnaire. The results are presented in the images below.

Figure 28 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire for the B4B Tailored inclusive Business training SLR and TRL levels

The B4B Tailored inclusive Business training has a Societal Readiness Level (SRL) of six. This means that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders in order to gain initial feedback. This demonstration and feedback phase (SRL 6) is crucial for refining the Programme based on real-world interaction, emphasising its focus on societal application. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is zero. This indicates that the Programme is not developing a technological innovation itself; its focus is on societal application, independent of technological development. The B4B Tailored inclusive Business training demonstrates potential for replication. It is particularly suitable for organizations collaborating with underserved communities, women in rural or underserved urban areas, minorities, like Roma community and individuals with limited access to traditional entrepreneurial education.

Problem

Small and medium-sized cities, as well as peripheral urban areas across Europe, often face significant challenges in promoting economic development and social inclusion for disadvantaged populations. Marginalised communities encounter unique barriers to entrepreneurship and economic self-sufficiency. These include limited access to education, digital tools, and entrepreneurial networks, exacerbated by systemic socioeconomic constraints that hinder their full participation in the local economy. Grassroots entrepreneurs, operating in "extreme niches," frequently lack access to financial, human, or infrastructural resources. Moreover, these cities often lack tailored training Programmes that address the specific needs of their diverse populations. Generic entrepreneurship initiatives fail to account for complexities such as limited resources, varying levels of preparedness, and cultural nuances, leaving many potential entrepreneurs without the tools to succeed. This gap is particularly pronounced for women in underserved communities, who often face additional challenges like balancing caregiving responsibilities, overcoming social stigma, and navigating digital exclusion. Key challenges include limited digital literacy, lack of access to essential technology (e.g., laptops or tablets), and unfamiliarity with online learning environments, all of which impede effective engagement with comprehensive business development curricula. Locally specific legal barriers to formalising business activities and significant financial constraints further limit participation in formal training.

Value Proposition

The Training 's core value proposition lies in its tailored hybrid entrepreneurship Programme, which uniquely combines personalised support with an interactive learning model. This approach empowers women from underserved communities to overcome barriers such as digital literacy while fostering creativity and practical skills through direct experiences. It places distinct emphasis on developing an entrepreneurial mindset, building confidence, resilience, and strategic thinking, enabling participants to launch their ventures confidently and engage with potential customers. Unlike traditional, one-size-fits-all entrepreneurship training solutions, this Training adapts content to reflect local contexts and specific barriers, ensuring solutions are practical and effective for each unique community.

The innovative model prioritises inclusivity, providing entrepreneurship opportunities to those who typically lack access. The Training fosters a strong community of support, promoting sustainable change and empowering participants to tackle economic and personal challenges creatively.

Key characteristics:

- **Modular and adaptable design:** The training can easily be adapted to fit each location's realities, language and digital skills level due to the modular structure. This will allow for the adaptation of all of the training's content to fit the specific reality and preparedness of participants.
- **Hybrid model:** The hybrid model combines in-class training with online training which can assist organizations like NGOs, municipalities and employment services who are looking to increase social inclusion, gender equality and/or local economic development.
- **Entrepreneurial mindset:** An important differentiator from other similar trainings is the focus on building an entrepreneurial mindset (entrepreneurial confidence, ability to think strategically and ability to be resilient) versus just providing business skills to create sustainable positive change over time.
- **Partnerships:** B4B partners with local organizations, NGOs and educational institutions to share resources and help improve delivery of the program and expand the reach of the program while providing a support system for participants.
- **Supporting EU priorities:** The training supports the EU priorities of increasing digital inclusion; supporting women entrepreneurs; and community led innovation.
- **Fostering Entrepreneurship and Job Creation:** The training aims to foster entrepreneurship leading to job creation and sustainable economic exploitation of re-designed urban spaces,

Customer Segments (Beneficiaries/Users)

The Programme serves two primary customer segments:

- **Beneficiaries (Target Group):** Individuals from **disadvantaged communities, with a focus on women from minority groups who face socioeconomic challenges and have a business idea.** They often face significant barriers, including limited digital literacy, lack of technology access, and economic constraints. Their primary goals are achieving economic independence, improving quality of life, and contributing to their communities through successful entrepreneurship, alongside building confidence and new skills. They require tailored training, financial support, practical experience, ongoing mentorship, a dedicated support network, and community-building opportunities.
- **Customers:** These are the organisations and entities that will adopt or use the Training's methodology to deliver it to the ultimate beneficiaries. This includes **municipalities** (local government bodies focused on economic development and social inclusion), **universities** (academic institutions for educational Programmes and research), **private and public sector organisations** such as non-governmental organisations (NGOs), educational companies, and startup incubators, **government agencies** focused on economic empowerment, **local or regional business development agencies and chambers of commerce, international NGOs and foundations, and women's empowerment groups.** These customers aim to stimulate economic growth, create employment, promote inclusion and

diversity, fulfil social responsibility goals, and foster long-term economic stability. They require dependable, scalable, and evidence-based training Programmes with demonstrated impact, clear metrics and reports, and opportunities for positive brand alignment.

Channels

The Training delivers its social value proposition to beneficiaries and customers through a combination of channels:

- **For Beneficiaries:** These include **community partnerships** and **local partner organisations**. Delivery occurs through **workshops and events, direct delivery, in-person training sessions, and peer-to-peer support networks**. The hybrid model, combining online and in-person elements, is crucial for accommodating varying digital literacy levels and ensuring inclusivity.
- **For Customers:** Channels include **community partnerships, local partner organisations, workshops and events, and direct delivery**. Collaborations with local organisations, NGOs, and educational institutions expand reach and create a robust support network.

Customer Relations

Relationships are built and maintained through specific mechanisms for each stakeholder group:

- **Beneficiaries:** Emphasis is placed on **skill development** through practical, tailored entrepreneurial training that builds both business and life skills, such as confidence, resilience, and financial literacy. **Personalised support** is provided through mentorship, ongoing guidance, and resources specific to participants' goals. **Community building** is fostered by creating a supportive network among participants, encouraging collaboration and peer learning beyond the Training. **Accessible learning** is ensured via a hybrid model that accommodates varying digital literacy levels.
- **Customers:** Relationships are maintained by enabling partner organisations to demonstrate **enhanced community engagement** through measurable participant success and social inclusion outcomes. The Training contributes to **workforce development** by preparing skilled entrepreneurs who contribute to local economies. The provision of a **replicable model** allows partners to adopt and extend the Training's impact within their own networks.
- **Funding Stakeholders:** Relationships are solidified through **social impact reporting**, which regularly measures and shares metrics like participant income growth and business launches, demonstrating tangible outcomes. The Training's **scalability and replicability** potential, adaptable to various communities, highlights a sustainable and impactful solution. Offering opportunities for **positive branding and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) alignment** enhances funders' brand image and Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives.

Key Activities

The critical activities for achieving the social mission include:

- **Needs Assessment and Community Engagement:** Conducting comprehensive needs assessments to understand local conditions, participant readiness, and specific barriers like digital literacy or financial constraints.
- **Customised Curriculum Design:** Developing tailored hybrid entrepreneurship trainings with content optimised for the local context and varying participant preparedness levels. This includes designing interactive sessions, homework assignments, and progressive learning trajectories.
 - **Partner and Stakeholder Collaboration:** Actively collaborating with local organisations, NGOs, educational institutions, and authorities for resource sharing, enhanced delivery, and policy influence.
- **Outreach and Recruitment:** Identifying target communities and recruiting participants from underserved backgrounds.
- **Delivering Training and Mentorship:** Providing workshops, training sessions, and personalised support focusing on entrepreneurial mindset, business strategy, resource management, marketing, sales, and pitching skills.
- **Monitoring and Feedback Collection:** Collecting feedback from pilots and evaluating initial impact to refine and scale the Programme.
- **Building a Supportive Community:** Fostering collaboration, peer learning, and a long-term sense of community among participants.
- **Impact Measurement and Reporting:** Regularly measuring and reporting on social impact using quantitative and qualitative KPIs before, during and after the program.
- **Post-Programme Support and Follow-Up:** Connecting participants to local ecosystems and providing ongoing mentorship to support sustainability.

Key Resources

Successful delivery of the Training requires various key resources:

- **Human Resources:** Includes community outreach and engagement specialists, and crucial **trainers and mentors** or coordinators.
- **Technological Resources:** Essential communication tools (e.g., WhatsApp groups, video calls, voice notes) and a data management system are used to ensure engagement. While the Training is not a technological innovation, basic digital access remains a critical success factor for its hybrid model. Where participants lack access to devices, partnerships could be established to provide computers or tablets.
- **Financial Resources:** Securing funding for Training operations is essential and can be achieved by leveraging local partners from both the public and private sectors.
- **Educational and Training Materials:** A customised curriculum and practical business toolkits, including proprietary training frameworks and new materials created during the project.

- **Partnerships and Community Resources:** Collaborative partnerships with NGOs, municipalities, and community spaces. A network of potential customers and investors for participants is also vital.
- **Marketing and Outreach Resources:** Branding and promotional materials, and an alumni network to leverage.
- **Evaluation and Feedback Tools:** Impact measurement frameworks and feedback mechanisms for continuous improvement.

Key Partners

Key delivery partners essential for the Training's success include:

- **Local NGOs and Community Organisations:** These groups often work directly with underserved populations and are crucial for community access, outreach, recruitment, and Training promotion.
- **Educational Institutions (Universities, Community Colleges, Vocational Schools):** These groups play a vital role in co-management, providing on-site support, and leveraging expertise in innovation and research.
- **Government Agencies and Local Authorities (Municipalities, Employment Offices, Rural Development Agencies):** Instrumental for providing political and funding support, policy recommendations, and facilitating permits.
- **Private Sector Companies:** Potential funders aligning with Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives.
- **Microfinance Institutions and Banks:** To provide financial support or access to grants and funding opportunities for beneficiaries.
- **Business Mentorship Networks and Social Entrepreneurs:** To offer ongoing mentorship and a dedicated support network to participants.

Cooperation and Competition

Cooperation refers to the dynamic where organisations collaborate on specific initiatives while remaining competitors in other aspects of their work. The Inclusive Business Training engages in cooperation with organisations that share its mission of social impact and inclusion but compete for funding, participants, or influence in the entrepreneurship training space. This dual relationship allows for potential partnerships, such as co-hosting events or sharing resources, while maintaining distinct Training identities.

Main Competitors in Europe

The Inclusive Business Training faces competition from several prominent organisations and categories of providers in Europe, each offering entrepreneurship training or support for underserved populations. Examples of key competitors include:

- **Ashoka Europe:** Ashoka is a global leader in social entrepreneurship, supporting social innovators through fellowships and training Programmes. In Europe, Ashoka runs initiatives like the *Women's Social Entrepreneurship Programme*, which empowers women to develop social enterprises.

- **Impact Hub Network:** With hubs across Europe (e.g., in Lisbon, Vienna, and Amsterdam), Impact Hub offers incubation, acceleration, and training Programmes for social entrepreneurs. Their Inclusive Entrepreneurship initiatives target marginalised groups, including women and migrants.
- **Acumen Academy Europe:** Acumen Academy provides online and in-person courses on social entrepreneurship, with a focus on leadership and impact-driven business models. Its Social Impact Accelerator supports entrepreneurs, including women, in underserved regions.

Broader Competition

In addition to these specific organisations, the B4B Tailored inclusive Business training competes with several broader categories of providers:

- **Traditional Entrepreneurship Training Programmes and skills development trainings:** Offered by universities, community colleges, and NGOs across Europe, these Programmes provide general business education. They often lack tailored approaches for underserved populations, such as women in marginalised communities, and may not address barriers like limited digital literacy or caregiving responsibilities.
- **Online Learning Platforms:** Platforms like Coursera, Udemy, and FutureLearn offer low-cost or free entrepreneurship courses, accessible across Europe. However, these courses are typically designed for a broad audience and lack the personalised support, community engagement, and contextual adaptation needed for disadvantaged groups.
- **Incubators and Accelerators:** Organisations like EIT Climate-KIC, Social Innovation Academy, and regional accelerators provide startup incubation and acceleration Programmes. These often have stringent entry criteria, targeting entrepreneurs with established ideas or technical skills, which can exclude underserved populations.
- **Local Business Development Agencies:** Agencies such as chambers of commerce or regional development boards offer resources and support for small businesses. While valuable, these services often lack personalised guidance or a specific focus on underserved groups.

Coopetition Opportunities

The B4B Tailored inclusive Business training can leverage coopetition by partnering with competitors on shared goals, such as advocating for inclusive entrepreneurship policies or co-hosting workshops.

Cost Structure

Key cost areas include human resources (trainers, mentors, outreach specialists), technological resources (communication tools, data management), educational materials, community space rental, marketing, and evaluation tools.

This cost structure provides a general picture of expected expenses, but actual costs could vary based on Programme scale, location, and the extent of in-person events versus online components. Additional funding may be needed as the Programme scales or if new communities are added.

Revenue Streams

Some potential revenue sources are:

- **Product/Service Sales:** Direct provision of the training Programme services to customers (organisations, governments).
- **Grants:** Grants are available from a variety of sources, including EU social funds, grants for women’s empowerment and national start-up incentives.
- **Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Donations.**

Surplus

As a cornerstone goal of social business, any surplus is reinvested back into the community, either to expand Programme reach or enhance services for beneficiaries.

Social Impact Measurement

The B4B Tailored Inclusive Business Training Programme uses a comprehensive strategy for social impact measurement, aligning with its social mission through short-term outputs, medium-term outcomes, and long-term impact.

Table 22 - Key Impact Indicators (KIs)

Short-term output	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term Outcomes (impacts)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training Completion: Percentage of participants completing the full Programme. • Skill Development: Measurable improvements in key entrepreneurial skills (e.g., confidence, resilience, financial literacy) assessed through pre- and post-Programme evaluations. • Networking Growth: Increase in participants’ connections within their communities and access to support networks. • Number of Participants Enrolled: Total number of individuals starting the Programme. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Readiness and Launches: Number of participants who develop and launch viable business ideas. • Community Engagement and Collaboration: Number of partnerships and collaborations initiated by participants within their local community. • Business Projects Developed: Number of participants who submit a business idea or plan. • Jobs Created: Number of new jobs generated by participants’ businesses, including both self- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systemic Change: Evidence of policy or local support changes driven by Programme insights and data, helping to remove barriers for disadvantaged entrepreneurs and foster an inclusive business environment. • Economic Mobility and Financial Independence: Increase in participants’ financial independence and upward economic mobility over multiple years. • Business survival rate: The proportion of businesses started up in a given year that are still operating after n years.

Short-term output	Medium-term outcomes	Long-term Outcomes (impacts)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mentorship Hours Provided: Number of hours of personalised support offered during the Programme. ● Digital Engagement: Frequency of digital platform use (logins, task submissions). ● Participant Satisfaction Score: Based on post-Programme surveys. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● employment and additional hires. ● Sustainable Income: Percentage of participants who generate income from their business ventures within six months to a year of completing the Programme. ● Replication Instances: Number of times the Programme is adopted by other EU organisations. ● Increased self-confidence, shift in entrepreneurial mindset, community engagement, relevance of training content, perceived empowerment, improved digital literacy, and social cohesion impact. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inclusive Economic Growth: Contribution of new businesses to the local economy, as reflected in local employment, income levels, and business activity. ● Community-Led Entrepreneurship: Creation of a self-sustaining ecosystem with Programme alumni mentor and support new cohorts, reinforcing a cycle of inclusive entrepreneurship

Macro-Environment (PESTEL Analysis)

Political: EU political guidelines, mission letters, and the EU competitiveness compass frame investment policies for start-ups. However, Europe's inherent fragmentation — comprising 24 languages, 27 legal frameworks and nine currencies — continues to impede single market operations. To be effective, policy interventions must be meticulously tailored to specific national and regional contexts, and many EU Member States have already developed strategies for women, and unemployed entrepreneurs.

Economic: Broader macroeconomic factors such as inflation and interest rates continue to affect the economic conditions of entrepreneurs across Europe.

Social: A prevalent “culture” of extreme caution towards risk-taking poses a significant social challenge. While shifting this mindset will take time, concrete actions can be taken to foster private investment. Gender disparities remain a significant issue, with women being underrepresented and facing specific barriers, often requiring tailored training (GEM (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor), 2023b). The unequal access to resources experienced by women is explicitly highlighted as an anomaly that governments should no longer tolerate. Supporting the integration of migrants and refugees as entrepreneurs is an evolving policy focus. A notable trend is the increasing number of entrepreneurs who are motivated to “make a difference”, with many prioritising social and environmental sustainability over profits (GEM Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2025b).

Technological: The growing reliance on digital marketing tools, such as social media, email communication, and websites, among new entrepreneurs highlights the importance of digital literacy and relevant training. The growing prevalence of online learning formats offers greater flexibility and reduces geographical and time-related barriers for entrepreneurs. However, digital skill gaps among certain groups must be addressed to ensure equitable access.

Legal factors: Europe's fragmented legal landscape, comprising 27 distinct frameworks, poses a significant challenge to the creation of a cohesive single market for entrepreneurship.

Environmental factors: Europe is establishing itself as a hub for climate and green technology start-ups. The Horizon Europe Programme allocates substantial funding towards climate action, demonstrating political commitment to environmental sustainability. An increasing number of entrepreneurs are integrating sustainability into their strategic thinking, prioritising social and environmental impacts over pure profitability. This creates a demand for incubation Programmes that support “impact startups” and align with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Integrating digital technologies can further enhance collaboration towards these sustainability goals (SDG 17).

Critical Success Factors and Barriers to Implementation

Please find below a suggestion for the critical success factors and barriers to implementation. This list is not exhaustive and is intended to function as a starting point for further discussion.

Critical Success Factors

- **Strong Local Partners:** Local implementing organisations (e.g., NGOs, municipalities) must have trusted community access, especially for underserved groups.
- **Capacity to Adapt Content:** The Programme's success depends on the ability to localise content for language, examples, and relevance to the local economy.
- **Facilitator Training and Support:** Trained facilitators who understand both entrepreneurship and community-based support are essential.
- **Digital Accessibility Infrastructure:** A blended (hybrid) model relies on basic community access to smartphones or community centres with internet.
- **Ongoing Mentorship and Follow-Up:** Success is higher when participants receive continuous personal support beyond formal sessions.
- **Political and Funding Support:** Engagement from local authorities and access to funding sources (EU/local grants) significantly boosts sustainability and reach.
- **Community Engagement and Co-Design:** Involving community leaders and beneficiaries in Programme design ensures buy-in and relevance.

Barriers to Implementation

- **Digital Divide:** In some regions, limited digital literacy, lack of devices, or internet access can hinder even hybrid models, requiring additional tech support.

- **Cultural and Gender Barriers:** Resistance to women’s economic activity in some communities necessitates a highly culturally sensitive approach.
- **Low Local Organisational Capacity:** The absence of strong local partners makes implementation challenging, as trust-building is a long-term investment.
- **Resource Scarcity:** General lack of funding, infrastructure, or technical expertise limits growth and long-term sustainability.

Replication prerequisites

- **People:** The successful replication of the B4B Tailored inclusive Business training relies on community activators: trusted local figures who leverage their social capital to recruit participants from disadvantaged groups (e.g. Roma women or residents of deprived areas) and bridge the trust gap with institutions. This outreach work is supported by facilitators who can translate complex business concepts into local languages and adapt their teaching methods to suit different literacy levels. Crucially, the model also incorporates local mentors, who are volunteer business experts providing one-to-one guidance to ensure that participants receive the personalised motivation and professional validation necessary to persist in their entrepreneurial journey.
- **Processes:** From a procedural perspective, the training employs an inclusive recruitment strategy that bypasses traditional channels, using grassroots networks to identify high-potential individuals who would usually self-select out of standard innovation hubs. Operationally, the programme mandates a hybrid delivery model, combining online modules with compulsory in-person workshops to prevent digital fatigue and foster peer support networks. This is reinforced by adapted materials that are linguistically and culturally tailored, as well as a micro-granting mechanism featuring simplified administrative procedures to provide critical early-stage financial aid.
- **Other requisites:** Technically, the model requires specific infrastructure to address the digital divide, which often excludes the intended beneficiaries. A fundamental requirement is digital access infrastructure, ensuring the availability of tablets, laptops or community computer labs for participants lacking personal devices. Furthermore, the deployment of translated curricula is non-negotiable: training materials must be fully localised in terms of both language and cultural references, to ensure relevance and uptake within the specific local context.

Strategy Monitoring

Please find below a suggestion for a strategy monitoring model. This is a *non-exhaustive* list and is intended to be a starting point for further discussion.

Table 23 - Strategy monitoring indicators (Key Performance Indicators)

<p>1. People Dimension (Stakeholder Engagement) Strategic Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To empower people from underserved communities by enhancing their confidence and cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset. 	<p>2. Processes Dimension (Internal Processes & Service Provision) Strategic Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To deliver a hybrid entrepreneurship Programme that is accessible and culturally sensitive.
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To build a strong, supportive community among beneficiaries, encouraging collaboration and peer learning beyond the Programme’s duration. ● To increase participant engagement and provide personalised support that addresses individual barriers. <p>Strategy Tracking Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of participants enrolled ● Participant satisfaction score. Measured through post-Programme surveys. ● Increased self-confidence: Measured through pre- and post-Programme surveys and interviews. ● Perceived empowerment: Assessed via in-depth interviews. ● Community engagement: Level of participant involvement in local initiatives or peer support networks, evaluated through focus groups and testimonials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To customise training content to reflect local contexts and accommodate varying levels of participant preparedness, including those with limited digital literacy. ● To provide effective mentorship and guidance throughout the incubation Programme. <p>Strategy Tracking Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Completion rate: Percentage of participants completing the full Programme. ● Digital engagement: Frequency of digital platform use (e.g., logins, task submissions), target weekly activity. ● Relevance of training content: Perceived usefulness and cultural/local relevance, measured by feedback surveys and co-design feedback. ● Mentorship hours provided: Number of hours of personalised support offered. ● Improved digital literacy: Evaluated through observation and baseline vs. endline comparisons.
<p>3. Growth and Learning Dimension</p> <p>Strategic Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To foster a shift in entrepreneurial mindset beyond mere business skills, promoting long-term sustainable change. ● To encourage the development of viable business ideas and micro-businesses by participants. ● To ensure the Programme’s potential for replication and adaptability by other EU organisations. ● To promote community-led entrepreneurship by establishing a self-sustaining ecosystem in which alumni mentor new groups of entrepreneurs. <p>Strategy Tracking Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Business projects developed: Number of participants submitting a business idea or plan, target. 	<p>4. Financial Dimension</p> <p>Strategic Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To foster entrepreneurship leading to job creation and sustainable economic exploitation of re-designed urban spaces. ● To facilitate economic mobility and financial independence for beneficiaries. ● To leverage partnerships and external funding to ensure Programme sustainability and scalability. <p>Strategy Tracking Metrics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of persons employed due to the program. ● Employment/self-employment outcomes: Percentage gaining income within 6 months post-Programme. ● Number of new (social) businesses and survival rate of business launched.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Micro-businesses launched: Number of ventures created within 6 months post-Programme. ● Shift in entrepreneurial mindset: Evidence of critical thinking, initiative, and resilience, measured by facilitator assessments and participant journaling. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Revenue streams: Tracking income from product/service sales, grants, and donations. ● Costs: Estimated overall and main costs for Programme delivery, varying by scale and location.
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MARKET ANALYSIS

Disclaimer: Disclaimer: This is a market analysis developed for an IN-HABIT project. Some of the information may be outdated or inaccurate. If you wish to implement this idea, you should conduct specific market research tailored to your context, challenges, and target groups.

Market Overview

The market’s scope includes inclusive entrepreneurship incubation Programmes across Europe that specifically target the “missing entrepreneurs” (OECD/European Commission, 2023a) who are currently underrepresented in business creation. These groups include women, migrants, young people, older people, the unemployed and disabled people. Such Programmes fall under the business support services industry and the broader entrepreneurship ecosystem. Core offerings include comprehensive incubation and acceleration support, such as tailored training, coaching, personal development for entrepreneurs, mentorship, access to financing, networking opportunities, business advice, and administrative assistance (OECD/European Commission, 2023a).

Market Description

The geographical scope of the incubation Programme is defined by Europe, with a particular focus on its diverse urban regions, where entrepreneurial activity tends to be concentrated (GEM (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor), 2023a). There are significant regional differences within European countries, with some areas exhibiting higher levels of entrepreneurial activity that are often centred around dominant urban agglomerations (GEM (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor), 2023a). The sector is dynamic, with growing recognition of entrepreneurship as a key driver of innovation, job creation, and economic progress. There is an increasing emphasis on its contribution to overall societal well-being and the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Inclusive entrepreneurship policies aim to unlock entrepreneurial talent from all backgrounds, thereby contributing to more inclusive and sustainable growth.

Entrepreneurship training can be delivered in various formats to serve different purposes. Traditionally, training schemes for inclusive and social entrepreneurship have been delivered through one-to-many formats, such as classroom training courses, workshops, masterclasses, and boot camps, where an expert trainer delivers courses to a group of students. However, training can also be delivered online or in one-to-one formats, such as coaching, mentoring and business consultancy, or through peer learning. All formats aim to help participants develop practical skills that can be applied when starting and managing

their business. The choice of format depends on various factors, including the training objective (e.g. developing financial plans or identifying business models that facilitate social impact), the entrepreneurs being targeted (training formats are not equally effective for all entrepreneurs) and budget constraints (S. A. and I. and O. for E. C. and D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2023a).

In 2023, a total of 71.9 million people were at risk of poverty. Of these, 5.5 million were also experiencing severe material and social deprivation and living in a household with very low work intensity. (European Commission, 2024b).

Equivalised disposable income is the total net income of a household divided by the weighted number of household members (based on their number and age). This level of income is expressed in purchasing power standards (PPS), a unit that takes account of differences in prices between countries. The median equivalised income of a population is the income level at which half of the population has a higher income and half has a lower income. In 2023, the median annual disposable income in the EU was 19,955 PPS per inhabitant. This figure varied considerably across EU countries, with western and Nordic countries reporting the highest levels, and southern, eastern, and Baltic countries reporting the lowest (European Commission, 2024b).

Market Size and Growth

The market for inclusive entrepreneurship incubation programmes in Europe has substantial growth potential, primarily driven by the significant number of “missing entrepreneurs” (OECD/European Commission, 2023b). There are distinct growth opportunities within specific segments of the “missing entrepreneurs” category.

- **Women:** There is a persistent gender gap in early-stage entrepreneurship across the EU, with women participating at lower rates than men (e.g. 6% versus 9% in the EU from 2018 to 2022) (OECD/European Commission, 2023a). Established business ownership among women is half that of men (OECD/European Commission, 2023a). Addressing this disparity alone represents a substantial market segment. Women entrepreneurs are often underrepresented, particularly in high-growth sectors such as information and communication technology (ICT) (GEM (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor), 2023b). They are more frequently driven by necessity than opportunity and are less likely than men to anticipate high employment growth in their ventures (OECD/European Commission, 2023b). They tend to report lower levels of financial literacy and express a need for training in soft skills such as leadership and self-confidence, as well as hard skills including computer science, legal and accounting competencies (S. A. and I. and O. for E. C. and D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2023a).
- **Youth (18–30 years old):** Although they are generally more active in early-stage entrepreneurship than older age groups, young people still represent a “missing” group within the overall entrepreneurial landscape (OECD/European Commission, 2023a). Programmes targeting young people can leverage their familiarity with digital tools and aspirational business models.
- **Seniors (50–64 years old):** This demographic accounts for a significant proportion of “missing” entrepreneurs, alongside women (OECD/European Commission, 2023a), Programmes tailored to their needs could unlock their valuable experience and capital.

- **People with migrant backgrounds:** These groups are underrepresented in entrepreneurship. Recent trends, such as the number of Ukrainian individuals starting businesses in Estonia almost tripling between 2021 and 2022, demonstrate the immediate need for inclusive Programmes in this area (OECD/European Commission, 2023a). They may be unfamiliar with the local regulatory landscape, so they need more support to understand legal obligations such as licensing and taxation (S. A. and I. O. for E. C. and D. and H. D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2019). These entrepreneurs often initially limit their market scope to their own communities and require assistance to expand into broader markets (S. A. and I. and O. for E. C. and D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2023b).
- **People with disabilities:** Despite representing about 23% of the self-employed entrepreneurs with disabilities in the EU, policies, and Programmes for the “missing” group are underdeveloped.
- **The unemployed:** This group is a primary target for inclusive entrepreneurship policies and is frequently motivated by “job scarcity” (necessity entrepreneurship) rather than opportunity (S. A. and I. and O. for E. C. and D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2023b). A subgroup of the unemployed are young people who are not in employment, education, or training (NEET). This term is used to describe the situation of many young people aged 15–29 in Europe.

A common psychographic trait across these groups is the presence of untapped entrepreneurial potential, which is often hindered by structural obstacles. Interestingly, many new entrepreneurs are strongly motivated to “make a difference” and prioritise social and environmental sustainability over profits (GEM (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor), 2025a). This growing commitment to sustainability provides an ideal opportunity for the implementation of such Programmes.

Competitive Landscape (Porter’s Five Forces)

Assessing the competitive landscape using Porter's Five Forces model reveals the dynamics of the inclusive entrepreneurship incubation market in Europe.

Rivalry among existing competitors: The market already features numerous business incubators and accelerators across Europe, with some offering specialised support for specific target groups. Although public funding initiatives and Programmes are in place, they are often insufficient (ESNA, 2025).

Bargaining power of buyers (entrepreneurs): Entrepreneurs, as the direct recipients of incubation services, possess significant bargaining power due to the range of options available to them. They demand support packages that are tailored, flexible and integrated, and which address their unique challenges (S. A. and I. and O. for E. C. and D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2023b). Key preferences include robust networking opportunities, personalised coaching, and effective mentorship. Access to finance and assistance with navigating administrative obligations are also highly valued (S. A. and I. and O. for E. C. and D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2023b).

Bargaining power of suppliers (service providers): Suppliers to incubation Programmes primarily include trainers, mentors, consultants, financial institutions, and infrastructure providers. The quality and experience of trainers and mentors is paramount, particularly for those with expertise in supporting diverse groups (S. A. and I. and O. for E. C. and D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2023b). Successful incubators are adept at fostering strategic networks, which relies on

strong relationships with a broad base of suppliers and partners (S. A. and I. and O. for E. C. and D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2023b).

Threat of New Entrants: While governments and non-profit organisations can launch new initiatives to support entrepreneurship, establishing a truly effective and impactful incubation Programme requires considerable time, consistent data collection, and the overcoming of the inherent fragmentation within the European entrepreneurial ecosystem (OECD/European Commission, 2023a). Existing players benefit from established networks, funding channels, and accumulated experience, creating a moderate barrier to entry for newcomers.

Threat of substitute products or services: General business support services, management consultancies, online courses, and informal networks can serve as substitutes for formal incubation Programmes (S. A. and I. and O. for E. C. and D. European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, 2023a). However, the growing recognition that a “one-size-fits-all” approach is less effective, particularly for underrepresented groups, suggests that generic substitutes may not meet the nuanced needs of inclusive entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs can also choose to self-fund (“bootstrap”) or rely on support from friends and family, which reduces their immediate need for funding.

Barriers to entry

Several significant barriers hinder the entry of inclusive entrepreneurship incubation Programmes into the European market and their subsequent success:

- **Adoption by entrepreneurs:** Some incubation programmes do not allow for a flexible approach and are expensive (either a fee is payable, or equity is required from the entrepreneur), which creates an additional accessibility barrier. Also, incubation Programmes tend to target more privileged entrepreneurs, and the limited number of inspirational success stories from underserved entrepreneurs further hinders their representation in these Programmes/initiatives.
- **Regulatory burdens and fragmentation:** The existence of 27 distinct legal frameworks, 24 languages and nine currencies across Europe creates a highly complex operational environment that impedes the efficiency and scalability of Programmes aiming for a single market approach (ESNA, 2025).
- **Prevailing risk aversion:** The deeply ingrained “culture of extreme caution towards risk-taking” among European company leaders poses a significant obstacle to cultivating a dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystem and attracting private investment. Overcoming this cultural inertia requires long-term strategic interventions.
- **Administrative complexity:** New businesses often encounter significant bureaucracy, which affects their ability to start up and operate smoothly.
- **Perceived ease of starting a business varies significantly across European countries.** The perceived ease of starting a business varies significantly across European countries, reflecting heterogeneous national entrepreneurial environments.
- **Lack of tailored support:** Generic, “one-size-fits-all” incubation Programmes are largely ineffective for diverse groups as they fail to address specific, nuanced challenges.

- **Cost modelling:** Positive outcomes can be achieved with relatively modest funding. However, public funding often requires robust monitoring and evaluation practices.

Market Opportunities and Risks

The market for inclusive entrepreneurship incubation Programmes in Europe offers significant opportunities alongside notable risks.

Market opportunities

- **Untapped potential:** The most significant opportunity lies in the estimated 7.5 million “missing” early-stage entrepreneurs in the EU, representing a large unaddressed market segment across all targeted groups (OECD/European Commission, 2023a) and migrant entrepreneurs who are often in the grey economy.
- **Alignment with sustainability and impact:** An increasing number of entrepreneurs are motivated by “making a difference” and prioritise social and environmental sustainability over profits. Europe’s position as a hub for climate and green tech start-ups further strengthens the market for “impact start-ups.”
- **Leveraging digitalisation and AI:** the growing use of digital tools by women and younger entrepreneurs, coupled with a greater awareness of the importance of AI, creates demand for Programmes integrating digital marketing and AI solutions and offering online learning opportunities.
- **Driving inclusive growth and social cohesion:** Supporting underrepresented groups directly contributes to social equality, improved health and education services, and a higher quality of life for all, thereby aligning with key UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 5, 8, 10 and 17).
- **High demand for tailored support:** The realisation that generic support models are ineffective has created a clear demand for Programmes offering highly specific training, mentorship and networking opportunities tailored to the unique needs of diverse entrepreneurial groups.
- **Community building:** Incubators play a vital role in fostering entrepreneurial communities and networks, which are particularly beneficial for underrepresented groups who often lack established connections.

Risks

- **Persistent funding shortfalls:** Despite potential policy changes, the actual inflow of capital to start-ups may remain insufficient, hindering the growth of incubated ventures.
- **Challenges in policy implementation:** European fragmentation and varying national priorities can complicate the effective, harmonised implementation of inclusive entrepreneurship policies, potentially reducing their impact.
- **Lack of robust evaluation:** The general lack of robust monitoring and evaluation of inclusive entrepreneurship schemes makes it difficult to prove their effectiveness, secure long-term funding and identify areas for improvement.

Recommendations

Design and deliver tailored, integrated support.

- Conduct comprehensive needs assessments (*ex-ante* and *ex-post* evaluations) and stakeholder consultations with the target groups themselves (e.g. women's business associations and refugee support networks) to identify specific skill gaps and challenges precisely.
- Develop training content that is specifically tailored to the unique needs of each “missing entrepreneur” group. For instance, provide fundamental business management and regulatory guidance to young people and migrants/refugees; enhanced digital literacy and innovative business concept development to seniors; and targeted support to women in male-dominated, high-growth sectors.
- Implement integrated support packages that address multiple interrelated barriers holistically (e.g. combining training with access to finance, mentorship, and legal advice).
- Prioritise pre-incubation support to help potential entrepreneurs refine their business ideas and develop robust business plans. This is particularly important given the diverse profiles of inclusive entrepreneurs.

Foster robust networks and community building

- Highlight strategic networking activities as a core offering and organise regular events that connect entrepreneurs with investors, experienced mentors, and other key figures in the business community. This is particularly important for underrepresented groups, who often have smaller existing networks.
- Provide peer learning and collaborative spaces where entrepreneurs from similar backgrounds can share experiences and support each other. While group-specific Programmes can build trust, ensure that mechanisms are in place to prevent exclusion from the mainstream business community.

Embrace digitalisation strategically

- Use online delivery formats for training to increase flexibility and outreach, particularly to more remote locations. However, critically, address digital skill gaps among target groups by providing foundational computer training and ensuring that trainers are equipped for online delivery.
- Integrate training and support for digital marketing tools and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions, recognising the growing importance of these technologies for new businesses, particularly in higher-income economies.
- Recognising the growing importance of digital marketing tools and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions for new businesses, particularly in higher-income economies, integrate training and support for these technologies.

Strengthen monitoring, evaluation, and adaptation.

- From the outset, establish a robust monitoring and evaluation system that defines clear Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs should go beyond mere startup rates and include broader indicators such as skill acquisition, network expansion, and long-term business survival rates.
- Conduct periodic, objective impact assessments (ideally by external experts) to identify Programme strengths and weaknesses, enabling the continuous improvement and adaptation of support offers based on lessons learned. This is crucial given the historically underdeveloped evaluation of inclusive entrepreneurship schemes.
- Use collected data to inform policy dialogue at local, national, and European levels, highlighting successes and demonstrating the societal and economic advantages of inclusive entrepreneurship.

11. SELECTED BUSINESS MODELS FROM THE B4B INCLUSIVE BUSINESS INCUBATION PROGRAMME

Disclaimer: These are generic descriptions of projects that have been developed through the B4B Inclusive Business Incubation Programme, which is part of the IN-HABIT project. If you would like to use them as inspiration for your own project, you should develop a business plan that is tailored to your specific context, challenges, and target groups.

To protect intellectual property and sensitive business know-how, the detailed business models have been anonymised. This approach allows the replicability and impact potential to be analysed, while safeguarding the interests and originality of the participating entrepreneurs.

Introduction

As part of the IN-HABIT Inclusive Business Incubation Programme, 179 projects involving 223 entrepreneurs were supported in four pilot cities: Córdoba (Spain), Lucca (Italy), Riga (Latvia), and Nitra (Slovakia). From this extensive cohort, the B4B team has strategically selected a portfolio of representative models.

This curated portfolio covers the full spectrum of wellbeing innovation—including place-based, digital, service, and product-driven solutions—ensuring a diverse and mature set of reference cases. To ensure the portfolio comprises actionable opportunities, the maturity of each solution was assessed by evaluating its Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and Societal Readiness Level (SRL).

Figure 29 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire - Project SP-01 - SLR and TRL levels

The “Urban Farming kits” initiative has a Societal Readiness Level (SRL) of six. This means that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment in cooperation with stakeholders. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is two, indicating that, while the technological concept (DIY kits) has been formulated, it remains a low-tech enabler for a high-touch social process. The model has replication potential, particularly for educational institutions and municipalities seeking to incorporate sustainability into their curricula and promote intergenerational learning through agriculture.

Figure 30 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire - Project SP-02 - SLR and TRL levels

The “Rural Co-living Hubs” model has a Societal Readiness Level (SRL) of five. This indicates that the proposed solution has been validated by relevant local stakeholders. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of two reflects the fact that the innovation lies in the business model and asset management rather than in the development of new technology. The project demonstrates potential for replication in depopulated regions, making it particularly suitable for rural development agencies and tourism boards seeking to attract digital nomads and remote workers to underused heritage sites.

Figure 31 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire - Project IT-01 - SLR and TRL levels

The “Digital Pet Health Record” has a Societal Readiness Level (SRL) of five. This means that the solution is currently being validated by relevant stakeholders. The technology readiness level (TRL) is also five, indicating that the technology has been validated in a relevant environment and that the gap between a prototype and a fully operational system has been bridged. This model has potential to grow as a scalable digital tool. It is particularly well-suited to tech-savvy municipalities and private veterinary networks looking to centralise fragmented pet care services into a unified digital ecosystem.

Figure 32 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire - Project IT- 02 - SLR and TRL levels

The “Music and Animal Therapy” initiative has a Societal Readiness Level (SRL) of nine. This means that the project solution has been proven in a relevant environment. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is one, indicating that the programme focuses entirely on social application and therapeutic protocols, independently of technological development. The model demonstrates potential for replication due to its low barrier to entry. It is particularly well-suited to healthcare facilities, NGOs and nursing homes seeking holistic, non-pharmacological interventions to enhance emotional well-being.

Figure 33 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire - Project LV-01 - SLR and TRL levels

The “Food Digital Platform” has a Societal Readiness Level (SRL) of six. This means that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment. The Technology Readiness Level (six) is nine, which indicates that the system itself (i.e. the digital marketplace and logistics software) has been demonstrated in an operational environment. This model has potential for replication as a “plug-and-play” solution. It is particularly suitable for smart cities and regional governments that are looking to digitise local food systems and strengthen urban-rural economic links.

Figure 34 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire - Project LV-02 - SLR and TRL levels

The “Sustainable Functional Beverages” initiative has reached a Societal Readiness Level (SRL) of nine. This indicates that the product is fully embedded in the market and proven to meet consumer demand for healthy and environmentally friendly options. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is also nine, indicating that the system as a whole (including product formulation, packaging, and distribution) has been proven in an operational environment. This model has potential for growth via retail and export. It is particularly well-suited to the consumer goods sector and retail partners looking to offer products that combine personal nutrition with direct environmental action.

Figure 35 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire - Project SK-01 - SLR and TRL levels

The “Eco-Cycle Tourism” initiative has a Societal Readiness Level (SRL) of six. This means that the solution has been demonstrated in a relevant environment by setting up rest zones along cycling routes to gather feedback from the local community. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is two, as the focus is on service design and infrastructure revitalisation. This model has potential for replication in semi-rural areas. It is particularly well-suited to regional tourism offices and community organisations that promote active lifestyles and support local food and drink producers by providing sustainable mobility infrastructure.

Figure 36 - Results of the self-assessment questionnaire - Project SK-02 - SLR and TRL levels

The “Circular Wool Textiles” initiative has achieved a Societal Readiness Level (SRL) of nine. This indicates that the system has been fully proven in its operational environment and successfully integrates traditional craftsmanship with the principles of the circular economy. In contrast, the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is one, reflecting the fact that the innovation is process-based and rooted in traditional knowledge rather than modern technology. The project has potential to be replicated as a cultural and environmental asset. It is particularly well-suited to cultural centres, circular economy hubs and rural cooperatives that wish to repurpose local waste materials into high-value artisanal products.

A structured analysis of each selected business is provided in the next chapter, covering core elements such as their anonymised business model, market analysis, primary competitors, and sales channels.

11.1. URBAN FARMING KITS – PROJECT SP-01

SPAIN (Córdoba) incubated projects – Theme: Cultural Heritage

Business Model description (anonymised)

This initiative promotes urban sustainability by offering hands-on education and tools for growing food at home. It operates on a hybrid business model, generating revenue from the sale of DIY urban gardening kits and offering educational workshops for schools, families, and community groups. The kits are designed to be user-friendly, adaptable to small urban spaces, and come with both online and in-person guidance to ensure ease of use. The revenue model is diversified, with B2C sales of gardening kits complementing B2B partnerships with municipalities, schools, and cultural centres. This model creates value not only through environmental sustainability but also through fostering community cohesion and collective learning experiences.

Problem

The model addresses the lack of accessible tools and knowledge for urban residents to grow their own food. It tackles the barriers of limited space in dense urban environments and the disconnection between city dwellers and ecological cycles.

Value Proposition

The initiative enables **urban residents, families and community groups** to engage in **small-scale food production** through accessible, easy-to-use home-growing kits combined with **hands-on educational activities**.

It lowers barriers to urban farming by adapting tools and knowledge to **limited spaces and diverse user capacities**, while strengthening ecological awareness, food literacy, and everyday wellbeing.

The value proposition combines:

- **Practical tools** for growing food in urban environments,
- **Educational guidance** delivered through workshops and learning formats,
- **Collective learning experiences** that foster social cohesion and shared responsibility for sustainability.

Customer Segments

The primary beneficiaries are urban residents, families, and community groups seeking to engage in small-scale food production.

Channels

The initiative uses a hybrid distribution strategy. Physical channels include farmers' markets and sustainability festivals for direct engagement. Digital channels involve an online store for kit sales and social media campaigns for community outreach. Educational partnerships with schools serve as a key channel for delivering workshops.

Customer Relations

The source text implies a relationship built on education and community support. By offering "educational guidance" and "collective learning experiences," the model fosters social cohesion and shared responsibility, moving beyond a transactional product sale to a relational educational experience.

Key Activities

- Design and production of **DIY urban gardening kits** suitable for small indoor or outdoor spaces.
- Sourcing of **sustainable and climate-appropriate materials**.
- Development of **pedagogical content** related to food cultivation, ecology, and urban sustainability.
- Delivery of **workshops and educational sessions** for schools, families, and community groups.
- Coordination of B2C sales and B2B educational services.
- Logistics and distribution of kits.
- Outreach and engagement through community events, markets, and digital channels.

Key Resources

The model relies on sustainable materials for kit production and the intellectual capital required to develop educational content. There is also the need for a small but efficient operational team and partnerships to expand reach.

Key partners

- **Schools and educational institutions** implementing workshops.
- **Municipalities and cultural centres** commissioning educational activities.
- **NGOs and community organisations** working with families and disadvantaged groups.
- Community gardens and local sustainability initiatives.
- Environmental educators and facilitators contributing content and delivery.

Cost Structure

Initial and development costs:

- Product design and prototyping of gardening kits.
- Development of educational materials and workshop formats.
- Initial outreach and communication activities.

Operational costs:

- Materials and components for kit production.
- Logistics and distribution.
- Personnel costs linked to workshops and facilitation.
- Marketing and community engagement.
- Coordination with partner institutions.

Competition

The initiative faces competition from established garden supply chains and digital DIY platforms that offer similar products but often lack the integrated educational and social value proposition of this local model.

Revenue Streams

The model operates on a diversified hybrid basis. Potential revenue is generated through Business-to-Consumer (B2C) sales of gardening kits and Business-to-Business (B2B) educational service contracts with municipalities and schools.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Replication prerequisites

- **Spatial prerequisites:** The deployment of this model relies on the availability of small-scale urban spaces, which serve as the essential physical substrate for home-based production.
- **Operational capacity:** This requires access to basic sustainable materials and simple local production capacities to ensure the cost-effective manufacturing of the DIY kits.
- **Ecosystem integration:** The model's value proposition is maximised through strategic alliances with educational partners who are willing to embed food literacy into their curricula, transforming the product into a pedagogical tool.
- **Institutional alignment:** Successful replication requires municipal or institutional support to validate and facilitate community-based learning activities.
- **Market demand:** The strategic rollout must capitalise on the existing demand for hands-on sustainability education among urban populations, addressing the disconnect between citizens and food sources.
- **Adaptive capacity:** Scalability hinges on the capacity to adapt both the physical kits and the pedagogical content to specific local climatic conditions and cultural contexts.
- **Capital requirements:** From a financial perspective, the model requires moderate initial funding to cover the costs of product development, prototyping and initial market campaigns.

Market Analysis

Spain is a net exporter of agricultural products, and its exports have grown significantly over time. Between 2000 and 2021, agrifood exports increased fourfold, reaching USD 64.6 billion, with an average yearly growth rate of 7%.

With an area of 504,745 km² and a population of 47.4 million (in 2020), Spain is the second largest country in the European Union and the fourth most populous. Over half of Spain's total land area is used for agricultural purposes. Almost 7% of the Spanish workforce was employed in the agrifood sector (including primary and manufacturing activities) in 2020, which is in line with the EU average but above that of some European peers.

The agricultural sector represented 18% of Spain's goods exports and 10% of its total goods imports, which is twice the EU average and higher than in most other countries (OECD, 2023)

This model meets the demand for accessible tools and knowledge to help citizens grow their own food, linking ecological transition with local identity and everyday well-being.

Innovation & Replicability Potential

The project's innovation lies in transforming small urban spaces into food production sites, while promoting cultural reconnection through sustainable agriculture practices. The initiative adapts traditional farming methods for urban environments, making sustainability accessible through practical, family-friendly solutions. In Córdoba, where cultural heritage and health are interwoven, the project anchors well-being by tapping into the region's agricultural roots. This business model has potential for replication in other European urban areas, particularly those focused on food security and climate resilience.

11.2. RURAL CO-LIVING HUBS - PROJECT SP-02

SPAIN (Córdoba) incubated projects – Theme: Cultural Heritage

Business Model description (anonymised)

This initiative aims to reactivate underused buildings in small rural towns by transforming them into co-living and co-working spaces that promote wellbeing. It targets remote workers, creatives, and professionals seeking a slower pace of life and reconnection with nature. The revenue model is diverse, generating income from medium-term accommodation rentals, workspace rentals, events, and local experience packages. The initiative partners with rural municipalities, tourism networks, and local producers to create a hub for social, economic, and cultural regeneration in these rural areas.

Problem

The model addresses the dual challenge of rural depopulation and the underutilisation of heritage buildings in small towns. It responds to the growing demand from professionals for workspaces that offer a slower pace of life and reconnection with nature, which traditional rural infrastructure often fails to support.

Value Proposition

The initiative revitalises **underused rural buildings** by transforming them into **hybrid co-living and co-working spaces** that combine accommodation, work infrastructure, and wellbeing-oriented experiences.

It responds to the needs of **remote workers, creatives and professionals** seeking a slower pace of life, connection to nature and meaningful social interaction, while contributing to rural regeneration.

The value proposition integrates:

- **Flexible living and working solutions** in rural contexts,
- **Place-based wellbeing**, rooted in landscape, heritage, and daily rhythms,
- **Community-oriented experiences** that connect residents with local culture and producers.

Customer Segments

The target audience includes remote workers, creatives, and digital nomads seeking flexible living solutions. It also targets professionals who value "place-based wellbeing" and meaningful social interaction with local communities.

Channels

Marketing and outreach are conducted primarily through digital nomad platforms, sustainable tourism networks, and coworking directories. Word-of-mouth via creative networks is also identified as a key channel for attracting the target demographic.

Customer Relations

The model fosters relationships through "on-site facilitation" and community building. By connecting residents with neighbours and local stakeholders, the business moves beyond simple accommodation to offering an integrated community experience.

Key Activities

- Renovation and adaptive reuse of rural properties.
- Management of **co-living accommodation** and **co-working spaces**.
- Provision of guest services and on-site facilitation.
- Organisation of **cultural, wellbeing and community events**.
- Development of local experience packages (nature, food, heritage).
- Coordination with municipalities, tourism networks, and local businesses.
- Marketing and outreach through digital nomad and coworking platforms.
- Community-building among residents and local stakeholders.

Key Resources

Essential resources include the physical rural properties suitable for adaptive reuse and high-speed internet infrastructure. The model also relies on an active network of remote workers and access to local cultural capital for experience creation.

Key Partners

- **Rural municipalities** supporting regeneration and space activation.
- Regional and local **tourism boards and networks**.
- Local producers, artisans, and service providers.
- Digital nomad and coworking platforms.
- Cultural and wellbeing facilitators contributing to programming.

Competition

The primary competitors identified are traditional tourist accommodation providers and niche co-living brands that may operate in similar markets but lack the specific heritage and community integration focus.

Cost Structure

Initial costs:

- Property acquisition or long-term leasing.
- Renovation, refurbishment and furnishing.
- Installation of digital infrastructure (high-speed internet).
- Initial branding and market entry activities.

Operational costs:

- Property maintenance and utilities.
- Staffing for guest services and community facilitation.
- Programme and event delivery.
- Marketing and platform fees.
- Partnership coordination and local sourcing.

Revenue Streams

Potential income is generated through medium-term accommodation rentals and workspace rentals. Additional revenue streams include the sale of event tickets and local experience packages.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Replication prerequisites

- **Infrastructure:** Access to suitable rural properties with permission for adaptive reuse is critical. The success of the model depends on regulatory frameworks that allow underutilised assets, such as heritage buildings, to be converted into mixed-use commercial and residential spaces.
- **Connectivity:** Reliable high-speed internet is essential for remote working and forms the backbone of the model's operations. This digital infrastructure is essential to ensure that rural locations do not compromise the professional productivity of the target demographic of digital nomads.
- **Local ecosystem:** A community capable of providing authentic local experiences (food, nature, and culture) is vital for economic viability.
- **Capital and management:** Funding for renovation and the capacity to manage hospitality and community dynamics are required to bridge the gap between initial CAPEX and operational sustainability. Success hinges on specialised teams that can blend professional hospitality operations with social facilitation.

Market Analysis

The housing market plays an important role in the economy and society. The state of the housing market, alongside the labour and credit markets, influences how affordable housing is for households in the purchase and rental sectors (Banco de España, 2023). Despite the slowdown observed since Q4 of 2022, housing purchases remain robust. Recent developments include a rise in foreign purchases and a fall in mortgage financing, in the context of tighter financing conditions. The significant volume of sales coincides with modest new housing production, as reflected in the containment of real estate supply indicators.

Most housing transactions involve second-hand properties, accounting for around 90% of the market in 2023. The prevalence of second-hand housing is partly due to the accumulation of a large housing stock over previous decades, coupled with a shortage of new housing. Spain's Digital Nomad Visa, introduced in 2023, facilitates the relocation of remote workers to rural areas, further supporting initiatives like Project SP-02²⁹.

By integrating digital lifestyles with heritage-rich rural environments, this project addresses the dual challenges of rural depopulation and the increasing demand for remote workspaces, fostering inclusive well-being through placemaking and active rural lifestyles.

Innovation & Replicability Potential

The innovation of this initiative lies in seamlessly combining modern digital lifestyles with heritage-rich rural environments, transforming underutilized spaces into vibrant hubs for wellbeing, work, and community engagement. By leveraging the growing trend of remote working and digital nomadism, the

²⁹ Source: <https://www.exteriores.gob.es/Consulados/londres/en/ServiciosConsulares/Paginas/Consular/Digital-Nomad-Visa.aspx>

project introduces a new model of rural revitalization that not only attracts talent but also supports sustainable, community-driven economic growth.

In the context of Córdoba's IN-HABIT project, where cultural heritage is recognized as a driver for inclusive health, this initiative exemplifies how traditional architecture can coexist harmoniously with contemporary work practices. Its flexible, modular design, coupled with a range of services (such as accommodation, workspaces, and local experiences), makes it adaptable to different rural settings across Europe. This model can be replicated in other rural municipalities facing similar challenges of depopulation and economic stagnation, especially in areas aiming to attract remote workers and foster local entrepreneurship while preserving cultural heritage.

The potential for replicability lies in its scalability to other rural areas with available properties, high-speed internet access, and an interest in promoting sustainable tourism and wellbeing.

11.3. DIGITAL PET HEALTH RECORD - PROJECT IT-01

ITALY (Lucca) incubated projects – Theme Human-Animal Bond

Business Model description (anonymised)

This digital platform connects pet owners with certified pet care professionals, including veterinarians, groomers, and trainers. The core value proposition is to simplify pet health management by providing an integrated mobile app that features digital medical records, appointment scheduling, reminders, and service discovery. The business relies on robust digital infrastructure, partnerships with local animal professionals, and outreach through pet-related networks. Initial investment needs are moderate, primarily focused on app development, marketing, and partnerships. Key stakeholders include pet owners, veterinary associations, small service providers, and animal welfare advocates.

Problem

The platform addresses the fragmentation of the pet care sector and the lack of online visibility for professionals. It solves the difficulty pet owners face in managing health records and appointments, while helping professionals digitalise their services.

Value Proposition

It is a digital B2B2C platform designed to simplify pet care management and facilitate access to health and care services for domestic animals.

For pet owners, the platform reduces time, financial costs, and stress by providing updated information, personalised reminders, document storage, and direct access to service providers.

For professionals (e.g. veterinarians, groomers), it offers dedicated digital spaces to present services, manage bookings and communicate with clients, addressing the lack of updated and visible online profiles in the sector.

Customer Segments

The platform serves a dual market: Pet owners (B2C) who need to manage their animals' health, and Professionals (B2B) such as veterinarians, groomers, and trainers who need digital management tools and visibility.

Channels

The primary channel is the mobile application (iOS/Android). Other channels include partnerships with local vets, collaborations with shelters and pet shops, and presence at pet expos.

Customer Relations

For professionals, the platform offers a digital storefront and client management tools. For owners, it provides convenience through reminders and document storage. The relationship is maintained through the app's utility and communication features.

Key Activities

- Development and maintenance of a mobile digital platform (iOS and Android).
- Management of user functionalities: reminders, personalised notifications, document storage and sharing.
- Aggregation and continuous updating of service provider information.
- Enabling direct contact, appointment booking and client management.
- Development of booking and management tools for professionals.
- Platform promotion through online and offline communication channels.
- Progressive integration of additional services (e.g. pet sitting, pet training).

Key Resources

The text identifies software development capabilities, legal compliance structures, and the digital infrastructure required to host the platform as critical components.

Key Partners

- Veterinary clinics, groomers, and other pet service providers registered on the platform.
- Business partners supporting platform growth and service expansion.
- Communication and promotion partners (online and offline).
- Potential institutional and sectoral actors involved in pet care and wellbeing ecosystems.

Competition

The main competitors to this platform are large e-commerce platforms like **Zooplus** and **Amazon Pet Care**, which offer a wide range of pet products but lack the integrated services for pet care professionals.

Other competitors include **Petbacker** and **Rover**, which connect pet owners with local care providers but do not offer digital health records or appointment scheduling.

Cost Structure

Initial costs:

- Software development fully financed by the founders.
- Software registration and legal compliance.

Operational costs:

- Platform maintenance and updates.
- Marketing and communication campaigns.
- Development of advanced booking and management tools.
- Personnel costs as the team scales.
- Infrastructure and operational expenses linked to platform growth.

Revenue Streams

The model uses a Freemium approach: basic features for owners, while potential revenue comes from monthly subscription fees paid by professionals for premium features and visibility.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Replication prerequisites

- **Market scale:** A critical mass of active pet owners and service providers is fundamental to the viability of this two-sided platform. Successful replication depends on achieving sufficient local density to trigger network effects and ensure immediate utility for users and tangible business volume for professionals.
- **Technology:** Robust mobile infrastructure that is fully compliant with data protection regulations is a prerequisite for deployment.
- **Engagement:** Service providers who are willing to maintain updated online profiles are essential for the operational relevance of the platform. The model's success hinges on a cultural shift among veterinarians and groomers towards active digital management, ensuring real-time service accuracy for end users.
- **Financials:** Investment capacity for marketing and a market ready for subscription-based models are required to bridge the gap between development and profitability.

Market Analysis

The pet care sector across Europe has seen significant growth, with Italy ranking highly in terms of the number of companion animals per household. According to the European Pet Food Industry Federation

(FEDIAF), Italy has a large number of pet owners, and demand for pet-related services continues to rise (FEDIAF, 2025). Nevertheless, the sector remains fragmented, particularly with regard to day-to-day, non-emergency pet care services such as grooming and training.

Italy is one of the European countries with the highest number of pets (FEDIAF, 2025). Digital tools that simplify pet care and improve owners' quality of life could be introduced in other countries such as France, Germany, and the United Kingdom. This aligns with broader European trends towards the digitalisation of SMEs and more responsible pet ownership. The platform addresses these needs directly by offering pet care professionals and owners a unified digital solution. It is worth noting that the Italian pet care market is underserved in terms of localised, integrated digital services. This platform is in a strong position to fill the gap in the Italian pet care market by presenting a localised, integrated digital service. This initiative aligns with these actions by enhancing transparency, improving access to qualified professionals, and supporting the digitalization of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the pet care sector.

Innovation & Replicability Potential

The innovation of this platform lies in its ability to integrate pet health management with digital tools, providing pet owners with an all-in-one solution that includes medical records, appointment scheduling, and communication with certified professionals. This platform modernizes the traditionally offline pet care industry by centralizing services and improving convenience, trust, and accessibility.

Its modular, multilingual design makes it adaptable to other regions with large pet populations. The platform can be replicated in other cities and countries, particularly in areas with a high number of pet owners and a demand for digital pet care services. The model is scalable and could be expanded to include additional services, such as emergency care or pet insurance partnerships, making it a flexible solution for diverse markets.

11.4. MUSIC & ANIMAL THERAPY - PROJECT IT-02

ITALY (Lucca) incubated projects – Theme Human-Animal Bond

Business Model description (anonymised)

This service provides certified animal-assisted and music-assisted therapy to children, the elderly, and individuals with mental health or physical disabilities. The services are offered through structured partnerships with institutions such as schools, daycare centres, eldercare facilities, and correctional institutions. Revenue is generated through a mixed model: some therapy sessions are funded by municipalities or healthcare agencies, while others are supported by private foundations or philanthropy. The team is composed of certified professionals, including psychologists, educators, musicians, and animal therapists, ensuring compliance with national guidelines.

The model relies on a multidisciplinary team and certified therapy animals, supported by strong collaborations with healthcare and educational institutions.

Problem

The initiative addresses the need for non-medicalised, holistic support for disadvantaged groups. It offers an alternative to sterile clinical settings by providing emotional support and skill development through natural stimuli.

Value Proposition

The organisation designs and delivers **Animal-Assisted Interventions (AAI)** for children, young people, adults, and older people with physical or psychological vulnerabilities.

Through structured interaction with animals and immersion in a natural environment, the interventions aim to **increase motivation, engagement, autonomy, skill development, and socialisation**, while avoiding the negative effects of highly medicalised settings.

The value lies in combining:

- a **welcoming, non-institutional environment** designed for fragile users,
- **trained and continuously updated professionals**, and
- **high standards of animal welfare**, where animals are treated as respected participants rather than tools.

Customer Segments

Beneficiaries include children, the elderly, and individuals with mental or physical disabilities. Institutional customers include schools, daycare centres, eldercare facilities, and correctional institutions.

Channels

Services are delivered through direct institutional partnerships, participation in public tenders, and collaborations with foundations. The service is delivered on-site at partner institutions.

Customer Relations

Relationships are built on trust and the delivery of "personalised intervention pathways." The model emphasises co-design with social cooperatives and care managers to ensure interventions are tailored to specific needs.

Key Activities

- Design and delivery of **Animal-Assisted Activities (AAA)**, **Animal-Assisted Education (EAA)**, and **Animal-Assisted Therapy (TAA)**.
- Co-design of personalised intervention pathways in collaboration with **social cooperatives, associations, and service managers**.
- Management and daily care of animals involved in the interventions.
- Coordination of a **multi-professional team** (educators, psychologists, ethologists, musicians, certified AAI handlers, veterinarians).

- Monitoring and evaluation of outcomes through interviews, monitoring sheets and psychological tests.
- Continuous professional training and updating of staff.
- Maintenance and management of the natural and built environment where activities take place.

Key Resources

The model relies on a multi-professional team (psychologists, musicians, handlers) and certified therapy animals. It also requires access to suitable natural or built environments for session delivery.

Key Partners

- **Social cooperatives and associations** collaborating with people with disabilities or psychosocial vulnerabilities (clients and co-design partners).
- **Multi-professional collaborators** (educators, psychologists, veterinarians, ethologists, certified AAI professionals).
- **Local and regional networks** involved in disability services and inclusive wellbeing.
- Membership and affiliation networks (e.g. cultural and social promotion associations).

Competition

The primary competition comes from traditional rehabilitation centres that offer conventional therapeutic models without the integrated animal-music approach.

Cost Structure

Initial / start-up costs (distributed over time due to long-term operation):

- Training of operators.
- Purchase of basic IT equipment and office materials.
- Structural improvements of the operational site.
- Administrative and compliance-related costs.

Fixed operational costs:

- Animal care and maintenance.
- Insurance and certifications.
- Professional fees (consultants, accountants).
- Association memberships and volunteer/participant cards.
- Reimbursements and compensation for operators.
- Utilities and facility costs.

Revenue Streams

The model uses a mixed funding strategy. Potential revenue is generated through public service contracts (municipalities/health agencies) and private support from foundations or philanthropy.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Replication prerequisites

- **Environment:** A suitable natural setting adapted for disadvantaged users is essential in order to differentiate this model from traditional clinical or medicalised settings.
- **Expertise:** Access to certified professionals and veterinary support is critical. Successful replication relies on a multidisciplinary team comprising psychologists, musicians, educators, and handlers who receive continuous professional training to ensure the safety and efficacy of these interventions.
- **Standards:** Strong ethical guidelines and animal welfare protocols are the foundation of the model's legitimacy.
- **Operations:** The capacity to manage long-term personalised pathways and monitor outcomes is required to validate social impact. This involves co-designing specific intervention plans with care managers and using robust monitoring tools, such as psychological tests and interviews, to track cognitive and emotional progress over time.
- **Sustainability:** Financial stability to cover costs and ensure a surplus is necessary to sustain the high operational costs of animal care and specialised staff

Market Analysis

Animal-Assisted Therapy (AAT) involves the integration of specially selected and trained animals into therapeutic, or intervention plans that aim to improve physical, cognitive, psychosocial, behavioural, and/or emotional functioning in humans. As with AAE, it is developed, directed, or delivered by formally educated, licensed, or qualified healthcare or human services professionals, and progress is measured and documented³⁰.

Interacting with animals can benefit people in many different ways³¹. These benefits can be categorised into five types: social, emotional, health, benefits for persons with special needs, and financial.

The demand for AAT is further underscored by Italy's demographic trends, including an aging population and rising mental health concerns among youth. These factors make interventions like AAT highly relevant and timely. Moreover, the combination of AAT with music therapy offers a holistic approach to healing, enhancing emotional and social well-being.

³⁰ Source: <https://aas-int.org/aai/standards-of-practice/>

³¹ Source: https://europeanpetfood.comingsoon.site/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/FEDIAF_Benefits_of_pet_ownership.pdf

Innovation & Replicability Potential

This initiative offers a uniquely interdisciplinary and emotionally resonant model of care by integrating certified animal-assisted interventions with music therapy. It reinforces the human–animal bond as a source of healing, companionship, and emotional development, which is fully aligned with Lucca's IN-HABIT mission. Its service-based delivery model can be adapted to various settings, such as schools, care homes, and correctional centres, making it replicable in other regions where mental health and inclusion are key priorities.

11.5. FOOD DIGITAL PLATFORM - PROJECT LV-01

LATVIA (Riga) incubated projects – Theme Food

Business Model description (anonymised)

This digital platform connects small-scale food producers in rural areas with urban consumers who are looking for fresh, healthy, and traceable food. The platform offers an online marketplace where users can browse seasonal offerings from independent farmers and artisanal producers and receive direct-to-door deliveries. It operates on a smart logistics system, offering weekly or fortnightly orders to reduce food waste and unnecessary transport.

Problem

The platform addresses the disconnect between small-scale rural producers and urban consumers. It solves the logistical challenge of accessing fresh, traceable food in cities while providing farmers with a direct route to market that bypasses traditional, less transparent supply chains.

Value Proposition

The initiative provides a **digital marketplace** that directly connects **small-scale rural food producers** with **urban consumers** seeking fresh, healthy, and traceable food.

By curating seasonal offerings and enabling direct-to-consumer delivery, the platform shortens supply chains, increases transparency, and supports more resilient local food systems.

The value proposition combines:

- **convenient access** to locally produced, seasonal food,
- **trust and transparency** around food origin and production methods,
- and **eco-conscious consumption**, supported by reduced food waste and optimised logistics.

In addition to commercial exchange, the platform contributes to **food literacy and awareness** by emphasising provenance, seasonality, and responsible consumption.

Customer Segments

The platform serves two distinct segments: urban consumers seeking fresh, healthy, and traceable food, and small-scale rural producers (farmers and artisans) looking for fair market access. It also engages conscious consumer communities and food-related NGOs.

Channels

The primary channel is an e-commerce platform facilitating home delivery and pick-up points (including workplace hubs). Subscription boxes serve as a recurring channel to maintain customer engagement.

Customer Relations

Relationships are built on trust and transparency regarding food origins. The platform acts as an intermediary that creates a narrative connection between the consumer and the producer through storytelling and education around provenance.

Key Activities

- Development and maintenance of the digital marketplace platform.
- Curation and onboarding of local farmers and artisanal producers.
- Coordination of weekly and bi-weekly ordering cycles.
- Organisation of smart logistics and last-mile delivery.
- Management of subscription models and seasonal box offerings.
- Customer service and relationship management.
- Communication and storytelling around producers, products, and seasons.
- Data management related to demand forecasting and waste reduction.

Key Resources

The business relies heavily on IT infrastructure for the platform and cold-chain logistics partnerships to ensure food safety. A strong, curated network of local producers is also a fundamental resource.

Key Partners

- Small-scale farmers and artisanal food producers.
- Local and regional logistics providers supporting home delivery and pick-up points.
- Conscious consumer communities and food-related NGOs.
- Municipal actors involved in food policy and urban sustainability.
- Workplace or neighbourhood hubs hosting pick-up locations.

Competition

Competitors include supermarkets with organic sections, fragmented farmers' markets, and generic food delivery services. The platform differentiates itself through its specific focus on local, short supply chains and producer storytelling.

Cost Structure

Initial and development costs:

- Platform design and technical development.
- Setup of logistics coordination systems.
- Initial producer onboarding and quality control processes.

Operational costs:

- IT infrastructure and platform maintenance.
- Logistics and cold-chain partnerships.
- Personnel for operations, customer support, and producer relations.
- Marketing and community engagement activities.
- Payment processing and transaction-related costs.

Overall investment needs are **moderate**, reflecting a digital-first model combined with operational logistics.

Revenue Streams

The service could generate income through commission-based sales on transactions, premium subscriptions for consumers, and the sale of curated seasonal boxes.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Replication prerequisites

- **Supply and demand:** A sufficient number of local producers willing to sell directly, coupled with urban consumer demand for transparent, seasonal food, is the fundamental market driver.
- **Infrastructure:** A robust digital platform for e-commerce and subscriptions, supported by reliable logistics and cold chain solutions, forms the technological and operational backbone.
- **Management:** The capacity to manage seasonal variability and curate product lines is essential for operational resilience.
- **Policy alignment:** Support from local food strategies or sustainability policies provides the necessary institutional legitimacy.
- **Investment:** Moderate initial funding for technology and operational setup is required to launch the digital marketplace. Capital must be allocated to platform development and establishing

initial logistics partnerships to bridge the period before revenue streams from commissions or subscriptions become self-sustaining.

Market Analysis

In 2020, the EU's utilised agricultural area covered 157.4 million hectares, equivalent to 38.4% of the total land area. The proportion of utilised agricultural area within the total land area ranged from less than one-tenth in Sweden and Finland, to more than half in Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Hungary, Romania, and Denmark, peaking at 71.7% in Ireland (Eurostat, 2022b).

In 2020, more than three-fifths (62.3%) of the EU's utilised agricultural area was arable land used to produce crops for human and animal consumption. Permanent grassland accounted for almost a third (30.5%) of the utilised agricultural area, mainly providing fodder and forage for animals. The remaining 7.1% was used almost exclusively for permanent crops such as fruit, olives, and grapes (Eurostat, 2022b)

In 2020, there were 9.1 million agricultural holdings (referred to simply as "farms") in the EU. The average size of a farm in the EU that year was 17.4 hectares. However, almost two thirds (63.8%) of EU farms were smaller than 5.0 hectares, while just over one tenth (11.4%) had 30.0 hectares or more. The largest size category, comprising farms with at least 100 hectares, accounted for just 3.6% of the total number of farms but collectively had slightly more than half (52.5%) of the total area used for agricultural production in the EU (Eurostat, 2022b). In 2022, some 1.6 billion tonnes of food, beverages, and tobacco products were transported by heavy goods vehicles registered in the EU (European Commission, 2020)

This initiative addresses these needs by creating a digital bridge that strengthens regional food resilience. It aligns with the ambitions of the EU Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy by shortening supply chains and encouraging local economies. The Farm to Fork Strategy lies at the heart of the Green Deal. It comprehensively addresses the challenges of sustainable food systems and recognises the inextricable links between healthy people, societies, and the planet. The transition to sustainable food systems also presents a significant economic opportunity. Citizens' expectations are evolving, driving significant change in the food market. This presents opportunities for farmers, food processors, and food service providers. The transition to sustainability offers a "first mover" advantage to all participants in the EU food chain (European Commission, 2020)

Innovation & Replicability Potential

The project transforms a fragmented agricultural system into a connected, purpose-driven marketplace. By embedding trust, locality, and storytelling into every transaction, it redefines food as a cultural and ecological act. In Riga, where IN-HABIT focuses on food as a driver of wellbeing, the project reconnects people with producers and seasons, offering a replicable digital model for regional food sovereignty across Europe.

11.6. SUSTAINABLE FUNCTIONAL BEVERAGES – PROJECT LV-02

LATVIA (Riga) incubated projects – Theme: Food

Business Model description (anonymised)

This service offers plant-based functional beverage kits designed to combine nutrition, aesthetics, and environmental sustainability. Each kit includes a natural energy drink concentrate enriched with minerals and antioxidants, a reusable thermos bottle for on-the-go drinking, and natural sweeteners. Every purchase of the product funds the planting of a tree, creating a direct connection between consumers' lifestyle choices and environmental restoration.

Problem

The product addresses the lack of healthy, sustainable alternatives in the energy drink market. It targets consumers looking to avoid sugar, artificial ingredients, and the energy "crashes" associated with conventional beverages, while also addressing environmental concerns through its business practices

Value Proposition

The business provides a **clean, herbal, tea-based energy drink** designed for health-conscious consumers seeking **steady energy, focus and hydration** without sugar, artificial ingredients, jitters, or crashes.

The product combines functional wellness benefits with **environmental responsibility**, offering an alternative to conventional energy drinks and coffee that aligns with consumers' health and sustainability values.

The value proposition targets both:

- **B2C users**, who adopt the drink as a daily ritual supporting mental clarity and well-being, and
- **B2B partners** (e.g. yoga studios, wellness centres, retreat facilities), who offer the product as a value-aligned product to their clients.

Customer Segments

The primary segments are B2C health-conscious consumers seeking mental clarity and well-being, and B2B partners such as yoga studios, wellness centres, and retreats that wish to offer value-aligned products to their clients.

Channels

Sales are conducted through an online shop, health food retailers, and lifestyle boutiques. Strategic partnerships with yoga studios and workplace wellbeing programmes also serve as key distribution channels.

Customer Relations

The brand builds relationships through a subscription-based model for regular customers and by aligning with the consumer's values through environmental initiatives (e.g., planting a tree for every pack sold).

Key Activities

- Formulation and production of a **herbal, tea-based functional beverage**.

- Management of a **subscription-based distribution model** for regular customers.
- Marketing and brand positioning focused on wellness-oriented consumers.
- Customer acquisition through digital channels, content marketing, and partnerships.
- Management of B2B relationships with studios, retreats, and wellness programmes.
- Logistics and fulfilment of recurring and one-off orders.
- Environmental actions linked to the product (tree planting per pack sold, transition to zero-waste packaging).

Key Partners

- **Wellness studios, yoga teachers, and retreat centres** acting as B2B partners and distribution channels.
- Logistics and production partners ensure reliable supply and delivery.
- Marketing and influencer partners supporting brand growth.
- Strategic investors and business partners aligned with the brand's sustainability and wellness vision.

Key Resources

Not explicitly detailed as a standalone section, but the text implies the need for raw material procurement networks, production facilities, and a digital e-commerce infrastructure.

Competition

The main competitors are large-scale energy drink brands and emerging health beverage brands, including smaller specialist companies like Plenish.

Cost Structure

Initial and scaling costs:

- Raw material procurement.
- Production setup and scaling.
- Marketing and customer acquisition campaigns.
- Logistics and distribution.
- Team expansion as customer numbers grow.

Ongoing operational costs:

- Manufacturing and packaging.
- Subscription fulfilment and logistics.
- Marketing (paid ads, content creation, influencer collaborations).

- Personnel costs.
- Sustainability initiatives (environmental impact actions).

Revenue Streams

Potential revenue is derived from direct product sales, recurring subscription models, and limited-edition campaigns.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Replication prerequisites

- **Market demand:** The primary driver of viability is a sufficient segment of health-conscious consumers looking for functional beverages. To ensure economic sustainability, it is essential to capture this demographic by aligning the value proposition with shifting consumer preferences towards plant-based and low-sugar options.
- **Infrastructure:** Access to reliable production facilities and logistics for subscription delivery is critical for operational resilience. The model requires a robust supply chain that can manage high-quality raw materials and ensure timely direct-to-consumer distribution in order to maintain customer retention.
- **Brand positioning:** A strong identity linked to wellness and environmental values is essential for market differentiation. The brand must communicate its commitment to sustainability.
- **Compliance:** Compliance with food and beverage regulations in target markets is a non-negotiable prerequisite. It is vital to navigate the complex regulatory landscape regarding food safety, ingredients and labelling in order to avoid legal risks and ensure long-term market stability.
- **Partnerships:** Building connections with local wellness ecosystems, such as corporate wellness programmes and gyms, can function as a strategic lever for distribution and credibility.
- **Commitment:** Financial resources are required for market entry and dedication to impact measures such as reforestation to sustain the social business model.

Market Analysis

Europe is now the world's second-largest market for organic food and drinks, after the USA³².

In 2024, the value of the European food and drink market was estimated to be between €1.169 trillion, making it one of the region's largest manufacturing industries and a major contributor to the European economy. In 2022, EU consumers spent €1,778 billion, accounting for 21.8% of their budget, on food and drink, either purchased in shops or consumed in restaurants and cafés, with out-of-home consumption representing almost a third of total consumer spending on food and drink products. The share of overall

³² Source: <https://www.cbi.eu/market-information/natural-food-additives/what-demand>

household expenditure on food and drink products varied across Member States, ranging from 17% to 30% (11% to 27% when considering only food and drinks purchased in shops (FoodDrinkEurope's, 2024)

Europe has a large food and drink industry that requires natural additives for a variety of uses. Consumers are increasingly demanding healthier and more sustainable food ingredients instead of artificial ones, a trend that has been boosted by stricter European Union (EU) legislation³³.

According to a 2022 Food Safety Survey in the EU report, awareness of food safety topics remains high among Europeans. Respondents are most aware of additives such as colours, preservatives and flavourings used in food or drink (70%). More than half of respondents selected genetically modified ingredients in food or drink products (56%) (EFSA, 2022)

This initiative meets consumer demands for transparency, reduced packaging, and climate-positive practices. It reflects EU ambitions for sustainable consumption and innovation in the food and beverage sectors.

Innovation & Replicability Potential

This project offers a new approach to hydration, where every sip supports personal health and environmental regeneration. In the context of Riga's IN-HABIT, it broadens the conversation around food to encompass daily rituals and consumer empowerment. Thanks to its light infrastructure, modular design, and emotional brand positioning, it can be replicated in other European cities that are focused on wellbeing and ecological transition.

11.7. ECO-CYCLE TOURISM - PROJECT SK-01

SLOVAKIA (Nitra) incubated projects – Theme Art and Environment

Business Model description (anonymised)

This initiative aims to revitalize cycling routes in semi-rural areas by creating dedicated rest and refreshment zones for cyclists and families. Each site includes small-scale kiosks offering local food and beverages, bike services, and nature-based recreation. The flagship location features a bicycle pump track and an eco-playground, making it a multifunctional stop that blends sport, leisure, and regional promotion. The business generates revenue through food and drink sales, seasonal events, and partnerships with local producers. Additionally, it promotes local tourism and regional identity.

Problem

The project addresses the lack of cyclist-friendly infrastructure in semi-rural areas. It fills the gap for rest and refreshment zones that support longer, family-oriented cycling trips, which are currently underserved by generic roadside stops.

³³ Ibid

Value Proposition

The initiative creates **cyclist-oriented rest and refreshment hubs** along semi-rural cycling routes, designed for **families, individuals, and informal cycling groups** engaging in active leisure.

Each site offers **accessible food and beverages, basic bike rental and service, and informal social space**, responding to the lack of cyclist-friendly infrastructure that supports longer, inclusive, and family-oriented cycling experiences.

The value proposition lies in combining:

- **physical wellbeing through outdoor movement,**
- **convenience and comfort during cycling trips,** and
- **local identity,** by prioritising regional products and integration into local tourism narratives.

Customer Segments

The target audience includes families, individual cyclists, and informal cycling groups. The model also serves the local community by integrating regional producers into the tourism offering.

Channels

Sales occur on-site at "Freshbox" units. Promotion is conducted through digital channels, cycling maps (Points of Interest), social media, and collaborations with municipal tourism bodies.

Customer Relations

The business fosters relations by becoming a hub for the cycling community, offering not just food but also basic bike services. It integrates into the local tourism narrative, connecting visitors with regional identity.

Key Activities

- Operation of **Freshbox self-service snack units** along cycling routes.
- Management of **bike rental and basic service operations.**
- Day-to-day site management and seasonal staffing.
- Coordination with **local food and beverage suppliers.**
- Maintenance of outdoor infrastructure and recreational elements.
- Pricing optimization across different customer segments (families, individuals, groups).
- Promotion through **digital channels,** cycling maps (POI listings), and social media.
- Collaboration with municipalities and tourism stakeholders for visibility and events.

Key Resources

Physical infrastructure (Freshbox units, bike rental equipment) and seasonal staffing are key. Local food and beverage stock is also a critical ongoing resource.

Key Partners

- **Local suppliers** of food and beverages (with preference for Slovak products).
- **Municipalities and regional tourism offices** supporting site placement and promotion.
- Cycling platforms and mapping services (POI integration).
- Strategic ecosystem partners supporting visibility and community engagement.
- Operational partners and service staff for day-to-day management.

Competition

Competitors are identified as generic roadside stops or rural cafés that do not offer specific cyclist-oriented services or infrastructure.

Cost Structure

Initial costs:

- Installation of Freshbox units.
- Setup of bike rental and service equipment.
- Construction or adaptation of small-scale physical infrastructure.
- Initial marketing and inclusion in cycling platforms.

Operational costs:

- Purchase of food and beverage stock.
- Maintenance and servicing of bicycles and equipment.
- Staff costs (technical and operational personnel).
- Utilities and operational overheads.
- Marketing and communication activities.

Revenue Streams

Potential revenue is generated through food and beverage sales, seasonal events, and partnerships with local producers.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Replication prerequisites

- **Location:** Existing or emerging cycling routes with recreational traffic are essential. High-traffic corridors provide the necessary user density to ensure the hub's economic viability.

- **Support:** Municipal backing for permits and site placement is critical. Streamlined licensing for modular units on public land significantly reduces barriers to market entry.
- **Supply:** Local producers willing to supply food and beverages are vital. Short supply chains ensure authenticity, reduce the carbon footprint, and support the regional economy.
- **Investment:** Moderate upfront capital is required for modular infrastructure. Low CAPEX models using flexible units allow for rapid deployment and scalable growth.
- **Demand:** Sufficient seasonal traffic to support on-site sales is essential. Market analysis must confirm that peak-season density is high enough to cover annual operational costs.
- **Management:** Capacity for basic operations and maintenance is necessary. Local partners must efficiently manage inventory and technical repairs to ensure continuity of service.
- **Strategy:** Aligning with regional goals for active mobility, rural tourism and wellbeing ensures institutional support and potential funding.

Market Analysis

Cycling is becoming increasingly popular across Europe as part of the green transition. The state of play of national cycling strategies in the pan-European region is as follows: 14 countries now have a national cycling strategy in place. A further five countries have a strategy that is similar to a national cycling strategy (Küster, 2024). In the past, Slovakia had one cycling strategy: the “National Strategy for the Development of Cycling Transport and Cycle Touring in the Slovak Republic”, which was valid from 2014 (Küster, 2024).

The existence of this cycling network in Slovakia provides an opportunity to establish meaningful rest stops offering more than the basics. This project supports ecological mobility and local economic development by grounding services in regional identity and sustainability principles.

Innovation & Replicability Potential

The project reimagines roadside services as cultural, environmental, and economic assets, blending physical activity with regional storytelling. In Nitra, where the IN-HABIT project aims to connect nature, leisure and creativity, this initiative offers a model that promotes well-being through outdoor activity and a sense of place. Its modularity and requirements make it replicable in other EU regions developing green corridors or rural cycling strategies.

11.8. CIRCULAR WOOL TEXTILES - PROJECT SK-02

SLOVAKIA (Nitra) incubated projects – Theme Art and Environment

Business Model description (anonymised)

This project transforms surplus natural wool from local farms into artisanal clothing and homeware items, combining traditional techniques with environmentally friendly design principles. By working closely with farmers, designers and wool processors, the initiative aims to revive regional wool craftsmanship and promote circular production methods. Products are sold as seasonal collections, in limited runs or as part of design collaborations. The business also runs community workshops, awareness campaigns and partnerships with eco-design networks.

Problem

The initiative tackles the issue of waste in the local wool industry, where surplus natural wool is often underused. It also addresses the loss of traditional textile craftsmanship and the environmental impact of overproduction.

Value Proposition

The initiative transforms **underused local sheep wool** into **handcrafted clothing, accessories, and homeware**, combining traditional textile techniques with contemporary, eco-conscious design.

By collaborating directly with local farmers, wool processors and designers, the project re-establishes **regional wool value chains** while preventing material waste and overproduction.

The value proposition is based on:

- **made-to-order and small-batch production**, avoiding stock surplus,
- **full transparency** of material origin and production processes,
- **durable, timeless products** designed for long-term use, and
- integration of **cultural storytelling and regional identity** into sustainable fashion.

Customer Segments

The customers are implied to be conscious consumers interested in sustainable fashion, durability, and cultural heritage. The model connects local farmers with these buyers through value-added products.

Channels

Distribution channels include a proprietary online store, artisan fairs, concept stores, and regional design events. Collaborations with museums serve as a cultural channel for visibility.

Customer Relations

Relations are built on transparency and storytelling. By sharing the origin of materials and the production process, the brand connects consumers emotionally to the regional heritage and sustainability mission.

Key Activities

- Sourcing raw wool from **local sheep farmers** and regional suppliers.
- Coordination with Slovak and neighbouring wool processors for yarn preparation.

- **Artisanal production** of knitted garments and accessories.
- Product design and development, including limited editions and custom pieces.
- Direct sales via **social media (pre-orders)**, pop-ups, markets, and selected concept stores.
- Organisation of **educational workshops and courses** (schools, public).
- Storytelling and sustainability communication through digital channels.
- Development of own e-shop and curated product kits (planned).
- Outsourcing of specialised tasks (visual identity, photography, web, marketing).

Key Resources

Critical resources include the raw material (wool), access to skilled artisans and textile experts, and the digital infrastructure for branding and sales.

Key Partners

- **Local sheep farmers** ensure access to raw wool.
- Slovak wool processors and manufactories (e.g. regional yarn producers).
- Designers and textile specialists involved in product development.
- Cultural and creative partners (design consultancies, photographers, storytellers).
- Educational institutions (schools) for workshops and courses.
- Concept stores and artisan retail partners.
- Creative and environmental networks supporting visibility and funding access.

Competition

The business competes with eco-fashion brands and imports wool products that may lack the specific regional provenance and circularity of this model.

Cost Structure

Initial costs (low):

- Materials (wool, yarns).
- Prototyping and sample production.
- Branding, visual identity and basic digital infrastructure.

Operational costs:

- Payments to wool processors and artisans.
- Outsourced professional services (design, photography, web, marketing).
- Event and pop-up participation costs.

- Logistics and packaging.
- Marketing and customer acquisition (primarily digital).

Revenue Streams

Potential revenue comes from direct sales of woollen products, limited-edition collections, and creative partnerships. Workshops also contribute to the revenue mix.

Critical success factors and barriers to implementation

Replication prerequisites

- **Resources:** Access to underutilised natural fibres, such as wool, is essential. This waste-to-value approach transforms surplus raw materials into high-quality textile assets for the circular economy.
- **Skills:** Access to skilled artisans is essential for success. Reviving traditional textile expertise is essential to ensure high-quality production and preserve regional craftsmanship.
- **Collaboration:** Farmers willing to join short supply chains are crucial. Direct partnerships ensure transparent sourcing and fair compensation within the regional ecosystem.
- **Facilities:** Access to small-scale processing partners is required. Local manufacturing facilities are essential for transforming raw fibres into usable production materials.
- **Market:** Demand for sustainable, locally made products is the economic driver. Success depends on appealing to consumers willing to pay a premium for heritage and transparency.
- **Operations:** Storytelling and direct sales capacity are vital. The model relies on communicating the sustainability narrative to build brand loyalty.
- **Strategy:** Aligning with the goals of the circular economy and cultural heritage is essential. This dual focus attracts institutional support and sets the brand apart in a crowded market.
- **Investment:** Low to moderate start-up capital is required. Funds should be allocated towards securing raw materials and market entry strategies.

Market Analysis

The EU Green Deal's Circular Economy Action Plan has identified the textiles and clothing sector as a priority for the EU's transition to sustainability and circularity. The Green Deal comprises a series of policy initiatives designed to make the EU climate-neutral by 2050 (Eurostat, 2022).

In 2022, the value of knitwear imports to Europe (including intra-EU imports) amounted to €25.8 billion, up from €16.8 billion in 2017. This equated to approximately 2.75 billion items of clothing (up from 2.27

billion in 2017). During the five-year period from 2017 to 2022, the value of the EU's knitwear imports grew by an average of 9% annually, compared to 6.75% growth for the apparel industry as a whole³⁴. This project aligns with the EU's Circular Economy Action Plan and sustainable fashion objectives, providing environmental and cultural benefits.

Innovation & Replicability Potential

This initiative showcases the potential of natural materials and traditional craftsmanship when reimaged through circular design and local collaboration. Within the context of Nitra's IN-HABIT, it brings together environmental awareness, artisan identity, and sustainable economic opportunity. Its scalable, small-batch model can be adapted in other regions that have access to underutilised natural materials and a growing interest in slow fashion.

12. TRANSVERSAL LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE REPLICABLE BUSINESS MODEL

Based on the cross-analysis of the 16 replicable business models, the following transversal lessons were identified:

Hybrid value creation and financial resilience

- Hybrid models combine income generating components with lower income potential social value creating components through cross subsidisation.
- The surplus created by these models are reinvested to increase the scope of service and to ensure continuous service delivery.
- Financial Resilience may be achieved when the model includes at least two funding streams e.g. grants/public contracts, subscription/service-based revenues, corporate sponsorships/CSR, and in-kind contributions (volunteer time, etc.) rather than one single funding stream.

Governance as a replication enabler and risk-mitigation tool

- Models where end-users/local stakeholders have co-ownership/co-management of the solution model will be more likely to enhance credibility for the solution model; and mitigate the risks associated with implementing the solution model.
- Coordinated Polycentric Governance: A polycentric governance structure (public-private-people) provides clarity regarding role/responsibility; and facilitates coordination among the various parties beyond a single institution.

Implementation capacity matters

- Success in replicating the model depends on the local organization's capacity to facilitate onboarding; coordinate; and provide follow up services; particularly if the solution model requires behaviour change; community engagement; or the establishment of new routine behaviours.

³⁴ Source: <https://www.cbi.eu/market-information/apparel/knitwear/market-potential#what-makes-europe-an-interesting-market-for-knitwear>

Institutional anchoring to navigate regulatory and administrative conditions

- Innovative models may encounter regulatory and/or procurement barriers to implementation. The city has an easier time facilitating the replication of innovative models when it establishes agreement with relevant public authorities (e.g. Memoranda of Understanding; clear operational responsibility; and approved pilot arrangement); which allows the city to provide a safe and efficient environment for implementing the model.

Modular scalability and context-sensitive transfer

- Start Small and Scale Up: Pilot assessing a minimum viable intervention/process will allow the city to evaluate the feasibility of the solution model; develop support/stakeholder buy-in for the solution model; and de-risk future investment in the solution model.
- Transfer the Logic: Adapt the Execution: While the underlying logic of the solution model is potentially scalable and transferable across jurisdictions; the execution of the solution model will need to be adapted to reflect the unique institutional, capacity, target group, infrastructure, and market conditions of each jurisdiction.

13. CONCLUSIONS

IN-HABIT was a unique collaborative effort focused on exploring ways that small and medium sized European cities could build on existing and underutilized local assets to develop IHW projects.

Over the last five years, **IN-HABIT has demonstrated that inclusive wellbeing innovation** can be created, tested and scaled in urban environments, which are typically much closer to citizens daily experiences than larger city environments.

In order to provide a basis for strategic action regarding the **legacies of the IN-HABIT project beyond its pilot phase**, this deliverable represents a consolidated portfolio of sixteen business models that have been developed through interventions in four pilot cities: Cordoba, Riga, Lucca, and Nitra.

Each of the sixteen Replicable Business Models illustrates that IHW can be an engine of community engagement and economic development rather than simply a cost borne by municipalities. Furthermore, each model demonstrates the practical application of "hard" physical infrastructure investments or "soft" social innovations to address common problems including mental health, sustainable food systems, digital skills training, and circular economy loops.

Therefore, the information contained within this report contributes to broader European debates such as the Green Deal, the New European Bauhaus, and the Urban Agenda for the EU, demonstrating that Small and Medium Sized Cities (SMSCs) are particularly well-positioned to develop and implement business models that are citizen-centered, culturally sensitive to their local context, and economically viable.

Thus, at the conclusion of the IN-HABIT project, **Deliverable D8.16 provides** a strategic tool kit to assist decision makers and follow-up cities to both stimulate and enable scaling and adoption of innovative solutions in other local contexts. These results illustrate that IHW are not only desirable goals but that they are also capable of being implemented in an economically sustainable manner in a variety of different European contexts.

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 - RESOURCES FOR BUSINESS MODELS IMPLEMENTATION

This section provides a non-exhaustive list of useful resources, such as assessments and methodologies, to help you implement the chosen business model. It is essential that these resources are tailored to your specific context, and that you seek additional resources and information where necessary.

Strategic planning and definition of objectives to be achieved

Strategic planning involves determining how an organisation will position itself in the future and how it will achieve its goals. To conduct strategic planning, a coherent organisational vision must be developed, strategic objectives must be determined, and the best way to achieve them must be defined. The first step in implementing a new business model is to define a clear strategy.

BASIC QUESTIONS TO BE ANSWERED:

1. Who are we?
2. What do we want to achieve?
3. Where do we want to go?
4. What do we need to do to get there?
5. Who will lead the implementation?
6. Who else will be involved?
7. What is the expected geographic coverage of the business?

DEFINITION OF STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES

Strategic objectives are the quantitative and/or qualitative results that an organisation needs to achieve within a given timeframe in order to be successful. These objectives must be derived from the organisation's vision. Objectives must then be broken down into goals, which can be characterised as the level of performance or rate of improvement necessary for the organisation's success.

INSTRUMENTS

PESTLE analysis: It is of paramount importance to assess the external factors that influence a business, as these factors affect the business context. These factors include political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal considerations.

A **SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats)** is a strategic planning technique that helps organisations identify factors related to business competitiveness. The aim is to specify the risks of the business or project and identify the internal and external favourable and unfavourable factors for achieving these objectives.

INITIAL ACTIVITIES

1. Define the organisation's vision, mission and values.
2. Conduct a PESTLE analysis to investigate the context.
3. Identify key external factors and consider how they might influence the organisation.
4. Conduct a SWOT analysis to compile a list of internal strengths and weaknesses.
5. Cross-reference the information, viewing the strengths and opportunities as drivers and the weaknesses and threats as constraints.
6. Discuss organisational scenarios (best, worst and reasonable).
7. Suggest potential strategies in response to changes for each scenario.
8. Create strategies for the drivers and solutions to the constraints in consultation with a broad group of stakeholders.
9. Develop a theory of organisational change.
10. Identify the social value chain.
11. Focus on impacts and outcomes and prioritise them.
12. Turn these into strategic objectives.
13. Set specific goals.

Definition of the business plan

A business plan is essential for structuring and presenting a new business idea. It should focus on the key aspects of the project and define how the several types of resources will be allocated. Its purpose is to implement the idea and solve the inevitable problems that arise.

EXAMPLE OF BUSINESS PLAN STRUCTURE

1. Executive summary:
2. History of the idea and/or promoters
3. Market analysis:
4. The new idea and its market positioning
5. Project/product/idea
6. Commercial strategy
7. Business management and control
8. Investment required:
9. Financial projections/financial model
10. Investments
11. Financing
12. Financial statements
13. Economic and financial indicators
14. Project evaluation

Complementary analysis

Stakeholder mapping

Stakeholder mapping is a strategic process that involves identifying, categorising, and analysing the individuals or groups who are affected by, or who have influence over, a company, either directly or indirectly. It is essential to ensure that the diverse needs and expectations of stakeholders are carefully considered when making business decisions.

INSTRUMENTS

Stakeholder matrix: A stakeholder matrix is a diagrammatic tool used to visualise or map stakeholders based on a particular set of characteristics. First, all relevant stakeholders should be identified (e.g. users, regulators, partners and financiers). The next step is to assess the level of interest and influence they have over the business using the matrix.

Stakeholder Needs Analysis

A stakeholder analysis identifies the stakeholders involved in a project and the issues important to them, as well as how they will be affected by the project. This process helps to determine who to communicate with, which topics to keep them informed about and how frequently to interact with each stakeholder.

INSTRUMENTS

Customer journey map: A customer journey map is a visual representation of a customer's experience of interacting with a business. It provides relevant information about potential customers' needs at all stages of the process, as well as the business processes that motivate or inhibit their progress, either directly or indirectly.

Market analysis

A market analysis explores the target environment, including its size, trends, competitors, and market segmentation, in order to assess the feasibility of replication and identify market opportunities. Such an analysis is essential to ensure that the replicated business model meets genuine demand, is appropriate to local conditions, and exploits competitive advantages. This approach helps avoid costly mistakes and align the business model with market realities.

INSTRUMENTS

Porter's Five Forces Model: Porter's Five Forces model is a tool used to analyse the competitiveness of a market or industry. The analysis encompasses five forces (or dimensions): internal competition; the potential for new entrants; the bargaining power of suppliers; the bargaining power of customers; and the ability of customers to find substitutes.

Customer Demand Analysis

A customer demand analysis is a tool used to estimate demand for a product or service in a specific market. This research process directly informs the business's strategy and decisions, with a focus on a specific

market. It involves selecting the target market, analysing the product or service category, understanding business parameters, and analysing competitor and partner trends.

INSTRUMENTS

Market Research: Market research activities aim to gather information from target markets to improve understanding of target audiences. These surveys can be used to access important demographic information and find out what customers like about the business and what products or services they need.

Market validation

Market validation involves presenting the solution to the target market, which includes both existing and potential new customers. This process is essential for ensuring that the product aligns with the target audience and for gathering feedback on its effectiveness and appeal.

INSTRUMENTS

Pilot studies: To identify areas for improvement in the product or service's components and functionalities, it is recommended that real tests are conducted on a small scale to gather feedback and make refinements.

Revenue Model

The purpose of this section is to identify and describe the financial strategies through which innovation can generate revenue. It provides a comprehensive, yet non-exhaustive, list of potential revenue streams.

Table 24 - Types of revenue streams

Revenue Model	Description	Select your answer using an "X"
Advertising (ad-based)	The services are monetised through the display of advertisements, which are paid for by third parties.	
Affiliate/Referral Fees	Revenue is generated by referring customers to other businesses or platforms.	

Revenue Model	Description	Select your answer using an "X"
API access fees	Charge other developers for integrating their systems or data via APIs.	
Commission/Transaction Fee	A percentage of the transaction value is deducted from each transaction between two parties.	
Consultancy	Generate revenue by providing consultancy services to third parties.	
Crowdsourcing Rewards	Users have the opportunity to co-create or contribute and receive compensation or rewards.	
Donations/Crowdfunding	Voluntary financial contributions made by individuals or communities.	
Franchise Fees and Royalties	Generate revenue by licensing your business model, brand, or systems to third parties.	
Freemium	The basic service is provided for free, with premium features or content available via a paid subscription.	
Lease or Lease	Generate revenue by lending assets or products temporarily in exchange for one-off or recurring fees.	
Licensing	Charge customers for the use of intellectual property (IP), trademarks, or technology.	
One-Time Purchase (Direct Sales)	Customers pay a one-off fee to purchase a product or service.	
Pay-As-You-Go (usage-based)	Users pay based on their actual usage of a service or product.	
Product grouping	A variety of products and services are provided at a combined or discounted price.	
Razor and Blade	Offer a low-cost base product with high-margin consumables.	

Revenue Model	Description	Select your answer using an "X"
Sponsorship	External brands pay to be associated with your product, service, or event. In return, they receive exposure and publicity.	
Subscription	Recurring payments ensure continued access to a product or service.	
Support and Maintenance Fees	Charge for after-sales support, system maintenance, and upgrades.	

Level of Innovation

To ensure that the business model remains competitive and relevant, it is vital to assess the level of innovation of the innovative assets. This process helps to identify unique selling points and anticipate competitor responses, thereby supporting sustainable growth and defensibility. To assess the novelty, differentiation and market impact of the business model, frameworks such as the Innovation Radar can be used to systematically identify and prioritise high-potential innovations.

INSTRUMENT

Innovation Radar Methodology: The Innovation Radar is designed to identify innovations with high potential. It is a valuable source of information on innovations emerging from research and innovation projects funded by the European Union. Four distinct categories have been established to capture the different degrees of innovation readiness for commercialisation, each corresponding to a specific range of scores on the Innovation Management and Innovation Readiness Indicators.

Critical success factors and barriers

Critical success factors (CSFs) are the essential conditions that must be met for a business model to be successfully implemented in a new context. Addressing these factors during the design process is crucial for creating robust, transferable, sustainable business models that can be implemented across regions and sectors.

INSTRUMENT

Brainstorming workshop: A participatory brainstorming workshop should be held to identify critical success factors and implementation barriers.

Instructions and documentation

Instructions and documentation for products and services must be provided to users to ensure they have all the necessary information to use what they have purchased. For successful implementation and adoption, it is vital that the documentation is comprehensive, clear, and user-friendly.

INSTRUMENTS

Documentation: Create customer profiles (personas) based on different user segments. Identify users' information needs and produce relevant, comprehensive, user-friendly content for each target audience.

Regulatory and policy analysis

Conducting regulatory and policy analysis is essential to ensure compliance with local laws and regulations, thereby reducing legal risks and facilitating market entry. Compliance assessments can prevent costly legal issues in the future, support the smooth running of operations and foster trust with regulators and customers.

INSTRUMENTS

Regulatory compliance checklists: Before you can start selling a product in an EU country, it must comply with the relevant national and EU rules. Once a product has been approved for sale in one EU country, it can, in principle, be sold anywhere in the EU. In practice, however, individual EU countries do retain the right to restrict access to their market for products that are already being sold in another EU country.

External link: [Product compliance](#)

GDPR compliance: Ensuring compliance with the GDPR involves making sure that organisations falling within its scope comply with the requirements for the proper processing of personal data as defined by law.

External link: [GDPR compliance checklist](#)

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

It is essential to identify the types of intellectual property protection required for innovation, whether now or in the future. This guide provides a list of common IP types with descriptions to help you make your selection. It is important to evaluate the type(s) of IP protection you already have and require, including patents, copyrights, trademarks, industrial designs, geographical indications, and trade secrets, to name some.

INSTRUMENTS

WIPO IP Tools: Manage and protect IP assets globally.

External link: [WIPO IP Tools](#)

Patent and Trademark Databases: Identify existing IP and avoid conflicts.

External link: [Espacenet](#)

Remember to look for additional intellectual property rights (IPR) tools and support tailored to your specific needs.

Strategy monitoring

The strategic surveillance system is a continuous process of monitoring the external environment to identify risks and opportunities arising from societal changes. The system works with the concept of strategic themes, i.e. items that must be continuously monitored. By continuously monitoring the project's performance, you can understand what is going well and identify emerging challenges.

ANNEX 2 – LIST OF PLATFORMS AND CATALOGS

In this chapter, we present several platforms and catalogues that are relevant for implementing and scaling up the business models described in this document.

Funding opportunities

- **Public tenders:** The EU Funding and Tenders Portal is a central platform where users can explore EU funding opportunities and tenders, learn about EU Programmes, find collaboration partners, and register as experts. They can also access key guidance and documents. Designed to support applicants, businesses, experts, and citizens alike, the portal provides a public section offering general information, as well as a secure space called 'My Area' for managing proposals, grants, and contracts. [External link](#)
- **EU funding programmes:** A list of the funding programmes implemented through the 2021-2027 multiannual financial framework, divided by heading and cluster. [External link](#)
- **EBAN (European Business Angels Network):** This is a network for early-stage investors, providing a platform to connect with potential funders and help scale emerging social enterprises from the Programme. [External link](#)
- **EIC Transition:** This is a funding Programme under Horizon Europe that targets innovation activities beyond experimental proof of principles. It supports technology maturation and market readiness. Although it is primarily intended for technological innovation, it can offer booster grants or business acceleration services to support the appropriate commercialisation pathways for KERs. [External link](#)
- **Dealflow.eu Matchmaking Platform.** The first European portal to connect thousands of EU-funded innovations with investors and corporations. [External link](#)

Research and Investigation

- **CORDIS:** It is the online repository of all EU-funded research projects and their results. It provides factsheets on multilingual projects, as well as reports, deliverables, and articles. [External link](#)
- **Zenodo:** This is a recommended OpenAIRE-compliant repository for depositing peer-reviewed scientific publications and research datasets, ensuring direct access and the FAIR principles. [External link](#)
- **The Innovation Radar Platform.** The Commission launched Innovation Radar, a data-driven online tool. This tool makes information about EU-funded innovations publicly available. [External link](#)
- **The Habitats Directive.** The Habitats Directive aims to protect over a thousand species, including mammals, reptiles, amphibians, fish, invertebrates, and plants, as well as 230 characteristic habitat types. [External link](#)
- **Green infrastructure,** Promoting the use of green infrastructure in all EU policies to help restore nature and boost biodiversity. [External Link](#)

- **Sustainable urban development.** The Urban Agenda takes an integrated approach to EU and national policies and legislation relating to urban areas. It aims to enhance quality of life by addressing specific priority themes within dedicated partnerships. [External Link](#)
- **Portico.** Portico is the knowledge-sharing and community platform for sustainable urban development in the EU. It provides easy access to the latest knowledge and practical resources from a variety of partners who support EU Cohesion Policy, helping to create just, green, and productive cities. [External link](#)
- **The European Green Deal.** Climate change and environmental degradation pose an existential threat to Europe and the rest of the world. The European Green Deal aims to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy, in order to overcome these challenges. [External Link](#)

Support entities

- **Horizon Results Booster (Booster):** provides services to EU-funded projects to improve the dissemination and exploitation of results. [External link](#)
- **Enterprise Europe Network:** The Enterprise Europe Network provides specialised support services to help SMEs innovate and grow internationally. Its members include chambers of commerce and industry, regional development organisations, universities, research institutes, and innovation agencies. [External link](#)
- **European IP Helpdesk:** It provides free support for intellectual property (IP) management within transnational companies and EU research and innovation Programmes. [External link](#)
- **European Urban initiative (EUI).** Support urban areas of all sizes by taking innovative action, building capacity and knowledge, developing policies, and communicating about sustainable urban development. [External link](#)

Partners search

- The partner search tool helps you find partners for your project among the many participants of past EU projects. You will be able to select an organisation based on their profile or their previous participation. [External link](#)

Support networks

- **Social Innovation Match:** The Social Innovation Match (SIM) tool is a platform that allows users to explore successful social innovation initiatives and connect with potential partners. [External link](#)
- **URBACT.** URBACT It is a European exchange and learning Programme that promotes sustainable urban development. Integrating economic, social, and environmental dimensions, it enables cities to collaborate in developing pragmatic and sustainable solutions to major urban challenges. [External](#)

[link](#)

- **International Urban and Regional Cooperation (IURC).** The International Urban and Regional Cooperation Programme (IURC) involves working together to address shared urban and territorial challenges, paying particular attention to the green and digital transitions, and ensuring an inclusive post-pandemic recovery. [External link](#)
- **REGIO Peer2Peer +.** The REGIO Peer2Peer+ scheme allows staff from Programme authorities and other public bodies responsible for managing and implementing ERDF, CF, and JTF Programmes to meet and share knowledge and best practice at both bilateral and multilateral levels. [External link](#)

REFERENCE LIST

- Banco de España. (2023). Annual Report 2023. Chapter 4 The Spanish housing market: recent changes, risks, and affordability problems. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.bde.es/f/webbe/SES/Secciones/Publicaciones/PublicacionesAnuales/InformesAnuales/23/Files/InfAnual_2023_Cap4_En.pdf](https://www.bde.es/f/webbe/SES/Secciones/Publicaciones/PublicacionesAnuales/InformesAnuales/23/Files/InfAnual_2023_Cap4_En.pdf)
- BSC, K. R. (2024). IN-HABIT Deliverable D2.3 Monitoring and evaluation of VIS for IHW in Riga. Midterm report.
- Cristina Garita, U. of C., & Sergio Vegas, E. (n.d.). IN-HABIT IMMERSIVE EXPERIENCE - MANUAL DE ACOMPAÑAMIENTO AL USUARIO.
- Cycling Industries Europe. (2024a). Shared ambition: benchmarking bike sharing in 148 cities. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://cyclingindustries.com/fileadmin/CIE_Bike_Sharing_2024_Report.pdf](https://cyclingindustries.com/fileadmin/CIE_Bike_Sharing_2024_Report.pdf)
- Cycling Industries Europe. (2024b). Shared ambition: benchmarking bike sharing in 148 cities - Supplement. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://cyclingindustries.com/fileadmin/CIE_Bike_Sharing_2024_-_Supplement.pdf](https://cyclingindustries.com/fileadmin/CIE_Bike_Sharing_2024_-_Supplement.pdf)
- EFSA. (2022). Special Eurobarometer Wave EB97.2 Food safety in the EU 'Food safety in the EU', Report. <https://doi.org/10.2805/729388>
- European Commission. (2020). Farm to Fork Strategy. For a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system. https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-05/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf
- European Commission. (2019). IN-HABIT Grant Agreement.
- European Commission. (2024a). IN-HABIT Grant Agreement amendment.
- European Commission. (2024b). Key figures on European living conditions – 2024 edition. <https://doi.org/10.2785/8635485>
- European Commission: Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy, D. D. L. , B. F. , d'Hombres, B. , G. C. et al. . (2023). Report on the quality of life in European cities, 2023. In Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2776/182815>
- European Commission: Joint Research Centre, Benczur, P., Boskovic, A., Giovannini, E., & Sandor A. (2025). Measuring sustainable and inclusive wellbeing: a multidimensional dashboard approach. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/4186342>
- Eurostat. (2022a). Data Browser. Online data code: URB_LIVCON. European Commission. [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/ bookmark/343cd400-1177-403c-9fbb-30e076fe1ed0?lang=en](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/bookmark/343cd400-1177-403c-9fbb-30e076fe1ed0?lang=en)

- Eurostat. (2022b). Key figures on the European food chain 2022 edition. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/15216629/15559935/KS-FK-22-001-EN-N.pdf/1cb9d295-6868-70e3-0319-4725040cfdb8?version=3.0&t=1670599965263>
- FAO, I. U. W. and WHO. (2023). The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2023. Urbanization, agrifood systems transformation and healthy diets across the rural–urban continuum. In F. Rome (Ed.), The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2023. FAO; IFAD; UNICEF; WFP; WHO; <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc3017en>
- FEDIAF. (2025). 2025 facts & figures: Based on aggregated data from 2023. <https://www.europeanpetfood.org/>
- FoodDrinkEurope's. (2024). Data & Trends of the European food and drink industry 2024. <https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/FoodDrinkEurope-Data-Trends-2024.pdf>
- Francesco Di Iacovo (UNIFI), Massimo Rovai (UNIFI), Chiara Mariti (UNIFI), & Roberta Moruzzo (UNIFI). (2022). IN-HABIT Deliverable D 3.1. Inclusive Transformation Plan of Lucca.pdf.
- Giacomo Arrighini (ISIM), Sveva Batani (ISIM), Roberta Cocchioni (ISIM), Monica D'Arcangelis (ISIM), Maria Dentale (ISIM), Paola Di Lazzaro (ISIM), Helen Dodd (UREAD/Exeter), Rachel Mc Cloy (UREAD), Cristiana Russo (ISIM), & Shannon Wake (UREAD). (2022). IN-HABIT Deliverable D7.3 Baseline study on IHW report.
- Intellectual Property Organization WIPO, W. (2021). WIPO Technology Trends 2021: Assistive Technology. <https://doi.org/10.34667/tind.42582>
- Katarína Melichová (SUA), Soňa Bellerová (SUA), Sandra Šubertová (SUA), Michal Hrivnák (SUA), & Jana Popovicsová (HIDE). (2022). IN-HABIT Deliverable D 4.1. Inclusive transformation plan on Nitra.
- Küster, F. (2024). The state of national cycling strategies in Europe (2024). https://www.ecf.com/media/resources/2024/The-State-of-National-Cycling-Strategies-in-Europe-2024_ECF_final%20241212.pdf
- María del Mar DELGADO-SERRANO, Catalina CRUZ-PIEDRAHITA, & Francisco Javier MARTÍNEZ-CARRANZA. (2024). IN-HABIT Deliverable D1.3. - Monitoring and evaluation VIS for IHW in Córdoba. Midterm report.
- Michael Kinyanjui. (2024). Evaluating the Impacts of Urban Policies A Guide for Urban Policy Leaders Evaluating the Impacts of Urban Policies: A Guide for Urban Policy Leaders. www.unhabitat.org/ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS
- OECD. (2023). Policies for the Future of Farming and Food in Spain (OECD Agriculture and Food Policy Reviews). OECD Agriculture and Food Policy Reviews, OECD Publishing, Paris., <https://doi.org/10.1787/a93d26be-en>
- OECD. (2024). How's Life? 2024: Well-being and Resilience in Times of Crisis (How's Life?). OECD

Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/90ba854a-en>

- OECD Urban Studies. (2025). The Circular Economy in Cities and Regions of the European Union (O. P. P. OECD Urban Studies, Ed.). OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/e09c21e2-en>
- Osterwalder, A. et al. (2004). The business model ontology: A proposition in a design science approach. PhD Thesis, University of Lausanne, Switzerland.
- Pet Alliance Europe. (n.d.). Human-animal bond: PetPower. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-023-01544-9>
- Rogier van den Berg, L. G. I. T. (n.d.). Urban planning and design labs tools for integrated and participatory urban planning (P. S. S. N. UNON, Ed.). www.unhabitat.org
- WHO. (2021). Safe and healthy food in traditional food markets in the WHO European Region, March 2021, WHO/EURO:2021-1854-41605-56825. <https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/WHO-EURO-2021-1854-41605-56825>
- Winkle, M. , R. J. , G. P. , and V. D. (2022). Animal Assisted Intervention International Public Document: Standards of Practice and Competencies for Animal Assisted Interventions. aai-int.org
- World Economic Forum. (2016). Inspiring Future Cities & Urban Services Shaping the Future of Urban Development & Services Initiative. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>
- World Economic Forum. (2017). Collaboration in Cities: From Sharing to ‘Sharing Economy’. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>
- World Economic Forum. (2018a). Circular Economy in Cities Evolving the model for a sustainable urban future. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>
- World Economic Forum. (2018b). Innovation with a Purpose: The role of technology innovation in accelerating food systems transformation. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>
- World Economic Forum. (2021). How Mobility Shapes Inclusion and Sustainable Growth in Global Cities. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>
- World Economic Forum. (2022a). Accelerating Urban Inclusion for a Just Recovery. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/accelerating-urban-inclusion-for-a-just-recovery/>
- World Economic Forum. (2022b). BiodiverCities by 2030: Transforming cities’ relationship with nature. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/biodivercities-by-2030-transforming-cities-relationship-with-nature/>
- World Economic Forum. (2022c). Rethinking City Revenue and Finance. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>
- World Economic Forum. (2022d). Transforming Food Systems: Pathways for Country-led Innovation. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>
- World Economic Forum. (2022e). Unlocking the Shared Value of Smart City Data: A Protocol for

Action. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>

- World Economic Forum. (2023a). Defining Education 4.0: A Taxonomy for the Future of Learning. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>
- World Economic Forum. (2023b). Nature Positive: Role of the Household and Personal Care Products Sector. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>
- World Economic Forum. (2024). Improving Social Outcomes in Urban Development: A Playbook for Practitioners. <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>

IN-HABIT REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

D1.1: Inclusive Transformation Plan, Las Palmeras

D1.3: Monitoring and Evaluation of VIS for IHW in Córdoba

D1.5: Upscaling Plan of Las Palmeras

D2.1: Inclusive Transformation Plan of the Āgenskalns Market Area in Riga

D2.3: Monitoring and Evaluation of VIS for IHW in Riga

D3.1: Inclusive Transformation Plan of Lucca

D3.3: Monitoring and Evaluation of VIS for IHW in Lucca

D4.1 Inclusive Transformation Plan of Nitra

D4.3 – Monitoring and evaluation VIS for IHW in Nitra

D7.3: Baseline study on IHW report

D7.6: IN-HABIT Full Operative Data Platform

D5.1 Toolkit for Stakeholders' Engagement with a Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Perspective

D5:3: Final Report of the Inclusive Business Incubation Programme

D8.14: Market Analysis and Preliminary Exploitation Strategies